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Executive summary

Conventional fossil-based plastic packaging poses significant environmental challenges, including resource depletion and microplastic pollution. As part of the EU Horizon Europe–funded ViSS project, this deliverable D6.10 presents the second iteration of the interim sustainable by design (SSbD) assessment of a novel bio-based alternative: poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) produced from food industry residues through microbial fermentation. Building on the baseline established in D6.7 (M18), the present assessment covers the environmental, economic, and social sustainability dimensions of the ViSS value chain, and applies the ViSS scoring system, which benchmarks the performance of the ViSS solution against market references. The security dimension is addressed in D6.9 (Interim safety by design assessment), also presented at M33.

In the **environmental dimension**, the LCA results show that the current ViSS PHBV production system still generates higher impacts than the fossil polypropylene benchmark across all assessed categories. However, the trajectory between iterations tells a more relevant story: targeted process redesign — including elimination of the VFA separation step, solvent reduction, and implementation of recirculation strategies — produced impact reductions of 75–93% in most categories relative to the initial design. Recommendations focus on continuing the optimisation of chemical inputs and energy efficiency as the process transitions to demo scale. The use and end-of-life phases will be incorporated in D6.15.

In the **economic dimension**, the total production cost of 2,206 €/kg reflects the inherent inefficiencies of demo-scale operation and should not be interpreted as indicative of commercial viability. A 99.3% cost reduction was achieved between D6.7 and D6.10, driven by process improvements and functional unit corrections. Labour, raw materials, and equipment together account for 87% of total costs, identifying the priority areas for efficiency gains as the system scales. A comparison with conventional products will be conducted in D6.15 when data maturity permits.

In the **social dimension**, results are encouraging, with strong performance in the Workers category: wages, full-time employment rates, and collective bargaining coverage all perform above national reference values, and no fundamental labour rights violations were identified. The S-LCA, introduced as a product-level track at D6.10, adds important nuance: community grievance mechanisms are absent in two organisations, public sustainability reporting is absent across all three, and regional sourcing and local employment remain areas for improvement. These findings provide both immediate corrective actions for current consortium organisations and social performance standards to guide future value chain participants.

Complementary to the LCA-based environmental evaluation, a **circularity monitoring** assessment was conducted through a targeted literature review of existing frameworks for bio-based and plastic food packaging. A limited number of applicable frameworks were identified; key principles from these were used to define a set of quantitative circularity indicators for the ViSS PHBV system, organised into three relevance tiers: recommended, potentially relevant, and contextual metrics. The framework will be iteratively refined as the project progresses and operational data becomes available.

Overall, the ViSS solution shows a clear improvement trajectory across all environmental, economic and social dimensions, and the SSbD framework has proven well-suited to the objectives of the project. In that sense, together with D6.8 (Third integration and assessment of data in ICT Platform) and D6.9 (Interim safety by design assessment), this deliverable contributes to the verification of

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Milestone 7 (PHBV compounds processable and validated for target packaging applications, and end-of-life scenarios demonstrated), **Milestone 8** (ViSS demo plant built and start-up and SSbD safe strategies implemented), **Milestone 9** (Social readiness and marketability) and **Milestone 10** (First batch of PHBV range from Demo plant) and to **Specific Objective 9** (To increase and demonstrate Safety & Sustainability across the ViSS value chain and to create an enabling framework) of the ViSS DoA.

MS7 and MS8 are supported by the sustainability evidence base for the PHBV value chain and demo plant operation at M33, including the SSbD redesign recommendations that constitute the "SSbD safe strategies" referred to in the DoA. MS9 is supported by the social assessment, which establishes a quantitative social readiness baseline across five stakeholder categories. MS10 is supported by the process and cost data confirming the operational status of the demo plant production chain at M33. With respect to SO9, D6.10 constitutes the second application of the SSbD evaluation framework established in D6.3, demonstrating through measurable improvements across all three dimensions that the iterative assessment mechanism is functioning as intended.

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List of abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
A2C	Agro2Circular
BREF	Best Available Techniques Reference
CED	Cumulative energy demand
cSbD	Sustainability costing by design
eLCA	Environmental Life Cycle Assessment
eLCC	Environmental Life Cycle Costing
eSbD	Environmental sustainability by design
GHS	Globally Harmonized System
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative
GWP	Global warming potential
ILO	International Labour Organization
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
NGIB	Next-Generation Industrial Biotechnology
OEF	Organisation Environmental Footprint
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
S-SbD	Social sustainability by design
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SO-LCA	Social Organizational Life Cycle Assessment
SSbD	Safe and sustainable by design
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
VFA	Volatile Fatty Acid

1 Introduction

Conventional plastics pose major environmental challenges due to their dependence on fossil resources and the negative impacts associated with their end-of-life, including persistent microplastic pollution. Substituting fossil-based plastic food packaging with bio-based and biodegradable alternatives is therefore critical for reducing the environmental footprint of the food system and for advancing a circular bio-economy. Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) is a promising biopolymer for food packaging applications, produced through a microbial fermentation process that uses food industry residues as feedstock. The EU Horizon Europe–funded ViSS project aims to establish a safe, sustainable, fully functional, and highly replicable PHBV value chain, employing multiple circular economy strategies including the utilisation of industrial food waste as feedstock and designing the packaging for both recyclability and biodegradability.

Central to this ambition is the application of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework, which integrates both safety and sustainability evaluation directly into the product development cycle. Rather than assessing these dimensions as a post-hoc verification exercise, the SSbD approach embeds iterative assessment throughout the research and development process, with the explicit purpose of generating **actionable design recommendations** at each stage of technological maturity. The present deliverable, D6.10, focuses on the sustainability dimensions — environmental (LCA), economic (LCC), and social (S-LCA and SO-LCA); the safety dimension is assessed in parallel and reported in D6.9 (Interim safety by design assessment).

The ViSS SSbD framework was established in D6.3 (SSbD and Social Readiness evaluation framework), where all the methodological steps are described. Building on the baseline established in D6.7 (First sustainable by design assessment), D6.10 constitutes the second iteration of the ViSS sustainability assessment and the first conducted at intermediate TRL (TRL 5–6), as illustrated in Figure 1. As an interim assessment, its primary objective is not to produce definitive conclusions about the sustainability performance of the ViSS solution, but to identify concrete improvement opportunities across the three sustainability dimensions that can inform the redesign of processes, practices, and value chain configurations before the final assessment (D6.15, M47). Each dimension assessed contributes to this shared purpose, providing dimension-specific findings and recommendations that feed into the integrated SSbD evaluation.

Figure 1. VISS sustainability assessment iterations within the SSbD evaluation framework

A scoring system aligned with the latest JRC recommendations (European Commission, 2022) is applied across the environmental and social dimensions (Figure 2). Scores range from 0 to 4, represented by a colour scale from red (0) to blue (4). Indicators scoring 0 or 1 signal performance below an adequate level — either falling short of the market reference

Figure 2. Scoring system

(environmental dimension) or not meeting the minimum performance threshold defined for each indicator (social dimension) — and identify priority areas for improvement. Scores of 2, 3, or 4 indicate adequate or better performance, reflecting results at or above the reference or threshold level. The applicability of this scoring system to the economic dimension will be evaluated in D6.13, as it is contingent on the availability of sufficiently mature cost data and on the definition of an appropriate market benchmark for comparison. Assessment results will be incorporated into the ViSS ICT Tool (D6.8, Third integration and assessment of data in ICT Platform).

The **current TRL stage** shapes what can and cannot be assessed across all three sustainability dimensions. With ViSS solutions currently at TRL 5–6, the present assessment corresponds to an Intermediate SSbD assessment in line with EC indications (European Commission, 2022), meaning that not all product characteristics can yet be fully evaluated. **Data availability** remains constrained beyond design and laboratory scale, the number of identified benchmarks available for comparison is limited, and **lifecycle coverage is partial** — the phases for which sufficient primary data exist are assessed, while others await data availability as the project progresses. Additionally, some value chain actors that will eventually participate in the commercial PHBV value chain are not yet operational at scale and are therefore not included in this iteration. These are not limitations of the methodology but characteristics of where the ViSS solution stands in its development trajectory. The assessments presented here are designed to extract the maximum useful signal from currently

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available data, and each dimension-specific section includes explicit guidance on what to address, improve, or expand in the next iteration.

Complementary to the assessment of the three sustainability dimensions within the SSbD framework, this deliverable addresses circularity as a transversal design objective rather than as a separate evaluation dimension. Circularity is already embedded in several core design choices of the ViSS value chain — the use of food industry residues as feedstock, the design of packaging for both recyclability and biodegradability, and the development of a PHBV-specific sorting protocol — and has direct implications for environmental, economic and social performance. Improving circularity is therefore not an end in itself but a means of strengthening the sustainability profile of the ViSS solution across all three dimensions. As at the current TRL, a comprehensive quantitative circularity assessment is not yet feasible, this deliverable presents a structured literature review to identify suitable monitoring frameworks and define a set of circularity indicators and monitoring priorities for the ViSS PHBV system, with the aim of building a robust evidence base that will feed into the final assessment at D6.15.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the ViSS value chain and the organisations involved. Sections 3, 4, and 5 present the results of the environmental, economic, and social assessments respectively. Section 6 presents the circularity monitoring framework developed for the ViSS PHBV product system, including the indicator set and monitoring priorities identified through a targeted literature review. Section 7 consolidates the key recommendations for redesign and improvement emerging from the environmental, economic and social assessments conducted within the ViSS SSbD framework, together with the circularity monitoring actions identified in Section 6 and the methodological improvements to be implemented in the final assessment (D6.15, M47). Section 8 presents the overall conclusions.

2 ViSS value chain

ViSS value chain covers, in M33 of the project, all the production process from the collection of bones and feathers from poultry and sugar rich liquor waste to the production of 1kg of raw PHBV. The process and system boundaries of the assessed PHBV system compared to the benchmark PP system are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Process chart of ViSS PHBV system and benchmark fossil polypropylene system.

The partners that are involved in this value chain and have provided data for the sustainability assessment are CETEC, CETBIO and IRIS:

- **IRIS** is an advanced engineering company (SME) specialized in the manufacture and integration of Process Analytical Technology (PAT)-based real-time quality monitoring solutions for the process industries. IRIS will lead the production of volatile fatty acids (VFAs) (as feedstocks for the PHBV range production) from sugar residues by an innovative technology, including the process optimisation and scale up to the PHBV demo plant. Moreover, IRIS has a vast experience in the development of photonic solutions for plastics sorting. In ViSS, IRIS develops a protocol sorting to allow the identification and sorting of the new PHBV packaging in the future recycling facilities.
- **CETBIO** is a SME focused on the production of PHBV, a biopolymer from the polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) family, by using next-generation industrial biotechnology (NGIB) strategies. They develop the PHBV production from residues, including the processes (fermentation, downstream) optimisation and support in the start-up & operation of the PHBV production demo plant. Moreover, they will oversee the PHBV formulation scale up to achieve a stable PHBV range.
- **CETEC** (Project Coordinator) is a Technological Centre specialized in plastics and bioplastics with a broad experience in project management (6 H2020/HE projects coordinated). CETEC leads the technical activities linked to PHBV bioplastic behaviour for flexible packaging developed by extrusion and thermoforming, leading the eco-design approach. Moreover, CETEC develops the ICT platform and leads the engineering and construction of the PHBV production plant (Demo1). It also assists other partners as Project Coordinator.

3 Environmental assessment

This interim life cycle assessment expands the assessment provided in D6.7. The assessment continues to follow ISO 14040-44 standards (ISO 14040¹, ISO 14044²) and assess the same 16 different environmental impacts suggested in the European commission’s Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) guideline (European Commission, 2024). Similarly following the SSbD framework, the environmental impacts are grouped into toxicity, climate change, pollution, and resource use (European Commission, 2022). See Table 1.

The environmental sustainability in the SSbD framework is based on the life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology which is commonly used and standardized with ISO 14040-44 standards (ISO 14040, ISO 14044). LCA comprises of four stages, namely goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory, life cycle impact assessment and interpretation of the results, which are interlinked and iterative.

Table 1 The categories in eSbD design and the corresponding aspects with units assessed in eSbD

<i>eSbD category</i>	<i>Aspects (Impact category)</i>	<i>Unit</i>
<i>Toxicity</i>	Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh
	Human toxicity, non cancer	CTUh
	Ecotoxicity	CTUe
<i>Climate change</i>	Climate change	kg CO ₂ -eq
<i>Pollution</i>	Ozone depletion	kg CFC ⁻¹¹ -eq
	Particulate matter	disease incidence
	Ionizing radiation	kBq U ₂₃₅ -eq
	Photochemical ozone formation	kg NM _{VOC} -eq
	Acidification	mol H ⁺ -eq
	Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N-eq
	Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P-eq
	Eutrophication, marine	kg N-eq
<i>Resources</i>	Water use	m ³ world eq deprived
	Land use	
	Resource use, fossil	MJ, net calorific value
	Resource use, minerals, and metals	kg Sb-eq
	Cumulative energy demand (CED) ¹	MJ oil-eq./m ² a

According to the *Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials framework* (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2022b), the performance of the assessed product is evaluated against a reference i.e. benchmark product as the reduction of the impacts. The benchmark is kept the same as in the first LCA iteration.

¹ ISO, ‘ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework’. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html>

² ISO, ‘ISO 14044:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines’. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/38498.html>

In contrast to first iteration, the system boundary in interim assessment is expanded to cover the electricity usage. CETBIO was able to estimate demo scale production and improvements to production efficiency have also been made, thus mass balances differ from the first assessment as well. However, opposed to initial plans, the system boundary is still restricted to cradle-to-raw PHBV since the molding etc. was not mature enough to produce estimates. The more detailed description of the interim assessment system boundary and assumptions is given in Section 2.

3.1 Case description

LCA is carried out to evaluate the value chain of ViSS PHBV bioplastic. Currently, ViSS production has been partly moved to demo scale production. The process chart of current production is shown in Figure 6. The principles of ViSS value chain have remained the same.

In this interim LCA, mass and energy balance are included in the assessment. The system boundary is still set from cradle to gate of the production of 1kg raw PHBV, which was also set as functional unit of this calculation. The ViSS project has progressed so far, that in this iteration water and chemical recycling were included the assessment. Due to the first iteration LCA results, the production chain has been redesigned. Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) are not separated anymore but are used as they are in the PHBV fermentation. Implementation of salty brine circulation and chemical purification rounds decreased the chemical usage notably. The process chart is shown in Figure 3.

Similarly to first iteration, the transportation of materials used in production are included in the ecoinvent version 3.10 (2023)² market for -datasets utilized in the assessment. The emission factor data was taken from ecoinvent 3.10 database and Sulca 5.3³ was used for modelling with EF3.1 LCA methodology.

Due to the still developing nature of the ViSS process, there are some limitations and uncertainties regarding the interim assessment (see Section 7.1). For the VFA production, energy demand was estimated based on literature data for similar processes. No changes were made to burden free assumptions on wastes and for some chemicals proxies were used or they were modelled based on stoichiometric formula. The detailed list of impact factors used are in Annex 1.

The benchmark product was kept the same as in first iteration: A fossil-based polypropylene (PP). It has characteristics and applications similar to those of PHBV and it dominates the market. Benchmark LCIA values were obtained from “market for polypropylene, granulate, GLO” dataset from Ecoinvent 3.10 database. The benchmark product consists fully of virgin material of fossil origin. The SSbD framework proposes using best-available-tech and PP is it. However, the PP production benchmark is of highly optimised industrial scale production, and thus comparison reflects partly just process maturity than intrinsic material performance.

3.2 Results

The results of interim sustainability assessment are dominated by impact categories climate impacts, energy resources and material resources (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Normalised and weighted interim results by impact categories.

The contribution analysis for the ViSS PHBV enriched biomass for all studied impact categories is shown in Figure 5. In most of the impact categories, the most important life cycle stage is PHBV fermentation (Figure 5a). Substrate preparation dominated the land-use impact due to fodder yeast, and solid-liquid extraction dominates Ozone depletion. When looking at the source of impacts (Figure 5b) both electricity and chemical usage create half of the impacts. From individual inputs, glycol, sodium chloride, formaldehyde and IRIS culture media ingredient 2 are the most impactful chemicals (Figure 5c).

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Figure 5abc Contribution analysis by life cycle stages (a), broad category (b) and inputs (c) of ViSS raw PHBV.

The magnitude of impacts compared to benchmark are shown in Table 2. In the table, in addition to results for first and interim assessment, there are results for Solvent reduced design. Solvent reduced design iteration refers to assessment which was done soon after first iteration as an intermediate progress check. After D6.7 was submitted, IRIS optimized solvent usage in VFA production and decreased the use of solvent. The Solvent reduced design is otherwise a copy of first assessment, but accounts for reduced solvent usage.

Redesigning the solvent usage caused a 75-93% reduction in impacts compared to first iteration. When redesigns were continued with removing VFA separation steps completely and implementing recirculation, the impacts decreased further by 40-90% despite expanding the system boundary to cover electricity usage as well. When looking at the chemical usage only, its impacts decreased by 93-98% depending on the impact category even from the Solvent reduced design iteration. The impacts in category Ionizing radiation expectedly increased due to added electricity and nuclear energy in it.

However, the ViSS production impacts at the current TRL are still 13-344 times higher than of benchmark fossil polypropylene (PP) and therefore score 0 in all impact categories.

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Table 2 Magnitude ViSS product impact from different LCA iterations compared to benchmark polypropylene product (ecoinvent 3.10). The cells are highlighted with red if the impact of ViSS product is greater than the benchmark value and thus is score 0.

		Magnitude compared to benchmark			SSbD score
		ViSS raw PHBV			
		First assessment Lab scale	Solvent reduced design Lab scale	Interim assessment Demo scale	
Toxicity	human toxicity: carcinogenic	1788	133	25	0
	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic	1021	116	42	0
	ecotoxicity: freshwater	2926	198	13	0
Climate change	climate change	783	70	18	0
Pollution	ozone depletion	599	42	17	0
	particulate matter formation	929	101	14	0
	ionising radiation	485	88	344	0
	photochemical oxidant formation	577	62	16	0
	acidification	825	121	26	0
	eutrophication: terrestrial	1096	173	26	0
	eutrophication: freshwater	630	92	22	0
eutrophication: marine	3104	260	27	0	
Resources	water use	1828	307	41	0
	land use (soil quality index)	7027	1322	113	0
	energy resources: non-renewable	384	33	20	0
	material resources: metals/minerals	716	179	60	0

Despite the notable improvements in chemical usage efficiency, VISS PHBV still performs notably worse across all impact categories when compared to benchmark, fossil polypropylene.

3.3 Redesign opportunities

Together with each technical partner, redesign needs were discussed and potential solutions were identified. This assessment reflects plans prior start of the demo plant production. Electricity efficiency is kept in mind when purchasing equipments for demo plant. The process is now quite optimized given current economic and technical constraints, but further redesign possibilities for chemical and water recirculation and fermentation yields are still studied in ViSS project. In order to lower the impacts within the scope of the project, non-carbon electricity sources should be considered. The demo plant has solar panels to provide at least some part of the electricity. Efficiency gains are expected to be achieved when moving large scale production: Industrial scale equipments are more energy efficient and better optimized.

4 Economic assessment

As presented in the framework (D6.3) and the first economic sustainability analysis (D6.7), LCC methodology involves a thorough economic assessment of all the costs associated with a product (an asset, product, or service) throughout its entire life cycle and for all the actors of the value chain. This includes the acquisition of raw materials, moving through processing and maintenance, and ending with final disposal or product delivery, all within a defined time frame.

The implementation of the LCC follows a four-step process (Figure 6) that starts with setting the objectives and reach, then assess the estimated costs, aggregate them and, finally, interpret the results and inform the process from the economic perspective.

Figure 6 LCC four-step process (adapted from Ihobe, 2017)

In LCC methodology, the cost-effectiveness of alternative product or processes, considering all relevant economic factors both in terms of initial costs and future operational costs, are assessed to determine the most efficient. Therefore, LCC methodology is used to identify the impact of products and services to select the best alternatives. Several guidelines and standards have been developed to assess this: **Dependability management** (IEC 60300-3-3:2017³ - Part 3-3: Application guide - Life cycle costing), **Petroleum and natural gas industries** (ISO 15663-2021 (ISO, 2021) – Life cycle costing), **Standard Practice for Life Cycle Cost** (ASTM F2687-13(2019)⁴ - Analysis of Commercial Food Service Equipment), and **Environmental impacts** (ISO 14008:2019 (ISO, 2019) - Monetary evaluation).

³ <https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/31206>

⁴ <https://www.astm.org/f2687-13r19.html>

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VISS LCC follows the environmental LCC (eLCC) which relies on the basic life cycle perspective of the LCA and its output. The eLCC includes the monetization of the environmental impacts linked to each life cycle step of the products (see Section 6.4.7). For doing so, specific methods are used and internal cost assessed in the conventional LCC (cLCC) will be included. VISS LCC also includes the assessment of external costs to meet eLCC requirements. In addition, the possibility of undertaking a sLCC for the final economic sustainability assessment will be explored.

Deliverable 6.10 presents the associated economic conventional costs (cLCC) and environmental costs (eLCC) over the entire life cycle of the **innovative PHBV value chain for food packaging applications** (as in Month 33 of the project) (Section 6.4.8 proposes a summary tables of the total costs identified) and compare with the conventional product already found in the market (Section 6.4.9). VISS LCC is framed by D6.3 *SSbD and Social Readiness evaluation framework* which has set the overarching principles, aspects and indicators initially targeted by the assessment. As previously mentioned, the eLCC considers the conventional costs and the monetization of environmental externalities evaluated in the LCA (Section 4).

The definition of a **functional unit** is essential in Life Cycle Assessment as it works as a common reference unit that allows us to relate and compare the inputs and outputs involved in the solution. The eLCC uses the same functional unit defined for the LCA and it covers the function, quantity, duration and degree of quality of ViSS solution. The objective being to have a coherent analysis across these two sustainability dimensions.

At the present stage of the project in ViSS the functional unit is used is **1kg of raw PHBV** (Table 3).

Table 3 ViSS solution and conventional solution for comparison

ViSS solution	Conventional solution	Functional unit
Innovative PHBV value chain for food packaging	Conventional food packaging	1kg of raw PHBV

The characterisation of the system boundaries is also essential in LCC. ViSS system boundaries (see Section 2) defined for the LCA include the condition of the input for their fermentation to the PHBV drying for later elaboration of the food packaging; therefore, a portion of the final cradle-to-gate approaches. At the present stage of the project, this includes (see Figure 5 representing ViSS value chain):

- Hydrolysis
- Conditioning
- Fermentation
- Separation
- PHBV production
- Separation of PHBV
- Drying
- Solid-liquid extraction
- Solvent recuperation
- PHBV drying

This second assessment is, given the nature of the state of the project, preliminary but it informs as accurately as possible the costs associated to the production of ViSS solutions. The final assessment will be undertaken the analysis considering the final data available.

4.1 Inventory & procedure methodology

As presented in D6.7 and above, ViSS eLCC follows the same structure of the LCA with the objective of including the environmental externalities. The cost data in this assessment consist in primary data retrieved from the real case study when it exists within ViSS value chain (Table 4).

Table 4 Costs considered for ViSS LCC in M33

Raw material cost	Acquisition of waste stream input	
Production cost (other inputs and operating costs)	Water	Water consumption cost for the facility and systems
	Energy	Energy consumption cost for the facility and systems (including: electricity, thermal energy and natural gas used in the production process)
	Carbon dioxide to air	Associated cost to emitted carbon dioxide during the manufacturing process - <i>not included yet in the LCA</i>
	Transport	Cost of freight, cartage, transit insurance and cost of operating fleet and other incidental charges
	Equipment (capital cost)	Purchase cost associated with the equipment necessary to the production
	Installation	Cost of installing the systems and equipment
	Maintenance	Cost of maintaining the production capacity of the facility and equipment
	Labour cost	Needed man-hours associated with production
	Environmental costs	Associated environmental costs identified and quantified

4.2 Data gathering and data assumptions

The data gathered for ViSS eLCC is, as mentioned above, primary data collected by the means of questionnaires to the three organizations involved in ViSS value chain. The collection of this data has been undertaken by KVC in months 29-30 of the project using tables such as presented in Figure 7. The collected data correspond to each stage of the project (Hydrolysis, Conditioning, Fermentation, Separation, PHBV production, Separation of PHBV, Drying, Solid-liquid extraction, Solvent recuperation and PHBV drying) (see Section 6.1.1).

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Purchase costs of raw materials (inputs) (assumption of purchase cost of raw materials)

Is there a purchase cost of raw materials at this stage? Yes/No

Input	Amount	Unit	Cost (€)	Concerned value chain stage	Observations
TOTAL			0		

Transport costs of materials (inputs - outputs)

Is there an associated transport cost of materials? Yes/No

Transport service	Service costs (€)	Service cost per ton	Observation
TOTAL		0	

Transport service	Service costs (€)	Service cost per ton	Observation
TOTAL		0	

Energy costs

Is there an energy associated cost? Yes/No

< >
TOTAL
Hydrolysis - bones
Conditioning - candies
Fermentation
Separation of propionic acid
Purification
PHBV production
Separation of PHBV enr. bic

Figure 7 Example of data collection questionnaire for ViSS eLCC

ViSS eLCC data are assessed considering the following assumptions (developed in D6.7):

Service Life of the product and period of analysis:

The service life of a product is crucial for LCC, as it determines the timeframe for accounting all costs. For ViSS food packaging, a one-year service life is standard, while sectors like automotive or construction require much longer lifespans. The period of analysis—the time horizon studied—may be shorter than the service life, especially in construction, and is vital for calculating residual value (the asset’s worth at analysis end). For disposable ViSS solutions, the analysis period equals the service life, resulting in zero residual value. Both metrics are essential for accurate LCC assessments.

Discount rate and inflation rate:

In eLCC, the discount rate and inflation rate significantly impact investment costs. The discount rate converts future expenses to present value, reflecting expected returns. For ViSS food packaging, with its short (≤ 1 year) lifespan and low unit cost, these rates are not applied. Both factors are more relevant for long-lived assets (e.g., buildings, vehicles), where inflation and time-value adjustments are critical. Thus, ViSS analysis simplifies by excluding these variables, focusing only on immediate costs.

Environmental externalities:

Environmental externalities convert a product’s ecological impacts into economic costs. For ViSS solutions, these are quantified using the Environmental Prices method, which monetizes impacts based on prevention costs. The LCA identifies negative externalities across the value chain, translating them into Euros. This approach ensures environmental burdens are financially measurable, aiding comprehensive cost-benefit analysis.

4.3 LCC implementation (interim): Results & conclusions

As presented in Section 6.1, ViSS LCC builds on the LCA (see Section 4) with the objective of assessing the conventional and environmental externality costs related to the input and output included in the LCA model. The total costs considered for assessment in the second LCC assessment are presented in Table 32.

4.3.1 Physical input and output conventional costs

ViSS LCC assesses the same categories as the LCA but focusing on the related costs. The assessed costs are the raw materials used, and the costs related to the materials outputs, the water consumed in the production process, and the carbon dioxide emitted into the air. The physical input and output conventional costs were collected as shown in Table 5. The total cost related to the material input for producing 1kg of raw PHBV is of 508.40 € in M32.

Table 5 Physical input and output conventional costs

Input*	Amount	Unit	Cost (€)	Concerned value chain stage	Owner - Observations
1	0.6	kg	1.45 €	Hydrolysis	1
2	720.00	g	271.67 €	Conditioning	3
3	576.00	g	59.03 €	Conditioning	3
4	9.00	mL	0.80 €	Conditioning	3
5	10.55	L	4.58 €	Conditioning	3
6	144.00	g	7.96 €	Conditioning	3
7	14-40	g	2.64 €	Conditioning	3
8	3.60	g	0.81 €	Conditioning	3
9	0.51	kg	0.40 €	PHBV production	2
10	0.24	kg	9.74 €	PHBV production	2
11	0.07	kg	0.21 €	PHBV production	2
12	2.1	kg	2.69 €	PHBV production	2
13	14.53	kg	11.48 €	PHBV production	2
14	10.13	kg	8.71 €	PHBV production	2
15	81.86	kg	31.92 €	PHBV production	2
16	21.875	L	71.31 €	Solid-liquid extraction	2
17	5	L	23.00 €	Solid-liquid extraction	2
			508.40 €		

*: The inputs used in ViSS process are not presented for confidentiality issues.

4.3.2 Energy costs

Energy cost estimated in ViSS LCC refer to the electricity needed for the different processes involved in ViSS value chain. To produce 1kg of raw PHBV the total cost linked to energy consumption (electricity) is of 42.09 € in M32 (Table 6).

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Table 6 Energy related costs

Used energy	Purchase costs (€)	Concerned value chain stage	Owner - Observations
30 kWh	4.07 €	Hydrolysis	1
1 kWh	0.2 €	Conditioning	3 - Agitation
6 kWh	2.4 €	Conditioning	3 - Sterilization
14.4 kWh	1.2 €	Fermentation	3 - Agitation
28.8 kWh	5.76 €	Fermentation	3 - Jacket (35 °C)
111.53 kWh	15.11 €	PHBV production	2
39.6 kWh	5.37 €	Separation of PHBV	2
12.6 kWh	1.71 €	Drying	2
13.5 kWh	1.83 €	Solid-liquid extraction	2
2.7 kWh	0.37 €	Solvent recuperation	2
20.4 kWh	4.07 €	PHBV drying	2
	42.09 €		

4.3.3 Transport costs

The transport costs are assessed and collected in the same fashion as physical input and output conventional costs in Table 7. These costs refer to the transport related costs of raw material and the transportation of materials between project partners for the different production stages. The total cost related to the transport for producing 1kg of raw PHBV is of 207.00 € in M32 and relates only to three value chain stages (hydrolysis, PHBV drying and Separation).

Table 7 Transport costs (inbound-outbound) involved in ViSS value chain

Transport	Amount	Unit	Cost (€)	Concerned value chain stage	Owner - Observations
Transport (raw material-poultry bones and feathers)	-	-	70.00 €	Hydrolysis	1
Transport (innovative PHBV from CETBIO to HP)	-	-	67.00 €	PHBV drying	2
Transport (from IRIS to CETEC)	-	-	70.00 €	Separation of Propionic	2
			207.00 €		

4.3.4 Equipment, installation and amortization costs

The equipment costs considered in ViSS LCC include the acquisition of the equipment, the installation costs as well as the amortization cost. The calculation methods will be defined once the equipment is effectively acquired and its use (production / year) and its lifespan are defined (Table 8). The total cost related to the equipment required for producing 1kg of raw PHBV is of 280.53 € in M32.

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Table 8 Equipment costs including related installation costs (until M32)

Equipment costs (including installation and amortization costs)	Cost (€) /unit	Cost/1kg PHBV (€)	Concerned value chain stage / process	Owner - Observations
100 L glass reactor	7,323.00 €	2.98 €	Hydrolysis	1
Vessel 100L	11,000.00 €	2.64€ (0.29€ / 1.76€ / 0.59€)	Conditioning / Fermentation / Separation	3 – Fermentation unit for propionic production
Control cabinet	8,000.00 €	1.92 € (0.21€ / 1.28€ / 0.43€)	Conditioning / Fermentation / Separation	3 – Fermentation unit for propionic production
Interheater	6,555.78 €	1.58 € (0,18 € / 1.05€ / 0.35 €)	Conditioning / Fermentation / Separation	3 – Fermentation unit for propionic production
2 bioreactors x 300L	48,385.50 €	202.54 €	PHBV production	1 - Bioreactor units including auxiliary and monitoring equipment
1 bioreactor x 30L	21,254.80 €	29.66 €	PHBV production	1 - Bioreactor units including auxiliary and monitoring equipment
1xTangential filtration unit	25,760.00 €	7.49 €	Separation of PHBV	1
100 L dry-evaporator	34,500.00 €	18.05 €	Drying	1
1xSoxhlet extractor	3,964.00 €	2.30 €	Solid-liquid extraction	1 - Used in three extraction processes
1xRotary evaporator	6,546.50 €	1.90 €	Solvent recuperation	1
1xDrying oven	6,790.00 €	9.47 €	PHBV drying	1
	194,523.80 €	280.53 €		

4.3.5 Maintenance costs

The maintenance costs are calculated on a yearly basis and include preventive maintenance activities and reparation costs (Table 9). These costs are linked to the equipment involved in ViSS value chain and they are calculated in the basis of the need to produce a functional unit. The total cost related to the maintenance of the equipment required for producing 1kg of raw PHBV is of 40.23 € in M32.

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Table 9 Maintenance costs included in ViSS eLCC

Maintenance costs	Cost (€)	Concerned value chain stage / process	Owner – Observations
Preventive and corrective maintenance/Pieces	3.60 €	Conditioning	3
Calibration sensors/Pieces	21.58 €	Fermentation	3
Cleaning/Pieces	7.19 €	Separation	3
Checking O-rings, pressure, membranes, and support discs	2.62 €	Separation of PHBV	1
Electric, hydraulic and safety tests	5.24 €	Drying	1
	40.23 €		

4.3.6 Labour costs

Labour costs are estimated considering the cost of the work effort in hours needed to produce 1 tonne of material (this will be translated into the labour costs needed to produce 1kg of material). The total labour cost required for producing 1kg of raw PHBV is of 1,127.90 € in M32 (Table 10).

Table 10 Labour costs included in ViSS eLCC

Labour costs	Cost (€)	Concerned value chain stage / process	Owner - Observations
1xPlant operator and 1xPlant supervisor	43.95 €	Hydrolysis	1 - 6 h per month
1 Employee	100.00 €	Conditioning	3 - 1 person - 25 euros per hour - 4 hour working hours per 1 kg PHBV
1 Employee	300.00 €	Fermentation	3 - 1 person - 25 euros per hour - 12 hour working hours per 1 kg PHBV
1 Employee	100.00 €	Separation	3 - 1 person - 25 euros per hour - 4 hour working hours per 1 kg PHBV
1xPlant operator and 1xPlant supervisor	326,51 €	PHBV fermentation	2 - 1 person - 25 euros per hour - 4 hour working hours per 1 kg PHBV
1xPlant operator and 1xPlant supervisor	69.07 €	Separation of PHBV	2 - 1 person - 25 euros per hour - 4 hour working hours per 1 kg PHBV
1xPlant operator and 1xPlant supervisor	52.33 €	Drying	2 - 1 person – 31.25 euros per hour - 4 hour working hours per 1 kg PHBV
1xPlant operator and 1xPlant supervisor	92.09 €	Solid-liquid extraction	2 - 1 person – 31.25 euros per hour - 4 hour working hours per 1 kg PHBV
1xPlant operator and 1xPlant supervisor	27.21 €	Solvent recuperation	2 - 1 person – 31.25 euros per hour - 4 hour working hours per 1 kg PHBV
1xPlant operator and 1xPlant supervisor	16.74 €	PHBV drying	2 - 1 person – 31.25 euros per hour - 4 hour working hours per 1 kg PHBV
	1,127.90 €		

4.3.7 Environmental costs

At the present stage of the production process (relatively low TRL) the information relative to the externality costs, environmental cost, is limited to the cost of managing a by-product of producing 1 kg of PHBV. The by-product identified are the salts derived from the production of the PHBV and linked to the Separation of PHBV value chain stage and the associated costs are the treatment of waste from salts used which sum 25.00 €.

4.3.8 Value chain: total eLCC

This section compiles the total costs for producing 1kg of raw PHBV (Sections 6.4.1 to 6.4.7). These costs are be combined in Table 11.

Table 11 Combined table for costs included in ViSS LCC

	Hydrolysis	Conditioning	Fermentation	Separation	PHBV production	Separation of PHBV	Drying	Solid-liquid extraction	Solvent recuperation	PHBV drying	Total per cost line
Raw material costs	1.45 €	347.49 €	- €	- €	65.15 €	- €	- €	94.31 €	- €	- €	508.40 €
Water	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	- €
Energy	4.07 €	2.60 €	6.96 €	- €	15.11 €	5.37 €	1.71 €	1.83 €	0.37 €	4.07 €	42.09 €
Carbon dioxide into the air	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	- €
Transport related costs (input-output)	70.00 €	- €	- €	70.00 €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	67.00 €	207.00 €
Equipment, installation and amortization costs	2.98 €	2.64 €	1.92 €	1.58 €	232.20 €	7.49 €	18.05 €	2.30 €	1.90 €	9.47 €	280.53 €
Maintenance costs	- €	3.60 €	21.58 €	7.19 €	- €	2.62 €	5.24 €	- €	- €	- €	40.23 €
Labour costs	43.95 €	100.00 €	300.00 €	100.00 €	326.51 €	69.07 €	52.33 €	92.09 €	27.21 €	16.74 €	1,127.90 €
Total conventional costs per process	122.45 €	456.33 €	330.46 €	178.77 €	638.97 €	84.55 €	77.33 €	190.53 €	29.48 €	97.28 €	2,206.15 €
Proportion of each process	5.6%	20.7%	15.0%	8.1%	29.0%	3.8%	3.5%	8.6%	1.3%	4.4%	100%

4.4 Key learnings and comparison with conventional products

The learnings presented in this section are the opportunity to produce recommendation for the redesign of ViSS solutions. In relation to the First assessment the total cost calculated in this second assessment is much lower (in the first assessment the total cost was of 304,915.7€, we can observe a reduction of 99.3%). This reduction is mainly due to the improvement of the production process that is more efficiency than in preliminary iterations, and the effective adjustments to the functional unit in the costs related to Equipment (which include the acquisition, the installation and the amortization costs) and Labour costs.

However, the total cost for producing 1kg of PHBV is still elevated. The main costs lines identified are, at this stage, Labour, Acquisition of raw material and Equipment costs, with 51.1%, 23.0% and 12.7% of the total cost respectively. The three most costly processes were PHBV production (29.0% of the total cost), Conditioning (20.7% of the total cost) and Fermentation (15.0% of the total cost). The three processes where the reduction of costs will be more impactful represent almost 65% of the total cost and the three most important cost lines summing up 87% of the total cost. Therefore, this provides valuable information on where the partners in ViSS value chain should prioritize the efforts to reduce the overall cost of producing the ViSS solution and to have production costs converging towards more conventional products. This information is shared with the partners in the value chain with the objective of help them identify the most strategic costs and improve the efficiency of the process.

The environmental externality costs are not yet considered in ViSS value chain. The only Environmental cost identified (25 € See 4.4.7.) represents so far 1.1% of the total cost. The final LCC will include a complete list of environmental costs. The implementation of the SSbD framework is reducing the externalities of ViSS solutions.

The comparison with conventional products, if possible, will be done in the final economic sustainability assessment (D6.15). In D6.15 we will present the comparison of total LCC assessed of raw PHBV against comparable products that can be found in the market. This is not yet presented in this second assessment due to the low TRL of ViSS solutions at the present stage.

This section presents the results of the social assessment conducted for the intermediate evaluation (M33), building on and extending the first assessment delivered in D6.7 (M18).

5.1.1 Evolution of the methodological approach: from SO-LCA to a dual-track framework

The first assessment (D6.7) applied a Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) approach, in which the unit of analysis is the organisation rather than the product. This choice was methodologically justified at the early TRL stage of the project: production processes were not yet sufficiently defined to enable product-level differentiation, product-specific data were limited, and the high level of uncertainty made an organisational-level characterisation of social risk the most reliable available option. Under SO-LCA, each organisation in the value chain is assessed independently and results are aggregated as a simple average across organisations, implicitly treating each as an equal contributor to the product regardless of its actual share of production activity.

As the project has progressed to M33 and TRL has increased, the conditions that justified a purely organisational approach have partially changed. The ViSS production system is now better defined: material inputs are clearer, process stages are identifiable, and worker-hour intensity per process has become estimable from primary data. This creates the methodological basis for introducing product-level differentiation as a complementary layer of analysis.

For D6.10, a product-level S-LCA track is therefore introduced alongside the SO-LCA. The two tracks are maintained in parallel, with a clear separation of purpose, and together provide a more complete and robust picture of the social sustainability of the ViSS value chain than either approach could offer alone.

The SO-LCA approach offers two distinct advantages in the context of the ViSS project. First, it enables longitudinal comparability: by maintaining a consistent indicator set and aggregation method across assessment iterations, the SO-LCA provides a stable baseline against which organisational-level social performance can be tracked from D6.7 through D6.10 to D6.15. This is particularly valuable for monitoring improvements in management practices and governance — areas where the recommendations issued at each iteration can translate into observable changes within a relatively short timeframe. An organisation that had no community grievance mechanism at D6.7 can have one by D6.15; an organisation without a formal sustainability reporting commitment can adopt one. Structural indicators — such as sector-level collective bargaining agreements, workforce composition, or the general regulatory environment — are less likely to show significant variation between iterations, and the longitudinal comparison should be interpreted with this in mind. Second, the SO-LCA captures the broader organisational context within which PHBV operations are embedded — governance structures, CSR policies, supplier relationships, and community engagement practices that shape the social environment of the value chain regardless of the specific product being produced. Its primary limitation, however, is that it is insensitive to the product: an organisation's social performance is assessed holistically, irrespective of how much of its activity is actually attributable to PHBV production. This means that the SO-LCA

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cannot distinguish between social impacts generated by PHBV operations and those arising from other activities of the same organisation, nor can it weight organisations by their actual contribution to the product.

The S-LCA approach addresses precisely this limitation. By anchoring the assessment to the product and its lifecycle, and by weighting results according to the actual labour contribution of each organisation to PHBV production, the S-LCA generates scores that are attributable to the product rather than to the organisations as general entities. This makes it methodologically consistent with the LCA and LCC dimensions of the LCSA framework, enabling a genuinely integrated sustainability assessment. The S-LCA also allows for the identification of phase-specific social risks through the flag system, which can highlight critical conditions in phases that carry limited weight in aggregation but significant social exposure. Its primary limitation at this stage is data maturity: product-level attribution requires more granular data than organisational-level assessment, and lifecycle coverage remains partial at the current TRL.

The dual-track framework exploits the strengths of both approaches while containing their respective limitations. The SO-LCA provides the longitudinal anchor and the organisational context; the S-LCA provides the product-level attribution and the lifecycle perspective. Where both tracks converge on the same finding — as in the case of gender representation gaps, absence of CSR formalisation, or migrant worker integration — the recommendation is strengthened by the corroboration across two independent methodological lenses. Where they diverge, the divergence itself is informative, revealing how organisational-level performance and product-level impact can differ when activity is not uniformly distributed across the value chain.

The SO-LCA track is kept methodologically consistent with D6.7 to preserve longitudinal comparability across assessment iterations; no changes are introduced to its indicator set or aggregation method beyond the data updates corresponding to M33. The methodological improvements developed for this interim assessment are applied exclusively within the S-LCA track, where they can be evaluated and refined without disrupting the baseline established in D6.7.

5.1.2 Methodological differences introduced in the S-LCA track

Three differences distinguish the S-LCA from the SO-LCA approach. The first is a weighting methodology based on activity drivers. In the SO-LCA, all organisations contribute equally to the aggregate result regardless of their actual role in producing the PHBV product. In the S-LCA, results are weighted by an activity driver that reflects each organisation's relative contribution to the product. For D6.10, worker-hours dedicated to PHBV operations is used as the universal proxy activity driver across all stakeholder categories. This is an acknowledged simplification: the ideal driver differs by category — procurement spend would be more appropriate for Value Chain Actors, taxes attributed to PHBV operations for Society, and units sold for Consumers — but worker-hours is the only driver for which sufficiently reliable data are available at this stage across all organisations. The use of category-specific drivers will be re-evaluated for D6.13.

The second improvement is the introduction of composite indicators to replace binary measures. Several social indicators are inherently qualitative, structured as yes/no questions that produce

binary scores (0 or 4) with no intermediate recognition. This loses information that is genuinely present in the data. In the S-LCA track, selected indicators are decomposed into sub-indicators, each capturing a specific dimension of the same concept and each using a graduated scale. Sub-indicators are then aggregated into a composite 0–4 score. This approach recognises incremental progress and more accurately reflects the variation in social performance across the value chain.

The third improvement is the introduction of a flag system operating independently of the product score. Weighted aggregation by activity driver has a structural consequence: phases or organisations representing a small share of total activity have limited influence on the aggregate score, even if conditions in that phase are seriously problematic. The flag system addresses this by identifying specific phases or organisations where performance falls below defined thresholds, regardless of their weight in aggregation. Two flag levels are used: Flag 1 — Critical, triggered when a phase score reaches the minimum value, indicating a potential legal violation or fundamental rights issue requiring immediate intervention; and Flag 2 — High Concern, triggered when performance falls below an adequate threshold in a phase with relevant labour intensity. Flags do not modify the product score; they feed into a consolidated recommendation list that accompanies the S-LCA results.

Section 5.2 presents the SO-LCA results for the interim assessment (M33), following the same structure as D6.7 to ensure comparability. Section 5.3 presents the product-level S-LCA results, including the methodology applied, the scores by indicator and lifecycle phase, the flags activated, and a synthesis comparing findings across both tracks.

5.2 SO-LCA results: interim assessment

Section 5.2 presents the SO-LCA results for the interim assessment (M33), following the same methodological approach applied in the first assessment (D6.7, M18) to ensure longitudinal comparability. The unit of analysis remains the organisation: each of the three organisations in the ViSS value chain is assessed independently across the five stakeholder categories defined in D6.3 — Workers, Value Chain Actors, Society, Local Community, and Consumers — and results are aggregated as a simple average across organisations. The three organisations are anonymised and referred to as Organisation 1, 2 and 3 throughout this section. The scoring system follows the 0–4 scale established in D6.3 and applied in D6.7, where scores of 0 or 1 indicate performance below the reference data and scores of 2 to 4 indicate progressively better performance relative to that reference.

The data presented in this section correspond to primary data collected from the three ViSS partner organisations through the combined SO-LCA/S-LCA questionnaire administered in M29–30. The tools and methodology applied were adapted from the SO-LCA assessment previously implemented in the A2C project (D7.8 - Matamoros, A. et al, 2023) and are detailed in Annex 2. Table 12 below summarises the stakeholder categories, aspects and indicators covered in the ViSS SO-LCA screening analysis (see Annex 3 and Annex 4 for additional information on the selection process).

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Table 12 ViSS List of stakeholder categories, impact subcategories and indicators

DIMENSION	CATEGORY	ASPECT	INDICATOR
SOCIAL	Workers	Fair salary	Organisation average wage, per month
		Working hours	Full-time staff
		Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Gender equality
		Health and safety	Occupational safety measures Lost time injury frequency rate
		Social benefits, legal issues, social security	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations
		Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Collective Bargaining Agreement
		Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported
	Value chain actors	Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour
		Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility Suppliers audit
		Supplier relationships	Suppliers' communication relationship
		Wealth distribution	Fair price definition
	Society	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues
		Contributions to economic development	Total taxation per capita
		Technology development	Technology transfer Investments in technology development/ transfer
	Local community	Access to material resources	Environmental management system
		Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community
		Safe and healthy living conditions	Promotion of community health
		Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation Number of meetings with community stakeholders
		Local employment	Workforce hired locally Spending on locally based suppliers
		Secure living conditions	Security complaints by the community
	Consumers	Health and safety	Labelling Consumer complaints Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System
		Transparency	Organisation communication transparency
		End-of-life responsibility	Internal management systems

5.2.1 Value chain screening analysis by category

In Tables 13 to 21, the colours given to each indicator for each organization correspond to the scoring from lower to higher (as mentioned in Figure 2): 0: red; 1: orange; 2: yellow; 3: green; and 4: blue. Considering the lack of consensus based, systematized procedures and/or market benchmarks in the social dimensions for the assignment of the mentioned scoring (from 0 to 4), the team has implemented a qualitative assessment based on the search of comparative context data for different aspects. This qualitative assessment analyses the performance of ViSS value chain in social indicators and establishes the level of improvement or worsening conditions compared with relevant reference data. Therefore, those that score 0 or 1 fail to improve against the reference data, while indicators that score 2, 3 or 4 perform better than the reference data at different levels. Specific indications are given to each individual indicator.

5.2.1.1 Stakeholder category: WORKERS

In this category, occupational health and safety, fair wages, and general working conditions were collected, assessed and compared to the reference data (see Table 13 for screening phase results and Table 14 for the synthesis which proposes the average performance for the three organizations and an overall score for each Indicator).

Table 13 Workers category: aspects, indicators, results, and reference data

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Fair salary (question 4.1.2)	POSITIVE	Organisation average wage, per month	3,399.1 €	2,633.3 €	3,083.3 €	The average wage in Spain 2,337.50€ ⁵ SMI 2025: 1,184€ ⁶	2023	INE data, national scope, on the average wage (full costs model) in Spain
Working hours (question 2.1.2)	POSITIVE	Full-time staff	100.0%	100.0%	92.8%	Full-time staff in Spain 85,3% ⁷	2025 Q2	Calculated as the ratio of full-time permanent staff against the total company workforce.
Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	POSITIVE	Gender equality (question 6.4.2)	54.5%	66.7%	33.3%	Women's employment rate in Spain 46.5% ⁸	2025 Q4	Calculated as the percentage of women (total national workforce)
Health and Safety	POSITIVE	Occupational safety measures (question 5.1.1)	1 (no certificate)	1	1 (no certificate)	No comparable data found		Occupational safety measures are mandatory in Spain for companies/institutions of this size.

⁵ https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736177025&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735976596

⁶ <https://www.sepe.es/HomeSepe/que-es-el-sepe/comunicacion-institucional/noticias/detalle-noticia?folder=/SEPE/2025/Febrero/&detalle=boe-publica-smi-2025-se-establece-1184-euros>

⁷ https://www.mites.gob.es/ficheros/ministerio/sec_trabajo/analisis_mercado_trabajo/numeros/154/154.pdf

⁸ <https://www.ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=65309>

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	NEGATIVE	Lost time injury frequency rate (question 5.3.6)	0	0	0	Incidence rate in Spain, in Industry sector	INSST report on the injuries that occurred during work hours
						4.582,3 ⁹ 2024	
	POSITIVE	Presence of sufficient safety measures (question 5.1.1)	1	1	1	National regulation: BOE-A-1995-24292 and RD39/199710	Safety measures are mandatory in Spain for companies/institutions of this size.
Social benefits, legal issues, social security (question 3.1.1)	NEGATIVE	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	0	0	0	Social security infringement proceedings in Spain: labour relations	These data correspond to the reported infringement proceedings
						17.155 ¹¹ 2023	
Workers' rights	POSITIVE	Collective Bargaining Agreement (question 4.2.3)	1	1	1	Total number of CBA in Spain, in Manufacture Industry sector	In 2022 there were in Spain 191,501 companies in the industry sector ¹² , therefore only 0.58% of them have a CBA.
Sexual harassment (question 5.3.9)	NEGATIVE	Sexual harassment incidents reported	0	0	0	Actions against sexual harassment in Spain	Infractions reported during work hours and/or in the workplace
						627 ¹³ 2024	

The second assessment show that the three organizations have, overall, a good performance for Workers category, compared to the reference data (Table 14).

For instance, the **average monthly wages** across the organizations in the value chain (€3,399.1, €2,633.3 € and 3,083.3 €) exceed the ES average (€2,337.5, 2023) as well as the **full-time employment rates** (100%, 100% and 92.8%; ES: 85.3%, 2022).

The **Equal Opportunities/Discrimination** sub-category analyses equal opportunity management practices and discrimination in the opportunities approached within the organization context. In our cases, the proportion of women varies: 54.5%, 66.7% and 33.3% respectively. Averaging 39.7% ViSS value chain performs worse than the Spanish average (ES: 46.5%). This worst performance might be explained because in this industry the proportion of women staff is typically lower than male staff.

The **Health and Safety Impact** subcategory includes three indicators: 1) Occupational safety measures; 2) Lost time injury frequency rate; and 3) the Presence of sufficient safety measures. The three organizations perform very well in these three indicators; although only one can certify that it follows occupational safety measures.

Besides, within the **Social benefits, legal issues and social security** subcategory, we evaluated if the organisations comply with the current regulations in terms of employment, reporting zero reported violations of laws and employment regulations.

⁹ Informe anual de accidentes de trabajo en España. Datos 2024. Últimos datos de siniestralidad

¹⁰ RD39/1997 - Reglamento de los Servicios de Prevención

¹¹ Memoria 2023 interactivo.pdf

¹² <https://ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=36167>

¹³ Informe Anual 2024.pdf

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Concerning **Workers' rights**¹², the VISS SO-LCA measures it by the placement of Collective Bargaining Agreements (CBA); all three cases have a signed CBA.

Lastly, in our assessment, the aspect **Sexual harassment**¹³ was measured with the indicator sexual harassment incidents reported as a means of verification of whether the company registers or not the number of this type of incidents. No sexual harassment incidents were reported.

Table 14 Worker's dimension scoring

	Average	Scoring
Organisation average wage, per month	3.038,58 €	4
Full-time staff	97,58%	4
Gender equality	51,52%	2
Occupational safety measures	100%*	3
Lost time injury frequency rate	0 days	4
Presence of sufficient safety measures	1	4
Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	0	4
Collective Bargaining Agreement	100%	4
Sexual harassment incidents reported	0	4

In general, the analysis revealed a greater social performance in the workers dimension, compared to the national reference data. However, gender representation and workers' rights remain as improvement areas.

5.2.1.2 Stakeholder category: VALUE CHAIN ACTORS

The value chain category was evaluated through a relationship-focused approach by asking about fair competition, social responsibility (SRC) and economic fairness as shown in Table 15. Table 16 presents a synthesis which proposes the average performance for the three organizations and an overall score for each Indicator.

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Table 15 Value chain category: aspects, indicators and reference data

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Fair competition	NEGATIVE	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour (question 7.2.3)	0	0	0	Cases opened by the National Commission for Markets and Competition at the national level	2024	The reference law is 1/2002, of February 21, on antitrust ¹⁴ .
						5 (MU); 82 (ES) ¹⁵		
Promoting social responsibility	POSITIVE	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility (question 8.1.2)	0	0	0	Companies that plan to implement CSR agreements/ guides in Spain	2024	Existence in the organisation of a CSR agreement.
	POSITIVE	Suppliers SCR audit (question 7.2.5)	0	0	0	Percentage of companies with SCR policies and certifications 0.01% (n2989/N=3207580 companies ES) (EP DATA, 2023); ≈1% (Dun & Bradstreet, 2024); MU: 41 Companies SCR 2024 ISO 9001 ¹⁷ PYMES That have sustainable buying policies: 20.6% ¹⁸	2024	Recent grey literature was consulted for determining the number of companies formally integrating SCR within their supply processes
Supplier relationships (question 7.2.6)	POSITIVE	Suppliers' communication relationship (question 7.2.6)	4	4	6	29% (ES); ISO 14001: (ES 2018) >26000 orgs. ; total (ES 2014) 2413 (Pérez-Mesa et al., 2021; ACMS Consultores, 2019; Revista Alimentaria, 2014)	2019, 2021	Likert scale: 1 to 6 (1: coercive communication to 6: very fluent communication)
Wealth distribution (question 7.2.8)	POSITIVE	Fair price definition	1	1	1	No data available		Existence of a policy for deciding a fair price.

Fair competition is key in supporting economic growth and innovation¹⁹. None of the three organizations have reported sanctions for antitrust behaviour, and all cases demonstrated compliance with competition regulations.

The aspect “**Promotion of social responsibility**” assesses whether the value chain organisations promote social responsibility among their suppliers and through their actions. In the VISS framework we use two indicators to assess this: Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility and Suppliers audit. Concerning CSR initiative adoption, the analysis reveals heterogeneous CSR implementation patterns, whilst aligned with the national reference data (i.e., 2693 companies).

To assess the organisations’ **relationship with their suppliers**, VISS organisations were asked to rate on a scale of 1 (coercive communication) to 6 (very fluent communication) their communication with this group of actors as a proxy for their relationship with their suppliers. Regarding the chain

¹⁴ Ley 1/2002, de 21 de febrero, de Coordinación de las Competencias del Estado y las Comunidades Autónomas en materia de Defensa de la Competencia.

¹⁵ Memoria CNMC 2024 .pdf

¹⁶ info.pactomundial.org/implantacion-desarrollo-sostenible-agenda2030-ods-empresas-espanolas-2024

¹⁷ <https://www.nueva-iso-9001-2015.com/2019/09/control-de-proveedores-externos-en-iso-9001/>

¹⁸ <https://info.pactomundial.org/implantacion-desarrollo-sostenible-agenda2030-ods-empresas-espanolas-2024>

¹⁹ <https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/competitive-and-fair-markets.html>

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audit mechanism, zero audits across all cases were conducted. The reference data is not considered, regarding the methodological limitation and the comparison between 10-year span data (2014-2024).

Wealth distribution can be explained as how the value is distributed among all the actors of the value chain. An equal distribution is obtained when a fair selling price for a product or service is established. As a proxy of this and to assess this aspect the organisations were asked whether they have defined a specific policy for deciding a fair price. The price fixation mechanism is unevenly distributed, and only one organisation reports to have a specific policy for deciding a fair price for their suppliers.

Table 16 Value chain dimension scoring

	Average	Scoring
Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	0	4
Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	0	0
Suppliers SCR audit	0	0
Suppliers' communication relationship	5	3
Fair price definition	100%	4

The analysis reveals very different performances: competitive compliance and supplier communication overperform, while Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility and Supplier SCR audit are areas to be improved.

5.2.1.3 Stakeholder category: SOCIETY

The stakeholders' category Society was analysed by evaluating the sustainability commitment, economic indicators mediated by taxes and R&D investment. Table 17 proposes the scores for each of the three organizations and the reference data, and Table 18 presents a synthesis which proposes the average performance for the three organizations and an overall score for each Indicator in the Society stakeholder category.

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Table 17 Society category: aspects, indicators and reference data

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Public commitment to sustainability issues	POSITIVE	The presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues (question 8.1.1 and 8.1.3)	0	0	0	Percentage of entities that have a sustainability strategy aligned with SDGs	2024	The reference data is set for a sample of 2107 companies.
			29.7% ²⁰					
Contribution to economic development	POSITIVE	Total taxation per capita (question 8.2.1)	12,190.78 €	9,090.28 €	21,150.93 €	Tax collection in Spain by budget chapters and taxes (Total chapters I, II, III) per capita	2022	The INE indicates that 153.224,8 million € were collected in 2023 ²¹ , considering that in T4 2023 there were 21389100 ²² workers the average taxation per capita in Spain was 7164€.
						7,164€ / Total: 153.224,8 (mill.€)		
Technology development	POSITIVE	Technology transfer (question 8.3.1)	1	1	1	1% companies in Murcia transfer results or are beneficiaries of transference (0,7% in Spain) ²³	2024	According to the INE data, 907 of 92.458 companies in Murcia transfer results or are beneficiaries of transference (in Spain 24,275 companies out in 3.255.276 invest in research 2024)
Technology development	POSITIVE	Investments in Technology development/ transfer (question 8.3.3)	371,308.44 €	18,978.48 €	2,064,420.00 €	Average investment in Innovation in companies in 2024, in Murcia	2024	In Murcia INE data (2024) and the demarcation between R&D, technologies and innovation are not well-differentiated. 907 companies invest in total 385,701,000€ (in Spain 24,275 companies invested 23,554,119,000€ in 2024)
						425,249€ ²⁴		

Our data reveals critical patterns in regard to the sustainability strategy implementation: none of the cases have declared to make available promises or agreements on sustainability issues. It is close to the national average: in 2024, only 2,107 companies out of 3,255,276²⁵ have declared to have a sustainability strategy aligned with the SDG (0.06%).

²⁰ info.pactomundial.org/implantacion-desarrollo-sostenible-agenda2030-ods-empresas-espanolas-2024

²¹ [Recaudación y Estadísticas del Sistema Tributario Español 2012-2022](#)

²² [Ocupados por sexo y rama de actividad. Valores absolutos y porcentajes respecto del total de cada sexo\(65123\)](#)

²³ [Empresas por municipio y actividad principal\(4721\)](#)

²⁴ [Empresas y gasto en innovación por comunidades y ciudades autónomas donde se realizó el gasto](#)

²⁵ https://ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736160707&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735576550

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In regard to the corporate taxes paid, all cases demonstrate a significantly greater economic contribution and fiscal responsibility. ViSS value chain components have a total taxation per capita higher than the national average, and also a remarkable variation in taxation contributions:

There is not a technology transfer program across the three cases, **whilst they are involved in EC-funded projects**. It is being assumed that the reporting involves some methodological issues, as long as the EC projects necessarily imply some sort of technology transfer or knowledge sharing. However, a limited reference data availability constrains comparative analysis.

There is also a significant heterogeneity in technology development expenditure. Although on a different scale, two of the cases have invested in technology development and/or transfer, reporting a better result when compared to the national reference data (14.38%).

Table 18 Society dimension scoring

	Average	Scoring
The presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	0%	0
Total taxation per capita	14.144,00 €	4
Technology transfer	100%	4
Investments in technology development/ transfer	818.235,64 €	2

In sum, complex patterns in organisational sustainability and economic performance emerged: e.g., heterogeneous innovation investment may suggest a different scale of priorities for the involved organisations in regards the technological advancement. A parallel systematic gap in sustainability strategy formalisation seems to prevail. Thus, there is limited shared knowledge and technology transfer within a context of heterogeneous innovation commitment, whilst the economic development support is higher than the national average. In this dimension, those showed insufficiencies and weaknesses due to the lack or scarcity of data, standardisation of the metrics and limitations concerning the availability of the statistical information at regional and national levels.

5.2.1.4 Stakeholder category: LOCAL COMMUNITY

For Local Community stakeholder category, Table 19 presents the scores for each of the three organizations and the reference data, and Table 20 presents a synthesis which proposes the average performance for the three organizations and the overall score for each Indicator in the Local Community stakeholder category.

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Table 19 Local community category: aspects, indicators and reference data

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Access to material resources	POSITIVE	Environmental management system (question 9.1.1)	0.75 (Yes, not certified)	0.75 (Yes, not certified)	0	Number of organisations with Community Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS) in Spain ≈1% n=787 ²⁶ companies	2025	Data from the EC.
Delocalization and migration	POSITIVE	Immigrant workforce rate (question 9.2.2)	4.5%	0%	18.8%	Employment rate of foreign nationality in Spain 15.9% (n=3575900 ²⁷ /22463300 ²⁸)	2025 4Q (ES)	INE; percentage of the occupied migrant population (not merely active, which also includes those seeking employment)
Safe and healthy living conditions	POSITIVE	Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community (question 9.2.3)	0	0	1 (Legal/Administrative Assistance)	0.13% ^{29,30}		Companies with CRS compromise: n 4146 ³¹ /N=3255276 ³² companies ES
Community engagement	POSITIVE	Promotion of community health (question 9.1.5)	0	0	0			Likert scale: 1 to 6 (1: not very diverse to 6: very diverse)
Community engagement	POSITIVE	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation (question 9.4.5)	3	3	3			
Community engagement	POSITIVE	Number of meetings with community stakeholders (question 9.4.6)	20	6	0	No data available		Comparable data were not found ³³

²⁶ [Statistics and Graphs](#)

²⁷ <https://www.ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=65112>

²⁸ <https://www.ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=65112>

²⁹ <https://andaluciainforma.com/aumento-en-responsabilidad-social-corporativa-2-500-empresas-se-comprometen-y-2-000-publican-transparencia-no-financiera/>

³⁰ [Empresas por municipio y actividad principal\(4721\)](#)

³¹ <https://andaluciainforma.com/aumento-en-responsabilidad-social-corporativa-2-500-empresas-se-comprometen-y-2-000-publican-transparencia-no-financiera/>

³² [Empresas por municipio y actividad principal\(4721\)](#)

³³ BON Europe (Bioplastics Organisations Network Europe) does not provide figures in regards community's stakeholders and meetings, fairs, etc [BIO-PLASTICS EUROPE | Stakeholder Engagement](#), [BON EUROPE – European Bioplastics e.V.](#) whilst it seems that the cluster and network are quite active.

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Local employments	POSITIVE	Workforce hired locally (question 9.4.2 and 9.4.4)	3 (13.6% local employment)	0 (0.0% local employment)	10 (14.5% local employment)	51% ³⁴ . - 84% ³⁵	Proxy: 51% of workers in Madrid Community work in the same municipality where they live (2017). - SEPE data concerning intra-inter provincial geographical mobility (2025)
	POSITIVE	Spending on locally based suppliers (question 9.4.9)	93,866.77 €	2,998.59 €	3,209,870.63 €	80% ³⁷	2021 CSR Practices with Suppliers: Always try to buy from local suppliers (Murcia region, sample of 128 companies) The reference data were extracted by a limited local (Murcia) sample. Results might lack transferability and representativeness. Comparable data is not available ³⁶
Secure living conditions	NEGATIVE	Security complaints by the community (question 10.2.1)	0	0	0	No data available	Specific data on this issue was not found, whilst community complaints in the context of the plastics sector typically focus on environmental contamination and false claims (EHN, 2024)

Only one of the three organizations in ViSS value chain has a certified environmental management system. However, the proportion is higher than the national average - only 1,009 companies were EMAS-certified organisations in 2023 (0.03% ES). The data presents significant variations in workforce integration: the proportion of migrant workers in ViSS value chain is lower than the national average. For instance, case 3 reported 25.33% immigrant workforce (ES: 57,40%). Concerning migrant workforce, a notable absence of formal mechanisms for integrating them emerged across all cases, which may indicate a potential systemic gap in workforce integration and/or limited institutional support mechanisms.

Two out of the three organizations in ViSS value chain have declared to have dedicated financial resources to strengthen community health. There are not data available for the reference data.

ViSS value chain members estimate that the Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation is medium to high. The three partners have declared to have participated to several meetings with community stakeholders in the last year.

The impact in the community engagement might be explained by their involvement in EU funded projects that imply such activities.

³⁴ <https://aquiensiasierra.es/comunidad-de-madrid/51-ciento-los-trabajadores-madrilenos-trabaja-municipio-residencia>

³⁵ https://www.sepe.es/HomeSepe/que-es-observatorio/publicaciones-observatorio/detalle-publicacion-observatorio~publicaciones_publicaciones-observatorio_Resumenes-ejecutivos-2025_movilidad-geografica-2025~.html - Movilidad geográfica de la contratación en España en 2024

³⁶ [5b1fc119-24eb-6ca3-8d7f-d743c2ce3770](https://www.sepe.es/HomeSepe/que-es-observatorio/publicaciones-observatorio/detalle-publicacion-observatorio~publicaciones_publicaciones-observatorio_Resumenes-ejecutivos-2025_movilidad-geografica-2025~.html)

³⁷ [5b1fc119-24eb-6ca3-8d7f-d743c2ce3770](https://www.sepe.es/HomeSepe/que-es-observatorio/publicaciones-observatorio/detalle-publicacion-observatorio~publicaciones_publicaciones-observatorio_Resumenes-ejecutivos-2025_movilidad-geografica-2025~.html)

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Concerning the local employment, the three members of the ViSS value chain indicate that they have hired at least one worker in the last accounting year. However, there is a significant variation in local workforce engagement due to the organisations’ size and characteristics.

None of the three members of the value chain have reported legal complaints by the local community in the last accounting year received regarding security concerns.

Table 20 Local community scoring

	Average	Scoring
Environmental management system	0.5	2
Immigrant workforce rate	7.8%	1
Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community	33% organizations in VISS provide some assistance to integrate migrant workers	1
Promotion of community health	0	0
Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation	3	3
Number of meetings with community stakeholders	8.7	2
Workforce hired locally	4.3	2
Spending on locally based suppliers	1,102,245.33€	3
Security complaints by the community	0	4

**: The organizational procedures for integration are not in place, and at the same time there are not migrants, neither integration policies*

Heterogeneous local community engagement and integration practices arose. The stakeholders’ practices and procedures in terms of community engagement and environmental management systems appeared as more advanced than the reference data. Nevertheless, the limited migration workforce integration and the absence of suppliers’ audit formalised system may lead to further sustainability and organisational issues.

5.2.1.5 Stakeholder category: CONSUMERS

The consumers’ assessment examined quality management, transparency and end-of-life systems and responsibilities in the three organizations sampled, as well as the national reference data (Table 21). None of the partners in ViSS value chain work directly with final consumers (Business to consumer activity, B2C), therefore this section of the survey was not completed, and this category was discarded from this intermediary assessment.

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Table 21 Consumers category: aspects, indicators and reference data

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Health and safety	POSITIVE	Labelling	NA	NA	NA	Mandatory RD 1055/2022 ('Novedades de etiquetado a partir del 1 de enero de 2025', 2024)		Labelling for consumer goods is strictly regulated: it does not apply to cases 1 and 2
	NEGATIVE	Consumer complaints	NA	NA	NA	No data available		Recent data concerning consumers' complaints concerning environmental hazards, packaging defects, public health issues, & applicable to similar organisations/business models is not available.
	POSITIVE	Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System	NA	NA	NA	Number of ISO 9001 certificates in Spain GFSI : ≈15.7% ES (n=6,067) (Hensen, 2021) ISO 9001 : ES n=30 341 (ISO/CASCO - Committee on conformity assessment, 2023)	2021, 2023	Data from GFSI certifications (including IFS Packaging certification), and ISO 9001 is considered
Transparency	POSITIVE	Organisation communication transparency	NA	NA	NA	% of companies in the region of Murcia that communicate information to their customers with full transparency (sample of 128 companies)		Likert scale: 1 to 6 (1: not very transparent communication to 6: very transparent communication)
						86% ³⁸	2021	
End-of-life responsibility	POSITIVE	Internal management systems	NA	NA	NA	GFSI : ≈15.7% (Hensen, 2021) ISO 9001 : ES n=30 341. Total:3.2mill (≈1%) (ISO/CASCO - Committee on conformity assessment, 2023) Management of plastics' end-of-life: mandatory for consumer goods: RD 1468/1988		This is mandatory for food and packaging. However, GFSI certifications for plastics/pack and ISO extend the internal management procedures.

5.2.2 SO-LCA: Synthesis and conclusions

Within each analytic category, a summary table comprising the results against the reference data was provided. For this second report, 3 organizations and 31 indicators were analysed; the major hardship was to find accurate and recent reference data metrics, comparable and updated. But the present interim assessment has been the opportunity to set the basis for this comparison and to identify areas for improvement. **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** recapitulates

³⁸

<https://www.um.es/documents/4156512/13232792/Baro%CC%81metro+de+la+RSC+en+Pymes+de+la+Regio%CC%81n+de+Murcia+%28enero+2022%29.pdf/5b1fc119-24eb-6ca3-8d7f-d743c2ce3770?t=1654095930237>

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the areas in which ViSS value chain outperforms or that need improvement in comparison to the reference data. These areas where improvement is needed can be the subject of specific actions.

Figure 9 Overview of improvements areas and strengths observed in the three organisations in comparison with the reference data metrics

The mid-term assessment reveals how certain dimensions demonstrate excellence (quality management, transparency), while others present significant variation (technology investment, workforce integration) and highly differentiated organisational maturity across social performance dimensions. These differences might be explained by the nature of the industry in which these organisations evolved (for instance, the higher wage than the national average might be explained by the characteristics of the sector that tend to employ more specialized personnel but also the low women presence in the organizations' staff).

Therefore, although not final, this interim assessment, compiled in Table 22, has been the opportunity to point out at areas where ViSS value chain performs well, but also areas that should be closely monitored for improvement. The colours correspond to the scoring (as mentioned in Figure 2): 0: red, 1: orange, 2: yellow, 3: green, 4: blue.

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Table 22 Interim SO-LCA Results

CATEGORY	ASPECT	INDICATOR	Score
Workers	Fair salary	Organisation average wage, per month	4
	Working hours	Full-time staff	4
	Equal opportunities...	Gender equality	2
	Health and safety	Occupational safety measures	3
		Lost time injury frequency rate	4
	Social benefits...	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	4
	Workers' rights...	Collective Bargaining Agreement	4
Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported	4	
Value chain actors	Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	4
	Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	0
		Suppliers audit	0
	Supplier relationships	Suppliers' communication relationship	3
Wealth distribution	Fair price definition	4	
Society	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	0
	Contributions to eco. dev.	Total taxation per capita	4
	Technology development	Technology transfer	4
Investments in technology development/ transfer		2	
Local community	Access to material resources	Environmental management system	2
	Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate	1
		Organisational procedures to integrate migrant workers	1
	Safe and healthy living conditions	Promotion of community health	0
	Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups...	3
		Number of meetings with community stakeholders	2
	Local employment	Workforce hired locally	2
		Spending on locally based suppliers	3
Secure living conditions	Security complaints by the community	4	

5.3 S-LCA product approach: interim assessment

5.3.1 Methodological approach

The product-level S-LCA applied in this section builds on the three methodological specifications introduced for D6.10 and described in Section 5.1. This subsection provides the technical detail necessary to interpret the results presented in Sections 5.3.2 and 5.3.3. The complete indicator specifications, including measurement criteria, reference scales, sub-indicator structures and threshold definitions, are documented in Annex 5: S-LCA Indicators Technical Sheets, to which this section should be read as a companion document.

5.3.1.1 Activity driver and weighting

Results are aggregated across the lifecycle using worker-hours dedicated to PHBV operations as the universal activity driver for D6.10. The product-level score for each indicator is calculated as:

$$Score_{product} = \sum (Score_{phase} \times Worker\text{-}hours_{phase}) / \sum (Worker\text{-}hours_{phase})$$

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This weighting ensures that lifecycle phases with greater labour intensity carry proportionally greater weight in the product score, reflecting where social exposure is actually concentrated. The total worker-hours recorded across the three assessed phases amount to 27,292 hours, distributed as follows: raw material sourcing accounts for 74.7% of total worker-hours, production/fermentation for 18.7%, and end of life for 6.6%. This distribution means that social performance in the raw material sourcing phase exerts the strongest influence on the product-level score, a structural feature of the current value chain that should be borne in mind when interpreting results. Worker-hours as a universal driver is an acknowledged simplification at D6.10 stage: the methodologically preferred drivers for Value Chain Actors (procurement spend), Society (taxes attributed to PHBV), and Consumers (units sold) are not yet available with sufficient reliability, and will be introduced for D6.13. One indicator applies a variant of this driver: LC2 (Integration support for workers with linguistic barriers) is weighted by migrant worker-hours rather than total worker-hours. The calculation method is specified in Annex 5.

5.3.1.2 Composite indicators

Two stakeholder categories include composite indicators — Workers and Consumers — where binary yes/no measures have been replaced by graduated sub-indicator structures that recognise incremental progress and capture real-world nuance in social performance. Each composite indicator is calculated as a weighted sum of its sub-indicators, scaled to the 0–4 range. The specific weights and sub-indicator scales are defined Annex 5. The qualitative interpretation framework applied to composite and product-level scores is presented in Section 5.3.3.

5.3.1.3 Flag system

The flag system operates as a diagnostic layer independent of the product score. Two flag levels are applied:

Flag 1 — Critical: triggered when a lifecycle phase scores at the minimum value on an indicator, signalling a potential legal violation or fundamental rights issue requiring immediate intervention regardless of the phase's weight in aggregation.

Flag 2 — High Concern: triggered when a phase score falls below an adequate threshold. Priority is calibrated to the phase's share of worker-hours: the same performance gap carries different urgency depending on whether the phase represents 5% or 60% of total labour exposure.

Flags do not modify the product score. All flags triggered across all indicators are compiled in a consolidated recommendation list in Section 5.3.4.

5.3.2 Scope and system boundary

The S-LCA covers two lifecycle phases of the PHBV value chain for which primary data are available at D6.10: raw material sourcing, and production (fermentation). The phases not covered — including use, and end-of-life — fall outside the scope of this interim assessment due to data unavailability at the current TRL stage. Their inclusion will be evaluated for D6.13 according to the definition of the corresponding processes and relevant organisations.

The three organisations assessed are the same consortium partners evaluated in the SO-LCA (Section 5.2), anonymised as Organisation 1, 2 and 3. Each organisation is responsible for one or more lifecycle phases within the assessed scope; collectively they cover the raw material sourcing, and production/fermentation phases. The functional unit and system boundary are consistent with those defined for the LCA (Section 3).

5.3.3 Results by stakeholder category

Results are presented below by stakeholder category. For each category, individual organisation scores are reported alongside the worker-hour-weighted product score and its qualitative category. Scores follow the 0–4 scale established in D6.3, where individual organisation scores on non-composite indicators take discrete values and composite and product-level scores are continuous values resulting from weighted aggregation. To facilitate interpretation, product-level scores are assigned a qualitative category based on the midpoints between the reference values of the 0–4 scale, such that each category corresponds to the nearest reference value (Table 23):

Table 23. Qualitative interpretation categories for product-level S-LCA scores

Score range	Category
0.00 – 0.49	Inadequate
0.50 – 1.49	Insufficient
1.50 – 2.49	Adequate
2.50 – 3.49	Good
3.50 – 4.00	Excellent

The following table presents a summary of the product-level S-LCA results across all five stakeholder categories and fourteen indicators assessed in D6.10. Scores are reported on the 0–4 scale established in D6.3 and accompanied by a qualitative category based on the interpretation framework described above. Indicators recorded as N/A reflect the absence of the conditions necessary for their assessment at the current TRL stage, as detailed in the category-specific results below (Table 24).

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Table 24. Summary of product-level S-LCA results — D6.10

	Ind ID	Category	Subcategory	Indicator title	Product	
Gate	W1	Worker	Fundamental rights	Legal Compliance & Fundamental Rights - Minimum Threshold	No serious violations found	
Indicators	W2	Worker	Working hours	Full-time staff percentage	4.00	Excellent
	W3	Worker	Equal opportunities & non discrimination	Equal opportunities & non discrimination	2.30	Adequate
	W4	Worker	Health & Safety	Occupational H&S	3.82	Excellent
	W5	Worker	Right to collective bargaining	Collective Bargaining Coverage	4.00	Excellent
	W6	Worker	Fair salary	Organisation average wage	3.75	Excellent
	VC1	Value Chain	Supplier relationships	Fair payment terms to suppliers	3.00	Good
	VC2	Value Chain	Supply chain localization	Regional supplier spending	1.13	Insufficient
	S1	Society	Public commitment to sustainability	Public sustainability reporting	0.00	Inadequate
	S2	Society	End-of-life social impact	End-of-Life Pathway Design	N/A	N/A
	LC1	Local Community	Safe and healthy living conditions	Environmental management system for community impact mitigation	1.87	Adequate
	LC2	Local Community	Delocalization and migration	Integration support for workers with linguistic barriers in product operations	0.53	Insufficient
	LC3	Local Community	Community engagement	Community grievance mechanism	0.13	Inadequate
	LC4	Local Community	Local employment	Local employment in product operations	1.13	Insufficient
	CO1	Consumers	Health and safety	Consumer product information quality (COMPOSITE)	N/A	N/A
	CO2	Consumers		Consumer complaints mechanism effectiveness	N/A	N/A

Overall, the PHBV product value chain shows strong social performance in the Workers category, with four out of five indicators rated Good or Excellent at product level. Performance is more heterogeneous across the remaining categories, with notable weaknesses in community engagement (LC3, Inadequate), and public sustainability reporting (S1, Inadequate). These results reflect both the characteristics of the current R&D-phase value chain and areas where targeted improvement is needed prior to commercial scale-up. The following subsections present the detailed results and analysis by stakeholder category.

5.3.3.1 Workers

The Workers category covers five indicators: full-time staff percentage (W2), equal opportunities and non-discrimination (W3, composite), occupational health and safety management system (W4, composite), collective bargaining coverage (W5), and average wage (W6). Prior to scoring, a prerequisite compliance gate (W1 — Legal Compliance and Fundamental Rights) was assessed across all three organisations. W1 evaluates the absence of serious violations of fundamental labour rights, including forced labour, child labour, freedom of association restrictions, and documented discrimination. No violations were identified in any of the assessed organisations, and the assessment proceeded normally to W2–W6 (Table 25).

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Table 25. Workers category — S-LCA scores by organisation and product level

	Ind ID	Indicator title	Org 1	Org 2	Org 3	Product	Comments	
Gate	W1	Legal Compliance & Fundamental Rights	No serious violations found					
Indicators	W2	Full-time staff percentage	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	Excellent	
	W3	Equal opportunities & non discrimination	2.40	1.60	3.10	2.30	Adequate	
	W3.1	Non-discrimination policy	0.50	0.50	1.00	0.53		
	W3.2	Gender pay gap monitoring+ actions	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.07		Org1 and Org 2: No obligation for SME
	W3.3	Women in decision-making	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.81		Org 2: No gender balance evidenced, no flag awarded because of size of the entity
	W3.4	Gender representation vs pipeline	1.00	1.00	0.25	0.95		Org 3: Gender representation gap below sector baseline (gap within 15–25pp range). Does not reach threshold for formal flag.
	W4	Occupational H&S	4.00	4.00	1.33	3.82	Excellent	
	W4.1	H&S management system presence	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00		
	W4.2	Process-specific PHBV risk assessments	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.93		Org 3: Risk assessment for PHBV operations – Flag 2 – High concern
	W4.3	H&S audit & continuous improvement cycle	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.93		Org3: Once risk assessment for PHBV operations is finished including these operations in the audit activities
	W5	Collective Bargaining Coverage	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	Excellent	
W6	Organisation average wage	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.75	Excellent		

Overall worker performance at product level is strong, with four of the five indicators reaching Good or Excellent. W2 (full-time staff), W5 (collective bargaining) and W6 (average wage) score 4.00; 4.00 and 3.75 respectively, all Excellent. W4 (Occupational H&S) scores 3.82 (Excellent) at product level,

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with the overall strong performance partially offset by one organisation's absence of PHBV-specific process risk assessments (W4.2 = 0) and audit coverage (W4.3 = 0). Both are noted as recommendations in the results table. W3 (equal opportunities) is the weakest indicator in this category at 2.30 (Adequate), reflecting heterogeneous performance across sub-indicators. Gender pay gap monitoring (W3.2) is the weakest dimension at product level (0.07), with two organisations scoring 0 due to absence of monitoring — both below the mandatory reporting threshold applicable to larger organisations — partially offset by the third organisation scoring 1. Gender representation versus sector pipeline (W3.4) scores 0.95 at product level, with one organisation showing a gap below the sector baseline that does not reach the threshold for a formal flag but is recommended as a point of monitoring at D6.13.

One flag is triggered in this category: Flag 2 — High Concern on W4.2 for one organisation, for absence of PHBV-specific process risk assessments. A recommendation has been issued to that organisation (see Section 5.3.4).

5.3.3.2 Value Chain Actors

The Value Chain Actors category covers two indicators: fair payment terms to suppliers (VC1) and regional supplier spending (VC2) (Table 26).

Table 26. Value Chain Actors category — S-LCA scores by organisation and product level

Ind ID	Category	Indicator title	Org 1	Org 2	Org 3	Product		Comments
VC1	Value Chain	Fair payment terms to suppliers	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	Good	
VC2	Value Chain	Regional supplier spending	1.00	1.00	3.00	1.13	Insufficient	

VC1 (fair payment terms) scores 3.00 (Good) uniformly across all three organisations, reflecting consistent application of 30-day payment terms throughout the value chain.

VC2 (regional supplier spending) yields a product score of 1.13 (Insufficient), reflecting variation across the value chain. One organisation scores 3 while the remaining two score 1, with the product score pulled towards the lower end by the dominant weight of the phases with lower regional sourcing. Regional sourcing is encouraged but not a mandatory requirement and no threshold is defined for this indicator. It should be noted that the supplier configuration assessed here corresponds to the current R&D phase of the project, which may differ substantially from the supply chain that will support commercial-scale production of the PHBV product. As the product moves towards commercialisation, future value chain participants are encouraged to prioritise regional sourcing strategies, which would contribute positively to local economic development and reduce supply chain carbon footprint, consistent with the SSbD principles of the ViSS project.

5.3.3.3 Society (S1–S2)

The Society category covers two indicators: public sustainability reporting (S1) and end-of-life pathway design (S2) (Table 27).

Table 27. Society category — S-LCA scores by organisation and product level

Ind ID	Category	Indicator title	Org 1	Org 2	Org 3	Product		Comments
S1	Society	Public sustainability reporting	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	Inadequate	All organisations are SME, no reporting obligation
S2	Society	End-of-Life Pathway Design	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	

S1 (public sustainability reporting) scores 0.00 (Inadequate) across all three organisations and all lifecycle phases, yielding a product score of 0.00. All three organisations are SMEs with no mandatory sustainability reporting obligation under current regulation; the absence of voluntary reporting is therefore contextually noted rather than treated as a compliance failure. It should be noted, however, that the organisations currently assessed are research and development partners whose role in the value chain may differ substantially from the organisations that will eventually produce and commercialise the PHBV product at scale. As the product moves towards commercial deployment, future value chain participants — particularly those involved in manufacturing, transformation and distribution — are strongly encouraged to adopt recognised sustainability reporting frameworks (GRI, EMAS, ISO 26000) as a condition of participation in the PHBV value chain. Public sustainability reporting by commercial-scale operators would be consistent with the SSbD principles underpinning the ViSS project and with the growing regulatory and market expectations for transparency in bio-based packaging supply chains.

S2 (end-of-life pathway design) is a product-level indicator that evaluates the highest-accessibility end-of-life pathway for which the PHBV product is technically documented as compatible. This indicator does not aggregate by organisation — it is assessed once at product level based on technical product characteristics and market infrastructure data. At D6.10, the product's end-of-life pathway documentation is not yet sufficiently developed to assign a score; S2 is therefore recorded as N/A for this iteration and will be assessed in D6.13.

5.3.3.4 Local Community (LC1–LC4)

The Local Community category covers four indicators: environmental management system for community impact mitigation (LC1), integration support for workers with linguistic barriers (LC2), community grievance mechanism (LC3), and local employment in product operations (LC4) (Table 28).

Table 28. Local Community category — S-LCA scores by organisation and product level

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Ind ID	Category	Indicator title	Org 1	Org 2	Org 3	Product	Comments
LC1	Local Community	Environmental management system for community impact mitigation	2.00	2.00	0.00	1.87 Adequate	Org 3: No EMS, although no high-intensity community impacts are generated.
LC2	Local Community	Integration support for workers with linguistic barriers in product operations	0.00	N/A	2.00	0.53 Insufficient	
LC3	Local Community	Community grievance mechanism	0.00	0.00	2.00	0.13 Inadequate	Org 1 and Org 2: No community grievance mechanism. Flag 1 - CRITICAL
LC4	Local Community	Local employment in product operations	1.00	1.00	3.00	1.13 Insufficient	

LC1 (environmental management system) yields a product score of 1.87 (Adequate). Two organisations score 2 (partial EMS without certification but meeting key elements), while one organisation scores 0 (no EMS). The absence of an EMS in that organisation is noted as a recommendation rather than a formal flag, as the organisation do not generate the high-intensity community impacts — such as industrial-scale VOC emissions, fermentation odours or continuous noise — that would trigger a critical flag under the indicator's threshold criteria.

LC2 (integration support for migrant workers) yields a product score of 0.53 (Insufficient), weighted by migrant worker-hours. One organisation scores 0 (migrant workers present but no integration support provided), one organisation is assigned N/A (no migrant workers), and one organisation scores 2 (legal and administrative assistance provided to a migrant workforce). No flag is triggered as no evidence of discriminatory treatment was identified.

LC3 (community grievance mechanism) yields a product score of 0.13 (Inadequate). Two organisations score 0 (no mechanism exists) and one scores 2 (basic mechanism with accessible channels). The low product score reflects the dominant combined weight of the two organisations without mechanisms. Organisations 1 and 2 are recommended to establish an accessible grievance channel for community concerns prior (see Section 5.3.4).

LC4 (local employment) yields a product score of 1.13 (Insufficient), reflecting variation across organisations. One organisation scores 3 while the remaining two score 1.

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Two flags are triggered in this category. Flag 1 — Critical on LC3 for Organisation 1 and Organisation 2, for absence of a community grievance mechanism. Recommendations have been issued to organisations in Section 7.

5.3.3.5 Consumers (CO1–CO2)

The Consumers category covers two indicators: consumer product information quality (CO1, composite including prerequisite compliance check CO1.1) and consumer complaints mechanism effectiveness (CO2). Both indicators apply exclusively to business-to-consumer (B2C) organisations with direct consumer-facing packaging.

At D6.10, no data are available for either indicator. The PHBV product has not yet reached a stage where consumer-facing packaging exists or has been tested in a market context; consequently none of the three assessed organisations currently operates as a B2C entity in relation to the PHBV product. CO1 and CO2 are therefore recorded as N/A for this iteration. This is an expected outcome at the current TRL stage and does not constitute a data gap in the conventional sense — it reflects the absence of the conditions necessary for these indicators to be applicable.

5.3.4 Consolidated flag list and recommendations

Table below compiles all flags triggered across the five stakeholder categories. Flags are reported at organisation level and classified into two levels: Flag 1 — Critical, indicating a potential legal violation or fundamental rights issue requiring immediate intervention regardless of the organisation's weight in the product-level aggregation; and Flag 2 — High Concern, indicating performance below an adequate threshold that requires corrective action prior to the next assessment iteration. Flags do not modify the product-level scores reported in Section 5.3.3 (Table 29).

Table 29. Consolidated S-LCA flag list — D6.10

Flag level	Indicator	Organisation	Issue	Recommendation
Flag 2 — High Concern	W4.2	Org 3	No PHBV-specific process risk assessments documented	Conduct and document risk assessments specific to PHBV operations
Recommendation	LC1	Org 3	No environmental management system (no obligation)	Identify and document processes with high community impact potential. If present, basic EMS implementation is recommended.
Flag 1 — Critical	LC3	Org 1	No community grievance mechanism	Establish accessible grievance channel for community concerns
Flag 1 — Critical	LC3	Org 2	No community grievance mechanism	Establish accessible grievance channel for community concerns

6 Circularity monitoring

As outlined in the Introduction, circularity is addressed in this deliverable as a transversal design objective that complements the three sustainability dimensions assessed within the SSbD framework. This section presents the methodology and results of the targeted literature review conducted to identify suitable circularity monitoring frameworks for bio-based food packaging systems, and their application to the ViSS PHBV product system. The circularity-related recommendations and monitoring actions that emerge from this work are consolidated in Section 7.4.

6.1 Circularity in the context of food packaging and the ViSS value chain

Circular economy strategies are increasingly important for reducing the resource dependence, waste generation and environmental impacts associated with food packaging. However, circularity cannot be assumed from the use of a bio-based material, a recycled input, or an intended end-of-life route alone. It needs to be demonstrated through measurable evidence on material inputs, production processes, packaging design, use-phase performance and end-of-life outcomes. This is particularly important for food packaging, where circularity must be assessed alongside the core functions of packaging: protecting food, maintaining quality and safety, supporting distribution and helping to avoid food losses. Pauer et al. (2019) emphasise that environmental assessment of food packaging should account not only for the direct environmental effects of packaging, but also for packaging-related food losses and waste, as well as circularity.

This report focuses on the development of a circularity monitoring approach for food packaging, with application to the ViSS PHBV product system. The aim is to support the quantitative measurement and validation of circularity-relevant aspects of the ViSS solution in comparison with conventional market alternatives. The ViSS product system provides a relevant application case because it combines several circular economy strategies in a single emerging value chain. PHBV is produced through microbial fermentation using food industry residues as feedstock, and the ViSS concept aims to establish a safe, sustainable and functional PHBV value chain in which packaging is designed for both recyclability and biodegradability.

Circularity monitoring is needed because the circular performance of emerging food packaging solutions cannot be inferred from design intentions alone. In the ViSS case, the use of food industry residues provides a strong circularity basis, but it needs to be supported by data on residue type, quantity, alternative uses, conversion efficiency and avoided virgin or fossil-based inputs. Similarly, recyclability and biodegradability indicate potential end-of-life routes, but each requires separate evidence. Recyclability depends on detectability, sorting, stream compatibility, recycling process performance and recovered material quality. Biodegradability or compostability depends on defined conditions, standards, infrastructure and degradation outcomes. A robust monitoring approach therefore needs to distinguish between circularity claims that are already supported by

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data, circularity features that remain design-stage intentions, and circularity outcomes that require scenario-based or future value-chain evidence.

The early development stage of the ViSS solution makes circularity monitoring particularly valuable. Design choices, production processes and value-chain configurations can still be adjusted more effectively at this stage than after commercial deployment. This aligns with the logic of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD), which aims to integrate safety and sustainability considerations into the design and redesign of chemicals, materials, processes and products, rather than assessing them only after development has been completed. The European Commission established the SSbD framework through Commission Recommendation (EU) 2022/2510, which provides a European assessment framework for safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials (European Commission, 2022).

Circularity monitoring should also be understood as a complement to wider sustainability assessment. Circularity indicators can show whether material loops are being closed, whether renewable or recycled inputs are used, whether end-of-life pathways are technically plausible, and whether recovered materials can retain value. However, circularity indicators do not by themselves determine whether a packaging system is environmentally, economically or socially preferable. Circularity improvements may introduce trade-offs through energy use, auxiliary inputs, process complexity, treatment costs, land-use implications or social conditions across the value chain. For this reason, circularity monitoring should be interpreted alongside life cycle assessment, life cycle costing, social assessment and safety assessment.

The need for reliable circularity data is also reinforced by the evolving European policy and reporting landscape. The Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation, Regulation (EU) 2025/40, establishes harmonised requirements for packaging and packaging waste across the EU and is directly relevant to the future evidence base expected for packaging systems ([Regulation \(EU\) 2025/40](#)). The Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation, Regulation (EU) 2024/1781, establishes a framework for setting ecodesign requirements for sustainable products, including requirements that may relate to durability, reusability, recyclability, recycled content and product information ([Regulation \(EU\) 2024/1781](#)). ERSR E5, established under Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772, addresses resource use and circular economy reporting, including resource inflows, resource outflows and waste where material ([Commission Delegated Regulation \(EU\) 2023/2772](#)). ISO 59020:2024 provides requirements and guidance for organisations to measure and assess circularity performance within defined economic systems ([ISO 59020:2024](#)).

These policy and standardisation developments do not prescribe the specific food packaging circularity indicators selected in this report. They do, however, define the wider direction of travel: circularity claims are expected to become more evidence-based, comparable and verifiable. For emerging systems such as ViSS, this creates a practical need to establish monitoring principles that are transparent, proportionate to the maturity of the system, and capable of being updated as more data become available.

The purpose of this section is therefore to establish the rationale for circularity monitoring in food packaging and to explain why a staged, evidence-based approach is needed for the ViSS PHBV

product system. The framework developed in this report is intended to be suitable for food packaging circularity monitoring more broadly, while the ViSS case demonstrates how such an approach can be applied to a novel PHBV packaging system. This allows the assessment to support early design decisions, avoid premature circularity claims, identify data gaps, and clarify what evidence is required to demonstrate credible circularity performance as the value chain matures.

6.2 Circularity monitoring methodology

A targeted literature review was conducted to identify existing frameworks, tools, guidelines and indicators relevant to circularity monitoring in food packaging systems, with particular attention to plastic and bio-based packaging in agri-food value chains. The review was motivated by the recognition that a wide range of circularity indicators and assessment tools already exists, but that the rationale for selecting suitable metrics for a specific product system is often unclear. For emerging packaging systems such as ViSS, this creates a need for a structured screening process that can identify which existing approaches are most relevant, what dimensions they cover, and how they can inform the development of a fit-for-purpose circular economy monitoring framework for food packaging.

The review was guided by two research questions:

- What metrics are suitable for assessing and monitoring the circularity of food packaging within agri-food supply chains?
- What existing frameworks, tools or guidelines are available for assessing or monitoring the circularity of food packaging within agri-food systems?

The methodological approach is illustrated in Figure 10.

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Figure 10 Methodological approach used to identify and analyse circularity monitoring approaches for food packaging systems.

A targeted literature search was conducted in **Web of Science** and **Scopus** between **November 2025 and February 2026**. Searches were carried out iteratively to capture literature at the intersection of circular economy, food or agricultural systems, plastics or polymers, and packaging. Two main search strings were applied in both databases:

- (circular* econom*") AND (framework* OR tool*) AND (agricultur* OR food) AND (plastic* OR polymer*) AND packag*
Web of Science: n = 72; Scopus: n = 79
- (circular*) AND (framework* OR tool* OR monitor* OR assessment* OR measur*) AND (agricultur* OR food) AND plastic* AND packag*
Web of Science: n = 216; Scopus: n = 216

The search results were compiled and screened to remove irrelevant records and identify publications with potential relevance to circularity monitoring in food packaging systems. Additional publications were identified through snowballing from the reference lists of relevant papers. Targeted searches were also conducted using Consensus to identify further papers addressing specific questions on circularity assessment, food packaging, plastic packaging, bioplastics, recyclability, biodegradability, material flow analysis and circular economy monitoring.

The resulting publications were screened based on their relevance to the scope of the study and their potential applicability to the ViSS PHBV product system. Particular attention was given to whether the papers addressed food packaging, plastic or bio-based packaging, circularity indicators, material flows, design for recycling, end-of-life pathways, food-contact safety, food loss prevention,

or broader agri-food supply-chain circularity. The reviewed approaches varied considerably in scope and level of assessment. Some focused on product-level circularity indicators, while others addressed design tools, life cycle assessment, material flow analysis, waste prevention indicators, food-contact safety, social assessment, or economy-wide circularity monitoring.

The screening distinguished between two broad groups of literature. The first group included papers that explicitly proposed, adapted or structured a framework, tool, guideline, indicator set or methodological approach for circularity assessment, sustainability assessment or monitoring. The second group included papers that did not propose a dedicated monitoring framework, but provided important insights for developing one. These included studies on food-contact safety, recycling quality, sorting, material-flow gaps, reporting limitations, bioplastic life cycle assessment, waste prevention, and the practical conditions under which circularity claims can be substantiated. The selected publications were then analysed qualitatively to identify the circularity dimensions, indicators and assessment considerations most relevant to food packaging. The analysis focused on what each paper contributed to the monitoring of circularity, which part of the packaging system it addressed, and whether its insights were directly applicable to the ViSS case or only indirectly useful. The assessment also considered whether the approach captured material inputs, production processes, packaging functionality, use-phase implications, end-of-life performance, food-contact safety, value-chain conditions, or wider sustainability trade-offs.

The primary criterion for extracting insights was the ability of each approach to clarify what should be monitored in order to understand circular economy progress in food packaging systems. The focus was not only on identifying quantitative metrics, but also on determining the conditions under which those metrics are meaningful. This was important because circularity indicators can be misleading if they are interpreted without considering packaging function, food-contact requirements, sorting feasibility, recycling quality, biodegradation conditions, or the distinction between design intentions and measured material flows.

The review findings were used to inform the structure of a staged circularity monitoring approach for food packaging with application to the ViSS PHBV product system. The ViSS case was used to test the relevance of the identified monitoring dimensions and to clarify which aspects can already be assessed using available evidence, which should remain scenario-based, and which require future value-chain data. A detailed analysis of the reviewed literature is presented in the Results section (6.2), followed by an application of the findings to the ViSS product system.

6.3 Results

6.2.1 Frameworks, tools and guidelines identified for CE monitoring and assessment

The literature review identified a focused group of papers that explicitly propose frameworks, tools, guidelines, adapted indicators, indicator-selection procedures, or methodological approaches relevant to circular economy (CE) assessment of food packaging and related plastic/agri-food systems. These papers do not all operate at the same level. Some are directly food-packaging-specific; some address plastic packaging more generally; some operate at material-flow or macro-

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system level; and some provide methodological guidance for linking circularity with life cycle assessment (LCA) or social life cycle assessment (S-LCA). The distinction is important: not every paper in this group provides a complete food-packaging CE monitoring framework, but each offers a formal assessment structure that can inform one part of such monitoring.

6.2.1.1 Food-packaging-specific frameworks and design-stage tools

Pauer et al. (2019) provide one of the most directly relevant methodological frameworks for food packaging assessment. Their framework is explicitly designed for assessing the environmental sustainability of food packaging and is structured around three dimensions: direct environmental effects of packaging, packaging-related food losses and waste, and circularity. The authors also propose key environmental performance indicators and calculation procedures, while noting that quantifying packaging-related food loss and waste remains a methodological challenge. This framework is important for CE monitoring because it prevents circularity from being treated as a stand-alone measure of sustainability. Instead, circularity is positioned alongside packaging function and food loss prevention, which is particularly important for food packaging where material reduction or recyclability may conflict with preservation performance.

Schmidt Rivera et al. (2019) propose a decision-support framework for the design and selection of innovative food packaging. The framework combines three assessment steps: evaluation of packaging features related to food and packaging waste, application of CE principles to materials, energy and end-of-life management, and comparison of environmental impacts through LCA. The framework is tested on a prototype packaging for raspberries and meat. Its value for CE monitoring is mainly at the early design stage: the framework demonstrates that packaging circularity should be assessed only in relation to technical performance and environmental consequences, rather than as a purely end-of-life attribute. The authors also show that LCA may be unnecessary or premature if earlier technical and circularity criteria are unfavourable.

Arias et al. (2021) propose a multi-criteria roadmap for evaluating active food packaging films. This is not a general monitoring framework for all food packaging; it is specifically oriented toward bioactive food packaging prototypes. The roadmap considers five categories: packaging evaluation, environmental criteria, circularity criteria, economic criteria and social criteria. Its contribution is the staged evaluation logic: circularity is assessed alongside preservation performance, food safety, market criteria, environmental impacts, economic viability and social acceptance. The authors also acknowledge a limitation: the roadmap does not yet provide a final quantitative suitability score, which limits its use as a fully quantitative monitoring tool.

De Melo et al. (2025) propose a design tool for flexible polymeric film packaging for food applications. The tool combines Ashby's material selection methodology with the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI), using a decision flowchart that moves from packaging requirements to material selection, possible multilayer combinations, packaging concepts, circularity evaluation and cost ranking. This is best understood as a conceptual design-stage tool rather than a full CE monitoring framework. Its relevance is that it links packaging performance constraints, circularity potential and cost before material combinations are fixed.

6.2.1.2 Plastic-packaging circularity indicators and adapted assessment approaches

Matos et al. (2024) propose a structured selection and mapping of circularity micro-indicators for plastic packaging. The paper is not specific to food packaging, but it is highly relevant to plastic packaging assessment. It identifies MCI, Value-Based Resource Efficiency (VRE), and the Circular Economy Indicator Prototype (CEIP) as the most relevant micro-level indicators for packaging circularity assessment and maps these indicators against CE guiding principles and Design for X approaches. This paper is useful because it helps narrow the indicator landscape for packaging applications, showing that many CE indicators developed for durable or repairable products are not directly applicable to single-use packaging formats.

Vadoudi et al. (2022) propose an adapted MCI for multilayer plastic packaging and compare circularity outcomes with LCA results. This paper should be framed narrowly: it does not provide a complete CE monitoring framework, but it does make a methodological contribution by adapting an existing circularity indicator to multilayer plastic packaging. The adaptation introduces a utility factor based on polymer quality and reuse intensity. The paper is relevant because it highlights a recurring issue in circularity monitoring: mass-based circularity indicators may not capture the quality loss and downcycling potential of recycled polymers. It also shows that higher circularity does not necessarily improve every environmental impact category, reinforcing the need to interpret circularity and LCA results together.

Gonçalves et al. (2024) propose an MFA-based circularity assessment approach for plastic packaging and apply it to Portugal. The approach covers the full plastic packaging system from polymer production to post-consumption treatment, incorporates uncertainty analysis, and calculates eleven indicators with complementary scopes. These include recycled input rate, circular material use rate, collection rate, sorting rate, recycling rate, recycled potential performance, MCI and a modified MCI that accounts for production losses. This paper is important because it distinguishes between different points in the material system. Collection, sorting, recycling output and recycled input are not equivalent, and conflating them can overstate circularity.

6.2.1.3 Agri-food supply-chain and social assessment frameworks

Veloso et al. (2025) propose the CE@AFSC framework for assessing CE strategies in agri-food supply chains. This is not a dedicated food-packaging framework, but it is directly relevant to food packaging because packaging is one of the CE strategy areas within agri-food supply chains. The framework was developed through analysis of sustainability reports from companies across production, processing, distribution and valorisation stages. The authors identify CE strategies across the 5Rs and select 31 GRI indicators suitable for measuring, supporting or controlling CE strategies. They also propose additional agri-food-specific disclosures: avoided food waste, food waste identification and management, reverse logistics, circular packaging design and regenerative farming. The circular packaging design disclosure is particularly relevant because it links packaging to a broader agri-food reporting system rather than treating packaging as an isolated product.

Haslinger et al. (2025) propose guidelines for selecting and inventorying social life cycle assessment indicators for circular flexible plastic packaging. This paper does not assess material circularity or

environmental performance directly. Its contribution is social assessment: it develops procedural steps for identifying stakeholders, selecting impact subcategories, prioritising indicators and preparing inventory data for S-LCA. The case focuses on flexible plastic packaging in a European circular economy context and prioritises nine social indicators for entry-level assessment. This paper is relevant because CE monitoring of packaging systems may introduce new activities and risks across collection, sorting, pretreatment, purification and packaging production, which are not captured by material-flow indicators alone.

6.2.1.4 Macro-level monitoring and LCA guidance

Mayer et al. (2019) propose a macro-level monitoring framework for economy-wide material loop closing in the EU28. This framework is not food-packaging-specific and should not be treated as directly applicable to food packaging without adaptation. Its relevance is conceptual and methodological: it links material extraction, use, waste, recycling, downcycling and secondary material inputs through a mass-balanced approach. It also emphasises that CE monitoring should not only measure the degree of recycling but also the scale of material throughput and whether loop closing contributes to absolute reductions in resource use.

Nordahl & Scown (2024) provide methodological recommendations for LCA of recyclable plastics in circular systems. This is a guidance paper, not a CE indicator framework. Its contribution is to clarify how LCA study design can alter conclusions for recyclable plastics, especially through choices around functional unit, system boundaries, counterfactual scenarios, feedstock variability, preprocessing, closed-loop versus open-loop systems and material substitution. The authors recommend looking beyond greenhouse gas emissions and including metrics such as fossil carbon balance, net landfill diversion and avoided plastic leakage. For food packaging CE monitoring, this guidance is important because circularity indicators need to be consistent with the assumptions used in environmental assessment.

6.2.2 Non-framework/tool/guideline papers offering useful insights for CE monitoring

A second group of papers does not provide a dedicated CE monitoring framework, tool or guideline for food packaging. However, these papers are essential because they identify the conditions that determine whether circularity claims are meaningful in practice. They contribute evidence on food-contact safety, contamination, real recycling performance, recycle quality, material design, food waste, technological feasibility, and policy/reporting gaps. These papers therefore help define what a credible monitoring approach should consider, even when they do not themselves propose the monitoring structure.

6.2.2.1 Food-contact safety, contamination and preservation constraints

Geueke et al. (2018) review chemical safety aspects of commonly used recycled food packaging materials, including plastics, paper and board, aluminium, steel and multilayer materials. The paper shows that recycling can increase levels of potentially hazardous chemicals in packaging and, after

migration, in food. This is critical for CE monitoring because food packaging circularity cannot be evaluated only through recycled content or recyclability. A recycled material stream that cannot meet food-contact safety requirements may have limited relevance for closed-loop food packaging applications.

Franz & Welle (2022) further develop the food-contact safety perspective by reviewing the European approach to post-consumer recyclates in new food packaging applications. Their review focuses on safety assessment criteria, especially those developed by European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) for direct food-contact applications. The paper is useful because it clarifies that closed-loop recycling in food packaging is not only a technical or material-flow issue but also a regulatory and toxicological issue. Indicators such as “recyclable” or “recycled content” therefore require qualification: for food packaging, the question is not only whether material can be recycled, but whether it can be safely recycled back into food-contact applications.

Matthews et al. (2021) review the implications of the EU plastics strategy for food safety. Their paper highlights that multilayer food packaging can provide strong food protection, shelf-life extension and food waste reduction, while also being difficult or uneconomic to recycle. The authors warn that substitutes for multilayer plastics must offer the same level of food protection if increased food waste, reduced shelf life or food safety risks are to be avoided. This is directly relevant to CE monitoring because a packaging material should not be assessed only by end-of-life circularity; its function in protecting food must also be part of the interpretation.

Poças & Do Céu Selbourne (2023) provide a broader review of drivers, barriers and measures for effective circular food packaging. Their discussion reinforces the importance of packaging functions — protection, containment, preservation, information and convenience — and notes that packaging optimisation requires balancing extra protection, shelf-life extension and food loss prevention against packaging waste generation. The value of this paper for CE monitoring is therefore contextual: it shows that “less packaging” is not automatically better if it undermines food preservation or safety.

6.2.2.2 Food waste and broader LCA boundaries

Kakadellis & Harris (2020) review LCA studies of biodegradable bio-based plastics for food packaging and argue for broader system boundaries that include food production and food waste. Their review finds that bioplastics may show environmental benefits for global warming potential and non-renewable energy use, but that these can be offset by agricultural inputs for raw material production. The authors also emphasise that the environmental footprint of food production and food waste can be significant, and that packaging performance in food waste minimisation is critical. This paper is especially important for bio-based packaging assessment because it cautions against evaluating material substitution without considering food waste prevention.

Blanc et al. (2019) assess the use of bio-based plastics in a raspberry supply chain using LCA, life cycle costing and externality assessment. The study does not propose a CE monitoring framework, but it provides a useful example of how different sustainability dimensions can lead to different conclusions. In the case examined, the bio-based plastic scenario had lower environmental and

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social impacts, while the conventional plastic scenario performed better according to classic economic assessment. This supports the need to interpret circular or bio-based packaging options across environmental, economic and social dimensions, rather than assuming that renewable material origin is sufficient evidence of superiority.

Anli Dino et al. (2025) review macroalgae-based bioplastics, including technical challenges, economic viability and sustainability aspects. The paper is not food-packaging-specific in the narrow monitoring sense, but it contributes feedstock-level insights relevant to bio-based packaging. It highlights macroalgae's potential advantages, including rapid growth, low land requirements and use of waste biomass, while also noting that economic competitiveness depends on cultivation, extraction and processing improvements. For CE monitoring, the paper is useful because it shows that bio-based feedstock claims should be accompanied by data on scalability, process energy, co-products, costs and material performance.

6.2.2.3 Real recycling performance, material flows and reporting gaps

López-Aguilar et al. (2022) provide a realistic material flow analysis (MFA) of end-of-life plastic packaging management in Spain. The study is particularly relevant for circular economy monitoring because it shows that reported recycling rates may differ substantially from recycling performance estimated through material-flow analysis. While official figures indicated recycling rates of 48–70%, the authors' MFA estimated that only 15% of plastic packaging was collected and only 11% was ultimately converted into recycled output. This distinction is important because circularity monitoring should track what happens to materials across collection, sorting and recycling stages, rather than relying only on aggregated reported recycling figures.

Otto et al. (2025) analyse packaging waste prevention indicators used in national waste prevention programmes and by the German food retail sector. The paper is important for circular economy monitoring because it shows that packaging prevention is often measured and communicated without sufficient clarity on definitions, baselines, targets or monitoring schemes. This makes it difficult to determine whether reported progress reflects actual material reduction, improved reuse, packaging optimisation, material substitution or changes in reporting scope. The study also highlights that secondary and transport packaging are poorly covered, although they can represent important material flows in food supply chains. It therefore supports the need for precise indicator definitions, transparent system boundaries and clear monitoring logic, especially for terms such as “reduction” and “prevention”, which may refer to different actions with different circularity implications.

Voukkali et al. (2023) review waste metrics in the CE context. This is a broad CE waste-metrics paper rather than a food-packaging-specific framework. Its relevance is that it situates packaging monitoring within the wider landscape of CE tools, including KPIs, LCA, MFA, multi-criteria analysis, environmental management systems, quality protocols and digitalisation. The paper reinforces that CE monitoring remains fragmented and that no single tool captures all relevant dimensions of waste and circularity performance.

6.2.2.4 Recyclate quality, design for recycling and recycling technologies

Golkaram et al. (2022) propose the Quality Model for Recycled Plastics (QMRP), which estimates a single quality value for recycled plastics based on degradation, mixing, contamination and application-specific material property requirements. Although QMRP is a model and indicator, it is not a CE monitoring framework for food packaging; in this context it is more coherent to treat it as a contribution to one monitoring dimension: recyclate quality. Its relevance is that recycled material should not be counted only by mass. The ability of recyclate to substitute virgin material depends on whether it meets the quality requirements of the intended application.

Keller et al. (2022) examine how recyclability affects the LCA of packaging through a Design for Life Cycle approach. The study is based on non-food plastic packaging, so it should not be generalised directly to food packaging without caution. However, its findings are transferable at the level of design features: dark colour, material compounds, insoluble adhesives and large labels reduced recyclability, and lower recyclability was associated with higher carbon footprint in the assessed scenarios. The paper is useful because it links design-level recyclability attributes to environmental outcomes.

Chaudhari et al. (2023) assess solvent-based dissolution–precipitation recycling of waste PET using process simulation, techno-economic analysis and LCA. The paper is not a circularity monitoring framework, but it provides process-level evidence that recycling technologies differ substantially in economic and environmental performance. In the case examined, the anti-solvent process produced higher GHG emissions than fossil virgin PET, while evaporation and cooling approaches reduced GHG emissions by about 50%. This indicates that CE monitoring should not treat a recycling technology category as automatically circular or sustainable; process configuration, energy demand, yield, solvent recovery, contamination assumptions and economics matter.

Rumetshofer & Fischer (2025) discuss design for recycling, specifications, sorting and information-based tracking technologies for post-consumer mechanical recycling of plastics. This paper is not a CE monitoring framework, but it is useful for defining enabling conditions. It highlights that high-quality recycling depends on design choices, clear specifications, sorting efficiency and technologies such as digital watermarks. For food packaging monitoring, this suggests that theoretical recyclability should be distinguished from detectability, sortability, stream compatibility and recyclate quality.

De Pilla et al. (2024) examine product development based on recycled plastic from pesticide packaging through a short-supply-chain perspective. Although this is not food packaging and involves a different contamination context, it provides useful insights into supply-chain organisation, decontamination requirements and local circular value creation. It is relevant mainly as an analogy for the system conditions that enable circularity: reverse logistics, actor coordination, regulatory constraints and reliable treatment of contaminated packaging streams.

6.2.2.5 Broader plastic waste and single-use packaging context

Ncube et al. (2021) provide an overview of plastic waste generation and management in food packaging industries. It gives useful background on the scale and management of food packaging plastic waste, especially the role of single-use packaging and the need for stakeholder involvement across reduction, reuse and recycling. Its main contribution for CE monitoring is to reinforce that packaging circularity depends on waste management systems and stakeholder coordination, not only material choice.

Arijeniwa et al. (2024) review single-use plastic waste in the food and beverage industry through a CE lens. Despite the title using the term “framework”, the paper is better treated here as a review of strategies and technologies rather than a dedicated monitoring framework for food packaging CE assessment. It is useful for identifying broad CE strategies for single-use plastic reduction, recovery and reuse in the food and beverage sector, but it does not provide the kind of operational monitoring structure needed for this work’s framework/tool category.

6.2.3 Cross-literature synthesis

The review shows that the framework/tool/guideline literature and the non-framework literature on the CE monitoring provide different but complementary contributions. The framework/tool/guideline papers provide structured assessment approaches: food-packaging-specific sustainability frameworks, design-stage tools, plastic-packaging circularity indicators, MFA-based circularity assessment, agri-food supply-chain indicator frameworks, S-LCA indicator-selection guidelines, macro-level material-flow monitoring and LCA guidance. However, none of these papers alone provides a fully integrated CE monitoring framework for food packaging that simultaneously covers packaging function, bio-based or recycled inputs, actual end-of-life performance, food-contact safety, environmental impacts, recyclate quality, sorting feasibility and agri-food supply-chain embeddedness.

The non-framework papers show why such integration is necessary. Food-contact safety studies demonstrate that recycled content and closed-loop claims are constrained by migration, contamination and regulatory approval. Food waste and LCA studies show that packaging circularity must be interpreted in relation to food protection and system boundaries. MFA studies show that reported recycling rates can differ substantially from actual recycled output and that polymer type and packaging format matter. Recyclate-quality and design studies show that material recovered by mass may not be functionally equivalent to virgin material. Technology assessment papers show that recycling pathways vary in environmental and economic performance. Policy and indicator studies show that many communicated packaging indicators lack clarity, baselines, targets or monitoring schemes.

The main result of the review is therefore not that a single ready-made CE monitoring framework for food packaging already exists. Rather, the literature provides a set of partial building blocks. For a robust CE monitoring approach, product-level circularity indicators need to be combined with material-flow accounting, LCA-compatible assumptions, food-packaging functionality, food-contact safety constraints, recyclate quality assessment, and supply-chain-level reporting considerations.

6.4 Application of the reviewed frameworks and insights to the ViSS product system

6.4.1 Relevance of the reviewed literature for the ViSS PHBV value chain

The reviewed literature is relevant to the ViSS product system because it provides complementary perspectives for assessing circularity, rather than a single ready-made framework that can be transferred directly. The ViSS solution combines several circularity-relevant features that are often addressed separately across circular economy, food packaging and bioplastics research: residue-based feedstock use, microbial PHBV production, food packaging functionality, intended recyclability, intended biodegradability, sorting protocol development and comparison with a fossil-based polypropylene benchmark. This combination makes ViSS a useful application case for a broader food packaging circularity monitoring approach. PHBV offers a promising biopolymer route for food packaging, particularly when produced from food industry residues through microbial fermentation. However, the circularity of the system depends not only on the material being bio-based, but also on how the feedstock is sourced and converted, whether the packaging fulfils its food protection function, and whether end-of-life pathways such as recycling and biodegradation are technically and practically achievable.

The most coherent application of the reviewed literature is therefore to use the identified frameworks, tools and evidence as complementary building blocks for circularity monitoring. Food-packaging sustainability frameworks clarify the need to assess circularity alongside packaging function and food loss prevention. Plastic-packaging circularity indicators provide methods for evaluating material flows and end-of-life potential. Material flow analysis (MFA)-based approaches show how to distinguish between design intentions and actual circular material flows. Food-contact safety studies indicate where circularity claims may be constrained by contamination and migration risks. Design-for-recycling and sorting studies show that end-of-life circularity depends on detectability, sortability and infrastructure compatibility, not only on material properties.

This is particularly important for ViSS because the solution is still under development. The purpose of applying the reviewed frameworks and insights should not be to produce a single definitive circularity score. Instead, the application should identify which aspects of circularity are already supported by available evidence, which remain design intentions, which require scenario-based assessment, and which depend on future value-chain and waste-management conditions.

6.4.2 Transferability of reviewed frameworks, tools and guidelines to the ViSS product system

The food-packaging-specific frameworks are directly transferable to ViSS because they show that packaging circularity should be assessed in relation to packaging function. Pauer et al. propose a methodological framework for environmental assessment of food packaging structured around three sustainability aspects: direct environmental effects of packaging, packaging-related food losses and waste, and circularity. They also emphasise that food packaging protects food from physical, chemical and biological influences, supports distribution, prevents product losses, and provides information to consumers. For ViSS, this means that PHBV circularity should not be

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assessed only through material origin, recyclability or biodegradability. The packaging must also perform its core food-packaging function. Circularity-oriented redesign would be counterproductive if it weakened preservation performance, increased product damage or shifted burdens from packaging waste to food waste.

Plastic-packaging circularity indicators are also relevant, but they require careful interpretation. Indicators such as recycled input rate, circular material use rate, collection rate, sorting rate, recycling rate, recycled potential performance and MCI can help structure the assessment of material circularity. However, Gonçalves et al. show that these indicators have different scopes: some capture production-side circularity, others capture end-of-life performance, and others attempt to capture overall circularity. Their MFA-based approach also distinguishes between collection, sorting, recycling, closed-loop recycling, open-loop recycling and recycled material actually incorporated into new products. For ViSS, this distinction is essential because intended recyclability does not automatically mean that PHBV will be collected, sorted, recycled and reintroduced into food packaging or other applications.

The MFA-based literature is particularly useful for moving ViSS monitoring from circularity claims to circular material flows. ViSS currently has clearer information on upstream and production-stage processes than on downstream commercial end-of-life pathways. Therefore, material-flow logic can first be applied to the part of the value chain for which data exist: residue collection, VFA production, PHBV fermentation, downstream processing and raw PHBV output. As the system develops, the same logic can be expanded to include packaging conversion, use, collection, sorting, recycling, composting or other end-of-life routes. Gonçalves et al. explicitly propose an approach that begins with goal and scope definition, identifies relevant flows and processes across the product lifecycle, collects data and assumptions, assesses uncertainty, calculates circularity indicators and uses scenarios to evaluate how changes affect circularity. This staged logic is well suited to the ViSS case because different parts of the PHBV system have different levels of maturity and data availability.

The design-for-recycling and sorting literature is transferable to the sorting-related part of the ViSS solution. IRIS is developing a sorting protocol to allow identification and sorting of PHBV packaging in future recycling facilities. This is highly relevant because Rumetshofer and Fischer emphasise that design for recycling, specifications and efficient sorting need to work together to achieve high-quality recycling. They also highlight the potential of advanced sorting technologies, including non-destructive spectroscopic methods, AI-driven systems and information-based tracking technologies such as digital watermarks, to improve sorting efficiency and feedstock quality. For ViSS, this means that the sorting protocol should be treated as a core circularity-enabling element, not only as a technical support activity.

The food-contact safety literature is transferable as a boundary condition rather than as a circularity indicator. Geueke et al. show that food packaging in a circular economy raises chemical safety questions because recycled materials can contain contaminants that may migrate into food. For ViSS, this means that potential recycling routes for PHBV must be interpreted through food-contact safety requirements. A PHBV material stream may be technically recyclable, but if the resulting recycle cannot meet food-contact requirements, it may only support open-loop recycling into

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non-food applications. This would still represent a possible circular route, but it should not be presented as equivalent to closed-loop food-packaging recycling.

The key literature findings pertinent for ViSS product system are presented in Table 30.

Table 30 Translation of literature review findings into circularity monitoring for the ViSS product system.

ViSS circularity dimension	What the literature shows	Application to ViSS	Tangible monitoring/action point
Residue-based input circularity	Circularity claims based on alternative inputs need to be supported by material-flow evidence, not assumed from bio-based or waste-based origin alone.	ViSS uses food industry residues as feedstock for PHBV production. This is a core circularity strategy, but its contribution depends on residue type, quantity, competing uses and conversion efficiency.	Create a feedstock circularity inventory covering residue type, source, quantity, alternative use, transport, pre-treatment and conversion yield.
Process circularity	MFA-based approaches show the importance of tracking inputs, outputs, losses and recycling or recovery points across the system.	PHBV production involves residue conversion, VFA production, fermentation, downstream processing and polymer recovery. Circularity can be lost through process inefficiencies or unmanaged side streams.	Develop a process-flow map covering material inputs, auxiliary inputs, PHBV yield, process losses, by-products and potential internal recovery loops.
Packaging design circularity	Food packaging sustainability frameworks show that circularity must be assessed together with packaging function, food protection and food-loss prevention.	PHBV packaging should not be evaluated only through bio-based origin, recyclability or biodegradability. It must also meet food-packaging performance requirements.	Use a design circularity matrix covering packaging mass, barrier properties, mechanical performance, shelf-life function, food-contact suitability, material efficiency and circularity attributes.

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Recycling pathway	Plastic-packaging circularity indicators distinguish between collection, sorting, recycling rate, recycled output and recycled input; these should not be conflated.	PHBV may be designed for recyclability, but actual recycling depends on detectability, sorting, compatible recycling routes and recovered material quality.	Create a recycling evidence sheet covering detectability, sorting efficiency, stream purity, recycling compatibility, output quality and closed-/open-loop application.
Biodegradation or composting pathway	Biodegradability is only meaningful when linked to defined conditions, standards, receiving environments and infrastructure.	PHBV biodegradability should be monitored separately from recyclability. It should not be treated as a generic end-of-life circularity claim.	Create a biodegradation evidence sheet covering test conditions, standards, receiving environment, time frame, infrastructure and degradation outcome.
Sorting and infrastructure compatibility	Design-for-recycling and sorting studies show that circularity depends on specifications, sorting efficiency and feedstock quality, not only material design.	ViSS includes development of a PHBV sorting protocol, which is central to whether PHBV can enter a circular material stream.	Include sorting detectability and stream compatibility as circularity-enabling indicators.
Food-contact safety	Food-contact recycling is constrained by contamination, migration and regulatory safety requirements.	A recyclable PHBV stream may not necessarily be suitable for closed-loop food-contact applications.	Distinguish closed-loop food-contact recycling from open-loop non-food recycling in the monitoring framework.
System-level circularity	Agri-food and MFA-based approaches show that circularity depends on value-chain coordination and data availability across actors.	ViSS links residue providers, PHBV producers, converters, food packaging users, sorting actors and future end-of-life operators.	Develop a data responsibility map identifying which actor provides which circularity data.

6.4.3 Circularity monitoring dimensions for the ViSS product system

6.4.3.1 Residue-based feedstock use and input circularity

The first circularity dimension of the ViSS product system is input circularity. The PHBV value chain uses food industry residues as feedstock, including residues that are converted into volatile fatty acids and then used for PHBV production. This directly corresponds to a CE strategy based on valorising residual biomass and reducing reliance on fossil-based feedstocks.

In practice, input circularity monitoring should quantify the proportion of PHBV feedstock derived from residues, the type and origin of the residues, and the conversion efficiency from residue stream to PHBV output. It should also clarify whether the residues are genuinely residual streams or whether they have competing uses. This distinction matters because using a residue does not automatically guarantee environmental or circularity benefits. The circularity value depends on whether the residue would otherwise be wasted, downcycled, used for energy recovery, used as animal feed, or valorised in another pathway. Therefore, the practical monitoring implication for ViSS is to document both the physical input flow and the counterfactual use of the residue stream.

A tangible application for ViSS is to develop a feedstock circularity inventory that records residue type, source sector, quantity used, pre-treatment requirements, alternative uses, transport distance, conversion yield and share of fossil or virgin inputs avoided. This would make the circular input claim more robust and provide data that can be linked with environmental and economic assessment.

6.4.3.2 PHBV production process and process circularity

The second dimension is process circularity. ViSS does not only substitute one material for another; it develops a production route in which food industry residues are converted through microbial processes into PHBV. The circularity of this route depends not only on the origin of the feedstock, but also on how efficiently residues are converted into usable polymer and how much waste, loss, energy demand and auxiliary input are generated during the process.

Process circularity monitoring should therefore include indicators such as feedstock-to-product yield, losses during VFA production, fermentation and downstream processing, use of auxiliary materials, generation of side streams, and opportunities for internal recovery or valorisation. This is where circularity monitoring can function as a practical design tool. Low yields, high process losses or difficult-to-manage side streams would indicate opportunities for process optimisation. Conversely, improvements in fermentation efficiency, downstream recovery, or internal reuse of process outputs would strengthen the circularity case.

A tangible application for ViSS is to build a process-flow map that links each production stage to measurable circularity parameters: inputs, outputs, losses, by-products, waste flows and possible recirculation points. This would allow the monitoring framework to identify where circularity gains are achieved and where they are lost within the production process.

6.4.3.3 Packaging design, functionality and design circularity

The third dimension is design circularity. The reviewed food-packaging literature makes clear that circular food packaging must be effective, efficient, safe and circular. Pauer et al. explicitly position packaging-related food losses and waste alongside direct packaging impacts and circularity, and note that inadequate packaging can cause food degradation, transport damage or consumer-stage losses.

For ViSS, this means that PHBV design should be assessed against both circularity and food-packaging functionality. Monitoring should not only ask whether PHBV is bio-based, recyclable or biodegradable. It should also ask whether the PHBV packaging provides suitable mechanical strength, barrier performance, shelf-life protection, processability, food-contact suitability and material efficiency for the intended application. These criteria are not secondary to circularity; they determine whether the material can function as food packaging in the first place.

A tangible application for ViSS is to integrate circularity indicators into the eco-design process. For example, packaging concepts could be assessed against a design matrix covering packaging mass, share of residue-based material, additives and coatings, mono-material or multi-material structure, barrier function, mechanical properties, food-contact compatibility, recyclability, biodegradability and sorting detectability. This would help avoid design choices that improve one circularity attribute while weakening another essential performance criterion.

6.4.3.4 End-of-life pathway assessment: recyclability, biodegradability and sorting

The fourth dimension is end-of-life circularity. ViSS aims to design PHBV packaging for both recyclability and biodegradability, but the reviewed literature suggests that these should be monitored as separate pathways rather than combined into a single circularity claim. Recyclability refers to retaining material value in a technical cycle, while biodegradability or compostability refers to biological transformation under defined conditions. Each pathway requires different evidence, infrastructure and indicators.

For the recycling pathway, monitoring should distinguish between theoretical recyclability, detectability, sortability, recycling process compatibility, recycled output quality and final application of the recovered material. Gonçalves et al. show why this distinction matters: collection, sorting, recycling and recycled input are separate indicators, and a high value for one does not guarantee a high value for the others. For ViSS, the development of a PHBV sorting protocol is therefore central. Without reliable sorting, technical recyclability is unlikely to translate into actual circular flows.

For the biodegradation or composting pathway, monitoring should specify the relevant conditions: industrial composting, home composting, soil biodegradation, marine biodegradation or another defined environment. The term “biodegradable” should not be used as a general end-of-life circularity indicator unless the expected environment, time frame, standard and infrastructure are clearly defined. In practical terms, ViSS should treat biodegradability as a pathway-specific property rather than as a generic circularity outcome.

A tangible application for ViSS is to develop separate end-of-life evidence sheets for recycling and biodegradation. The recycling sheet would include detectability, sorting efficiency, contamination risks, recycling process compatibility, output quality and possible closed- or open-loop applications. The biodegradation sheet would include test conditions, relevant standards, receiving environment, required infrastructure and expected degradation outcomes. This would make the end-of-life claims more precise and defensible.

6.4.3.5 Value-chain integration and system-level circularity

The fifth dimension is system-level circularity. ViSS is not only a material innovation; it is a value-chain configuration linking residue providers, bioprocessing, polymer production, packaging conversion, potential food packaging users, sorting technology providers and future waste-management actors. This broader system dimension matters because circularity depends on actor coordination and data availability across the value chain.

The reviewed literature shows that circularity monitoring becomes more meaningful when it can connect product-level indicators to material-flow and supply-chain-level information. Gonçalves et al. emphasise full lifecycle material-flow coverage, while Pauer et al. show that food packaging assessment needs to include both packaging effects and food-related consequences. For ViSS, this means that monitoring should be designed so that data from different actors can be progressively added: residue suppliers, VFA producers, PHBV producers, converters, food packaging users, collection and sorting operators, recyclers or composting operators.

A tangible application for ViSS is to define a circularity data responsibility map. This would specify which actor should provide which data: residue quantities and origin, process yields, formulation and additive information, packaging conversion losses, food-packaging performance, sorting test results, end-of-life route assumptions, recovery rates and recovered material quality. This would support both internal improvement and future reporting needs.

6.4.4 Applicability of circularity indicators across the maturity of the ViSS system

The applicability of the reviewed findings depends on the maturity and data availability of each part of the ViSS product system. Some circularity dimensions can already be monitored with available or near-term data. These include residue-based feedstock use, production process inputs and outputs, PHBV yield, process losses, early packaging design features, material properties, intended recyclability and biodegradability, and development of the sorting protocol.

Other dimensions should be treated with caution because they currently depend on assumptions, future infrastructure or downstream value-chain development. These include actual recycling rates, closed-loop recycling into food packaging, collection rates, sorting rates in real facilities, composting or biodegradation outcomes under operational conditions, avoided food waste during use, and market substitution effects. The reviewed literature strongly supports this distinction. For example, Gonçalves et al. show that actual recycling performance depends on collection, sorting, recycling process efficiency and recycled material incorporation, not only on design claims.

For ViSS, this suggests a staged application of indicators. Current monitoring can focus on input, process and design-stage circularity. Scenario-based monitoring can then test alternative end-of-life pathways and value-chain configurations. Future monitoring should replace assumptions with measured data from packaging conversion, use, collection, sorting, recycling or composting once these stages become operational.

6.5 Circularity monitoring conclusions

Circularity monitoring for food packaging needs to move beyond generic claims of recyclability, biodegradability, bio-based content or waste-based feedstock use. These attributes can contribute to circularity, but they do not, on their own, demonstrate circular performance. Circularity needs to be evidenced through measurable information on material inputs, production processes, packaging design, use-phase functionality, end-of-life pathways and value-chain conditions.

Existing frameworks, tools and indicators provide important building blocks for monitoring food packaging circularity, but no single approach fully captures the requirements of an emerging PHBV-based food packaging system such as ViSS. Food-packaging-specific frameworks highlight the need to assess packaging function, food protection and food-loss prevention alongside circularity. Plastic-packaging indicators and material flow approaches clarify the importance of distinguishing between design-stage circularity, collection, sorting, recycling, recovered material quality and actual reintroduction into productive use. Food-contact safety considerations further show that technical recyclability is not necessarily equivalent to closed-loop food-contact recycling.

The ViSS PHBV product system illustrates the need for a staged and evidence-based approach. Some circularity dimensions can already be assessed with relatively strong evidence, including residue-based feedstock use, PHBV production process flows, process yields, early design features and sorting protocol development. Other dimensions, particularly downstream end-of-life performance, should remain scenario-based until operational data are available on packaging conversion, use, collection, sorting, recycling, composting, biodegradation and recovered material quality.

For residue-based input circularity, the use of food industry residues provides a strong starting point, but this should be substantiated through data on residue type, quantity, alternative uses, conversion efficiency and avoided fossil or virgin inputs. Residue valorisation should therefore be treated as a measurable circularity strategy, not as proof of circularity by default.

For end-of-life circularity, recyclability and biodegradability need to be assessed as distinct pathways. Recyclability depends on detectability, sorting, recycling compatibility and recovered material quality. Biodegradability or compostability depends on defined conditions, standards, receiving environments, treatment infrastructure and verified degradation outcomes. Combining these routes into a single circularity claim would reduce the precision and credibility of the assessment.

Sorting emerges as a critical enabling condition. For PHBV packaging to become a real circular material flow, it needs to be identifiable and separable within future waste-management systems.

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The development of a PHBV sorting protocol is therefore central to the circularity evidence base, because it helps bridge the gap between theoretical recyclability and practical recyclability under operational conditions.

Circularity monitoring should complement, not replace, wider sustainability assessment. Circularity indicators can show whether material flows are retained, recovered or redirected into higher-value uses, but they do not determine whether a system is environmentally, economically or socially preferable. Circularity improvements may involve trade-offs related to energy demand, auxiliary inputs, processing complexity, cost, infrastructure needs or social conditions across the value chain. For this reason, circularity monitoring should be interpreted together with environmental, economic, social and safety assessments.

Food packaging functionality also needs to remain central. A circular packaging solution is not robust if it compromises food protection, shelf-life performance, food-contact safety, processability, material efficiency or the prevention of food losses. Circularity monitoring for food packaging should therefore be embedded within a broader understanding of what the packaging is required to do in the food system.

The main limitation of the current assessment is that the ViSS PHBV value chain is still under development. This means that some circularity dimensions can be evaluated using available process, design and feedstock information, while others remain dependent on assumptions about future packaging applications, end-of-life infrastructure and value-chain actors. In particular, operational data on collection, sorting, recycling, composting, biodegradation, consumer handling and recovered material quality are not yet available. As a result, downstream circularity performance should be interpreted as potential or scenario-based rather than demonstrated performance.

A further limitation concerns the maturity of circularity assessment methods for food packaging. Existing indicators do not always capture the specific requirements of food-contact materials, packaging functionality, contamination risks, food-loss prevention or the distinction between technical recyclability and actual recycling. This creates a need for careful indicator selection and transparent interpretation. Circularity metrics should therefore be used as structured decision-support tools rather than as definitive performance scores.

Future research should focus on testing and refining food packaging circularity indicators using real product systems and measured value-chain data. For the ViSS system, priority areas include validation of PHBV sorting and detectability, assessment of recycling compatibility and recovered material quality, verification of biodegradation or composting outcomes under defined conditions, and evaluation of food-contact safety for potential circular pathways. Future work should also examine how PHBV packaging performs in use, including food protection, shelf-life effects and potential implications for food losses.

Further methodological development is also needed to connect circularity monitoring more systematically with LCA, life cycle costing, social assessment and Safe and Sustainable by Design evaluation. This would help ensure that circularity improvements are not assessed in isolation from

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wider sustainability trade-offs. Particular attention should be given to how circularity indicators can be updated as systems mature, how scenario-based assumptions can be replaced by measured data, and how results can be communicated transparently for policy, reporting and design decision-making.

Taken together, the findings indicate that future evaluation of food packaging systems requires a framework that is staged, evidence-based and capable of assessing circularity across material inputs, production processes, packaging functionality, use-phase performance, end-of-life pathways and value-chain conditions. Applied to the ViSS PHBV product system, this type of framework can help distinguish between evidence-backed circularity performance, design-stage potential and assumptions that require further validation. It can also support design decisions, avoid premature circularity claims, identify future data needs and build the evidence required for credible circularity performance as the PHBV packaging value chain matures. However, as shown in the application section, existing studies and assessment approaches already provide valuable insights into what should be monitored. They offer necessary components for the future development of a more holistic circular economy monitoring framework for food packaging, even if they do not yet provide such a framework in a complete form.

7 Recommendations and outlook for D6.15

The interim sustainability assessment presented in this deliverable is not an end in itself but a structured step in an iterative process of design improvement. Each assessment iteration is designed to generate evidence that feeds back into the development of the ViSS PHBV value chain generating actionable insights across the three sustainability dimensions: informing environmental and process design decisions, identifying social performance gaps, and revealing economic constraints, so that the final product and production system are progressively refined towards genuine sustainability. This chapter consolidates the key recommendations emerging from the environmental, economic, and social assessments conducted at D6.10, and outlines the methodological improvements to be implemented in the final assessment (D6.15, M47). Recommendations are formulated at two levels: immediate actions addressable within the current phase of the project, and forward-looking orientations to guide the design and configuration of the commercial-scale value chain.

7.1 Environmental dimension

The interim LCA results show that the current ViSS PHBV production system generates significantly higher environmental impacts than the fossil polypropylene benchmark across all assessed impact categories. These results must be interpreted in the context of the current development stage: the assessment covers a partial system boundary (cradle to raw PHBV, excluding use and end-of-life), relies on demo-scale data with inherent inefficiencies that will not persist at industrial scale, and reflects a process that is still actively being optimised. Taken in isolation, the absolute impact values would suggest an unfavourable environmental profile. Taken in trajectory, the picture is more nuanced and more informative.

Between the first assessment (D6.7) and this interim assessment, the ViSS process underwent significant redesign — most notably the elimination of the VFA separation step and the implementation of salty brine circulation and chemical purification rounds. These changes produced impact reductions of 75–93% in most categories from the solvent-reduced design iteration, and a further 40–90% reduction when VFA separation was removed and recirculation implemented, even as the system boundary was expanded to include electricity consumption. This trajectory of improvement is the most important finding of the interim LCA: it demonstrates that the SSbD-driven iterative redesign process is working, and that the environmental performance of the ViSS system is responsive to targeted process interventions.

This trajectory of improvement does not happen in isolation. The process changes documented between D6.7 and D6.10 are the result of a collaborative technical review conducted with each ViSS partner, in which redesign needs were identified jointly and potential solutions discussed. This iterative dialogue between sustainability assessment and technical development is precisely the mechanism through which the SSbD framework generates value: evaluation findings feed into process decisions, and process improvements feed back into the next assessment iteration. The

recommendations that follow build on this same process and are formulated with the transition to higher scale production in mind.

7.1.1 Process redesign recommendations

The following process-level improvements are recommended for implementation prior to or during the transition to demo-scale production:

- The most impactful environmental improvement lever identified is the continued reduction of chemical inputs. Fermentation yields should be further optimised to reduce substrate consumption per kilogram of PHBV produced. Chemical recirculation and regeneration strategies, already partially implemented, should be extended across additional process stages where technically feasible. Water recirculation deserves parallel attention as a resource efficiency measure with co-benefits for both environmental impact and operating cost.
- Electricity consumption, now included in the system boundary for the first time at D6.10, emerges as a significant impact driver alongside chemical use — together accounting for approximately half of total impacts. Transitioning to non-carbon electricity sources should be prioritised as the production system scales. The planned installation of solar panels at the demo facility is a step in the right direction and should be integrated into the demo plant design from the outset. Beyond the energy source, the energy efficiency of individual pieces of equipment should be a criterion in procurement decisions for the demo plant, as industrial-scale equipment typically offers substantially better energy performance than demo-scale equivalents.
- Glycol, sodium chloride, formaldehyde, and certain culture media ingredients were identified as the most impactful individual chemical inputs. These should be scrutinised specifically for substitution or reduction opportunities in the next process optimisation cycle.

7.1.2 Methodological improvements for D6.15

The final assessment should address several methodological limitations identified at D6.10:

- The extension of the system boundary to include the use stage and end-of-life of the PHBV packaging remains a key objective for D6.15, as these phases are essential for evaluating the environmental implications of PHBV biodegradability. Their inclusion will be contingent on the availability of sufficiently mature process data at the time of the final assessment.
- The benchmark used in this assessment is fossil polypropylene. In consecutive iterations, it may be worth considering additional benchmarks alongside the fossil polymer — not only in terms of polymer type but also accounting for quality and technical and mechanical properties relevant to packaging applications. This could require revisiting the functional unit to reflect material performance characteristics such as density or thickness, rather than mass alone as used in this assessment. Additionally, to unify the system boundaries between the VISS PHBV and any benchmark polymer, independent modelling of the benchmark LCA may need to be considered. These decisions will be evaluated in the context of the process maturity and data availability at the time of the final assessment.

- The lifecycle phases not covered at D6.10 — compounding, transformation and packaging, distribution, and use — will be incorporated into D6.15 where data availability permits, as additional value chain partners provide data through the demo plant phase.

7.2 Economic dimension

The interim LCC results show a total production cost of 2,206.15€ per kilogram of raw PHBV, with labour (51.1%), raw material acquisition (23.0%), and equipment (12.7%) as the three dominant cost lines, together accounting for 87% of total costs. These figures should not be read as indicative of the economic viability of the ViSS solution at commercial scale. At the current TRL, production costs are structurally conditioned by the small scale of operations: labour costs per unit of output are disproportionately high when a process is run by research staff at demo scale rather than by industrial operators in a continuous production environment; equipment costs reflect laboratory and demo-scale assets whose amortisation is spread over small production volumes; and process inefficiencies that disappear at scale are still fully visible in the cost structure. The relevant question at this stage is not whether the ViSS solution is competitive, but whether the cost structure reveals where the most significant improvement opportunities lie as the system scales.

In this respect, the interim LCC is informative. Between D6.7 and D6.10, total production costs fell by 99.3% — from 304,915.7€ to 2,206.15€ per kilogram — driven primarily by process improvements and by the correct adjustment of the functional unit for equipment and labour costs. This reduction mirrors the environmental improvement trajectory documented in the LCA and reflects the same underlying dynamic: as the process matures and becomes more efficient, both environmental impacts and costs decrease together. The alignment between environmental and economic improvement is a structural feature of the ViSS approach that should be actively leveraged in the next development phase.

7.2.1 Cost optimisation recommendations

- The cost structure identified at D6.10 provides a clear map of where optimisation efforts will have the greatest impact as the system transitions to demo scale. The three most costly processes — PHBV production (29.0% of total cost), conditioning (20.7%), and fermentation (15.0%) — together represent nearly 65% of total costs and should be the primary focus of process engineering efforts in the next development phase.
- Within these processes, labour and equipment costs are the dominant drivers, both of which are expected to decrease substantially with scale. Labour costs in particular reflect the current R&D context, where operations are carried out by research and technical staff whose salary profiles differ significantly from those of industrial plant operators; this structural difference will translate into notable cost reductions as production moves to demo and commercial scale. Equipment costs similarly reflect demo-scale assets whose amortisation is spread over small production volumes and will benefit from the greater throughput and energy efficiency of industrial-scale equipment.
- The chemical reduction measures recommended in the environmental dimension (Section 7.1.1) are directly relevant here: reducing chemical inputs lowers raw material costs

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simultaneously with environmental impacts, reinforcing the case for prioritising recirculation and regeneration strategies. This convergence of environmental and economic objectives is an important signal — improvements in process chemistry are not trade-offs but co-benefits.

- Environmental externality costs are currently marginal (25€, representing 1.1% of total cost) and incompletely accounted for — reflecting only a fraction of the environmental costs and none of the environmental benefits associated with the ViSS system. Should the system boundary be extended in D6.15 to include the end-of-life phase, positive externalities associated with the bio-based and biodegradable nature of PHBV packaging are expected to become visible: these may include avoided costs associated with plastic waste management, reduced microplastic pollution, and the displacement of fossil-based materials. In that case, the net externality balance — accounting for both negative environmental costs and positive avoided impacts — could be more meaningfully assessed, providing a more complete picture of the economic sustainability of the ViSS solution.

7.2.2 Methodological improvements for D6.15

- The comparison of the ViSS LCC against conventional products is planned for D6.15, subject to the availability of sufficiently mature process and cost data at the time of the final assessment. At D6.10, the gap between demo-scale costs and commercial-scale costs is too large to support reliable conclusions about the competitiveness of the ViSS solution relative to fossil-based alternatives.
- The applicability of the SSbD scoring system (0–4 scale) to the economic dimension will be evaluated for D6.15, contingent on the definition of an appropriate market benchmark and the availability of sufficiently reliable cost data for comparison. The possibility of incorporating a social LCC (sLCC) alongside the environmental LCC will also be explored, to capture the economic dimensions of social impacts across the value chain.

7.3 Social dimension

The social assessment conducted at D6.10 covers three organisations — all ViSS consortium partners involved in the R&D phase of the project — across two lifecycle phases: raw material sourcing, and production/fermentation. A key contextual factor shapes the interpretation of these results and the formulation of recommendations: the organisations currently assessed are research institutions, universities, and technology centres whose role in the value chain is specific to the development phase. The organisations that will eventually produce and commercialise PHBV at scale are likely to differ significantly in size, sector, and operational profile, and may present a substantially different social performance picture.

This dual reality defines the structure of the recommendations that follow. The first level addresses improvements that are actionable for the current consortium organisations within the remaining project lifetime — concrete steps that can be taken now to address identified gaps and flags. The second level translates the findings of the assessment into generalised social performance standards and orientations for the future commercial value chain — drawing on what the results reveal about which aspects are structurally important given the nature of PHBV production

processes, and what profile of organisations should be sought when building the commercial-scale chain.

7.3.1 Recommendations for current consortium organisations

The recommendations below draw on both assessment tracks — the SO-LCA, which evaluates organisational-level social performance against national reference data, and the S-LCA, which assesses social impacts attributable to the PHBV product across the value chain. Where both tracks point in the same direction, the recommendation is strengthened; where one track adds nuance to the other, this is noted explicitly.

Overall social performance across the three assessed organisations is strong in the Workers category, with four of five S-LCA indicators rated Good or Excellent, and SO-LCA results confirming performance above the national reference in wages, full-time employment, collective bargaining coverage, and absence of labour violations. The recommendations below focus on the areas where gaps or flags were identified across one or both tracks.

- The first recommendation concerns community engagement. Two organisations (Org 1 and Org 2) have no community grievance mechanism in place, triggering Flag 1 — Critical under S-LCA indicator LC3. Both organisations are recommended to establish an accessible and documented channel through which community members can raise concerns related to their operations. This does not require a complex system — a designated contact point, a clearly communicated procedure, and a documented response process are sufficient to meet the minimum threshold.
- On occupational health and safety, one organisation (Org 3) has not yet conducted or documented risk assessments specific to PHBV production/fermentation operations, nor incorporated these operations into its existing audit cycle, triggering Flag 2 — High Concern under S-LCA indicator W4.2. This organisation is recommended to complete PHBV-specific process risk assessments, and to ensure that PHBV operations are explicitly covered in its next H&S audit cycle.
- On environmental management, one organisation (Org 3) has no environmental management system in place. While this does not trigger a formal flag given the organisation's operational profile, it is recommended that the organisation identify and document any processes with significant community impact potential. If such processes are identified, the implementation of a basic EMS — even without formal certification — is recommended as a measure of good practice.
- On equal opportunities, the SO-LCA shows an average gender representation of 51.52% women across the three organisations — above the national reference of 46.5% — but with significant variation between organisations, one of which falls below the national benchmark at 33.3%. The S-LCA adds further nuance: gender pay gap monitoring is absent in two organisations, and gender representation in decision-making roles shows imbalances in one organisation. Both organisations without pay gap monitoring are encouraged to begin voluntary tracking as a proactive measure. Gender representation in decision-making should also be monitored, especially in Org 3 where the gap between women's representation and the sector pipeline baseline, while not triggering a formal flag, remains a point of attention.

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- On sustainability governance and CSR, the SO-LCA reveals a systematic absence of formal sustainability strategies and CSR policies across all three organisations — a result aligned with the national average but nonetheless an area for improvement. None of the three organisations conduct supplier audits, and only one has a formal fair price policy. Consortium partners are encouraged to take steps towards formalising their sustainability commitments — even at a basic level — as this will strengthen their position as references for the social performance standards expected of future commercial value chain participants.
- On workforce integration, both tracks identify gaps in migrant worker integration. The SO-LCA shows that formal integration mechanisms are absent in two of three organisations despite the presence of migrant workers, and the S-LCA confirms an Insufficient product-level score for LC2. Organisations with migrant workers in their PHBV-related operations are recommended to implement at minimum basic integration support — legal and administrative assistance is the most impactful first step, as already applied by one organisation.
- On supplier relationships and regional sourcing, all three organisations apply consistent 30-day payment terms (VC1, Good), which is a positive practice to maintain. Regional supplier spending (VC2) is Insufficient at product level, driven by the low regional sourcing of two organisations. While regional sourcing is not a mandatory requirement, consortium partners are encouraged to explore opportunities to increase local procurement where technically and economically feasible, both as a contribution to local economic development and as a step towards alignment with SSbD principles.

7.3.2 Recommendations for future value chain participants

The results of the D6.10 social assessment — across both the SO-LCA and S-LCA tracks — taken together with the characteristics of PHBV production processes, define a set of social performance orientations that should guide the selection and engagement of organisations for the commercial-scale value chain. These are not prescriptive requirements at this stage, but evidence-based standards derived from the assessment findings and from what the nature of the production system demands.

- Public sustainability reporting and CSR formalisation (S1) scored Inadequate across all three current organisations in both assessment tracks — a result that is contextually expected given that all are SMEs with no mandatory reporting obligation and broadly aligned with the national average. However, organisations that join the commercial value chain as manufacturers, transformers, or distributors of PHBV packaging are likely to be of a scale and profile that brings them within the scope of sustainability reporting frameworks. Future value chain participants are strongly encouraged to adopt recognised reporting frameworks — such as GRI, EMAS, or ISO 26000 — as a condition of participation, and to have formalised CSR policies that extend to their supplier relationships. The absence of supplier audits across all current consortium organisations, identified in the SO-LCA, highlights a gap that commercial-scale participants should be expected to address: supplier audit mechanisms are an important instrument for ensuring that social performance standards cascade through the supply chain rather than remaining confined to the directly assessed organisations.

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- Community engagement mechanisms (LC3) should be treated as a baseline requirement for any manufacturing organisation joining the value chain. The production of PHBV involves fermentation and chemical processing operations that may generate community-relevant impacts — odours, noise, waste streams — particularly at industrial scale. An accessible, documented grievance mechanism is a minimum standard of responsible community relations and should be a criterion in the selection of future value chain partners. Beyond reactive grievance mechanisms, future participants involved in manufacturing phases are encouraged to allocate dedicated resources to the promotion of community health — an area where the SO-LCA reveals a systematic absence across all current consortium organisations, and one that will become more material as production scales and community exposure increases.
- Environmental management systems (LC1) should similarly be a baseline expectation for organisations involved in manufacturing and transformation phases. At industrial scale, the community impact potential of PHBV production operations is substantially higher than at demo scale, and a certified or structured EMS — ISO 14001 or EMAS — provides the framework needed to identify, monitor, and mitigate those impacts systematically.
- Process-specific health and safety risk assessments (W4) — including assessments explicitly covering PHBV production and fermentation operations — should be a non-negotiable requirement for organisations involved in production phases. The fermentation, separation, and extraction processes involved in PHBV production carry specific occupational risks that generic H&S systems may not adequately capture. Future value chain participants should be able to demonstrate that their H&S management systems explicitly cover the process operations relevant to PHBV production.
- Regional sourcing strategies (VC2) should be actively encouraged in the design of the commercial value chain. The current Insufficient score reflects the specific supplier configurations of R&D-phase organisations, which are not necessarily representative of what a commercial-scale value chain would or could achieve. Prioritising regional suppliers for raw materials and processing inputs would contribute to local economic development, reduce supply chain carbon footprint, and strengthen the territorial embedding of the ViSS business model — all consistent with the SSbD and circular bio-economy principles underpinning the project.
- Integration support for workers with linguistic barriers (LC2) and local employment (LC4) both scored Insufficient at product level, reflecting the current workforce composition of R&D organisations. As production scales and the workforce profile shifts towards industrial operators, these indicators will become more operationally relevant. Future value chain participants operating in regions with significant migrant worker populations should have documented integration support programmes in place. Local employment should be prioritised where the labour market allows, particularly in the phases with the highest labour intensity.

7.3.3 Methodological improvements for D6.15

Several methodological improvements are planned for the final social assessment, subject to data availability and the evolution of the project.

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- The activity driver will transition from the universal worker-hours proxy used at D6.10 to category-specific drivers where data is available: procurement spend for Value Chain Actors, taxes attributed to PHBV operations for Society, and units sold for Consumers. This transition will improve the accuracy and interpretability of the weighted aggregation and will be implemented progressively if the relevant data becomes available from consortium partners and from the commercial-scale value chain configuration.
- The lifecycle coverage of the S-LCA will be extended to include phases not assessed at D6.10 — use, and end of life— where data becomes available through the demo plant phase and the engagement of additional value chain partners.
- The Consumers category (CO1 and CO2) remains non-applicable at D6.10 as no consumer-facing PHBV packaging exists in a market context. The indicator framework and data collection instruments are ready and will be applied as soon as the product reaches a stage where consumer-facing packaging is available and testable. Similarly, the Society indicator S2 (End-of-Life Pathway Design) will be assessed in D6.15 once the technical documentation of the product's end-of-life compatibility is sufficiently developed.
- The SO-LCA track will be maintained in D6.15 to preserve longitudinal comparability with D6.7 and D6.10. The dual-track framework — SO-LCA for organisational comparability and S-LCA for product-level assessment — will continue to serve complementary purposes, with the S-LCA track progressively incorporating the methodological improvements developed and validated through this interim assessment.

7.4 Circularity monitoring

The following recommendations translate the key findings of the literature review developed in Section 6 into concrete actions for the ViSS value chain.

Recommendation 1: Bio-based origin should not be used as a proxy for circularity.

The use of food industry residues provides a strong circularity basis for the ViSS PHBV system, but the claim should be substantiated through quantitative evidence. Relevant data include the type and quantity of residue streams used, their alternative or competing uses, the conversion efficiency from residue to PHBV, and the extent to which virgin or fossil-based inputs are avoided. The residue-based route should therefore be monitored as a circularity strategy whose performance depends on measurable material flows, rather than treated as circular by definition.

Recommendation 2: Recyclability and biodegradability should be monitored as separate end-of-life pathways.

Both may be relevant for PHBV, but they require different forms of evidence and should not be merged into a single circularity claim. Recyclability requires evidence on detectability, sorting, stream compatibility, recycling process performance, and recovered material quality. Biodegradability or compostability requires evidence under defined conditions, including the relevant standard, receiving environment, time frame, and treatment infrastructure. Treating these

pathways separately would make the circularity assessment more precise and would help avoid overstating the conditions under which each route is valid.

Recommendation 3: Sorting should be treated as a core circularity-enabling condition.

For PHBV packaging to become a real circular material flow, it must be identifiable and separable within future waste-management systems. The development of a PHBV sorting protocol should therefore be integrated into circularity monitoring through indicators or evidence fields covering detectability, sorting efficiency, stream purity, contamination risk, and downstream material quality. This would allow the assessment to distinguish between theoretical recyclability and practical recyclability under operational sorting conditions.

Recommendation 4: Circularity indicators should be interpreted together with environmental, economic and social assessment results.

Circularity improvements may reduce fossil resource dependence, improve residue valorisation, or reduce waste generation, but they may also introduce trade-offs through energy demand, auxiliary inputs, process complexity, treatment costs, land-use implications, or new social conditions across the value chain. Circularity monitoring should therefore function as a decision-support layer within the wider sustainability assessment, rather than as a stand-alone judgement of whether the system is sustainable.

Recommendation 5: Measured flows should progressively replace design intentions.

At the current stage, the most robust circularity evidence concerns residue inputs, PHBV production, process characteristics, early material and packaging design features, and sorting protocol development. Claims about actual end-of-life circularity should remain scenario-based until data are available on collection, sorting, recycling, composting, biodegradation, or other operational end-of-life routes. This staged approach allows circularity monitoring to guide development while avoiding premature claims about performance that depends on future infrastructure and value-chain actors.

Recommendation 6: Food packaging functionality should remain central to the circularity assessment.

PHBV circularity is meaningful only if the packaging performs adequately in its intended food packaging application. Monitoring should therefore include functionality-related criteria such as food protection, shelf-life performance, safety, processability, mechanical performance, barrier properties, and material efficiency alongside circularity metrics. A packaging solution that improves circularity indicators but compromises food protection or increases food losses would not represent a robust circular economy solution for the food system.

Overall, the recommendations indicate that circularity monitoring for food packaging should be structured as a staged and evidence-based assessment that can be applied to emerging solutions such as ViSS. The ViSS product system illustrates why such a framework needs to distinguish between currently measurable aspects, such as residue-based input flows, PHBV production process

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data, design-stage circularity features and sorting protocol development, and aspects that require scenario-based or future value-chain data, such as collection, sorting, recycling, composting, biodegradation and recovered material quality. This distinction helps ensure that circularity claims remain proportionate to the available evidence. Applied to ViSS, a fit-for-purpose framework can support design decisions, clarify which assumptions still require validation, and identify the data needed to demonstrate credible circularity performance as the PHBV packaging value chain matures.

8 Conclusions

The interim sustainability assessment presented in D6.10 represents a meaningful step forward in the iterative evaluation of the ViSS PHBV value chain within the SSbD framework. Conducted at TRL 5–6, this second assessment builds on the baseline established in D6.7 and advances the understanding of the environmental, economic, and social sustainability profile of the ViSS solution — while acknowledging the constraints that characterise this stage of development.

The ViSS SSbD framework, established in D6.3, has proven well-suited to the objectives of the project. The iterative assessment structure — with defined milestones at M18, M33, and M47 — provides a coherent mechanism for tracking progress and feeding evaluation results back into design and process decisions. The improvements documented between D6.7 and D6.10 across all three dimensions are evidence that this mechanism is functioning as intended. Together with D6.8 and D6.9, this deliverable contributes to the verification of **Milestones 7, 8, 9 and 10** and to **Specific Objective 9** of the ViSS DoA. MS7 and MS8 are supported by the sustainability evidence base for the PHBV value chain and demo plant operation at M33, including the SSbD redesign recommendations that constitute the “SSbD safe strategies” referred to in the DoA. MS9 is supported by the social assessment, which establishes a quantitative social readiness baseline across five stakeholder categories. MS10 is supported by the process and cost data confirming the operational status of the demo plant production chain at M33. With respect to SO9, D6.10 constitutes the second application of the SSbD evaluation framework established in D6.3, demonstrating through measurable improvements across all three dimensions that the iterative assessment mechanism is functioning as intended.

In the **environmental dimension**, the current ViSS PHBV production system still generates significantly higher impacts than the fossil polypropylene benchmark across all assessed categories. However, the trajectory between assessment iterations tells a more important story: targeted process redesign — including the elimination of the VFA separation step, solvent reduction, and the implementation of recirculation strategies — produced impact reductions of 75–93% in most categories relative to the initial design, with further reductions of 40–90% achieved through subsequent optimisation. This demonstrates that the SSbD-driven redesign process is generating measurable environmental improvements, and that the path towards a more competitive environmental profile is being actively pursued. The system boundary remains partial at this stage, and the inclusion of the use and end-of-life phases in future iterations will be essential for a complete assessment of the environmental implications of PHBV biodegradability. Recommendations for this dimension focus on continuing the optimisation of chemical inputs and energy efficiency as the system transitions to demo scale, while expanding the system boundary and benchmark scope in D6.15.

In the **economic dimension**, the total production cost of 2,206.15€ per kilogram of raw PHBV reflects the inherent inefficiencies of demo-scale operations and should not be interpreted as indicative of commercial viability. The 99.3% cost reduction achieved between D6.7 and D6.10 — driven by process improvements and functional unit corrections — mirrors the environmental

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improvement trajectory and underlines the alignment between environmental and economic optimisation in the ViSS approach. Labour, raw material acquisition, and equipment costs together account for 87% of total costs, providing a clear map of where efficiency gains will be most impactful as the system scales. A comparison with conventional products will be conducted in D6.15 when process maturity and data availability permit. Recommendations for this dimension point towards prioritising cost reduction in the three most resource-intensive processes — PHBV production, conditioning, and fermentation — and leveraging the convergence between environmental and economic improvement as the process matures.

In the **social dimension**, results are encouraging overall, with strong performance in the Workers category across both the SO-LCA and S-LCA tracks. Wages, full-time employment, and collective bargaining coverage all perform above the national reference, and no fundamental labour rights violations were identified. The S-LCA, introduced as a product-level track at D6.10, adds important nuance: community engagement mechanisms are absent in two organisations (triggering critical flags under LC3), public sustainability reporting is absent across all three, and regional sourcing and local employment remain areas for improvement. These findings serve a dual purpose: they provide actionable recommendations for the current consortium organisations, and they establish the social performance standards that should guide the selection and engagement of future commercial-scale value chain participants. Recommendations for this dimension are structured at two levels — immediate corrective actions for current consortium organisations, particularly around community grievance mechanisms and PHBV-specific H&S risk assessments, and forward-looking social performance standards for the future commercial value chain, including sustainability reporting, environmental management systems, and regional sourcing strategies.

Circularity monitoring for food packaging must move beyond generic claims, requiring measurable, evidence-based data across material inputs, production, design, use-phase, end-of-life, and value-chain conditions. For systems like ViSS PHBV, a staged approach is needed: some dimensions (e.g., residue-based feedstock, production flows) can be assessed now, while downstream performance (e.g., recycling, composting) remains scenario-based until operational data is available. Recyclability and biodegradability must be evaluated separately, with sorting protocols critical for practical recyclability. Circularity should be integrated with sustainability assessments (LCA, costing, social impact) to avoid trade-offs. Food packaging functionality—safety, shelf-life, food loss prevention—must remain central. Current limitations include immature methods and lack of operational data. Future work should validate PHBV sorting, recycling compatibility, biodegradation, and food-contact safety, while linking circularity to broader sustainability. A holistic, adaptive framework is essential to distinguish evidence-backed performance from assumptions, supporting credible circularity as the value chain matures.

Across all three dimensions, the results of D6.10 confirm that the ViSS solution is on a development trajectory consistent with the SSbD ambition — not yet meeting the performance targets of the final assessment, but demonstrably moving in the right direction. The recommendations consolidated in Chapter 7 translate these findings into concrete actions for the remaining development phase, with the aim of ensuring that the final assessment (D6.15, M47) reflects a PHBV value chain that is genuinely safe, sustainable, and ready for commercial deployment.

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Annexes:

Annex 1 The processes used in the LCA model

The ecoinvent 3.10 process used in the LCA Sulca 5.3 model (summary table):

Material	ecoinvent 3.10 process
electricity	market for electricity, low voltage, ES
1,3-dioxanone	market for ethylene glycol, RER and market for formaldehyde, RER
Sodium chloride	market for sodium chloride, powder, GLO
IRIS culture media ingredient 3	market for fodder yeast, GLO
IRIS culture media ingredient 2	market for fodder yeast, GLO
Potassium hydroxide	market for potassium hydroxide, RER
MRS broth and bacterium	market for chemical, organic, GLO
Sugar rich liquor waste	-
Bones and feathers	-
Potassium chloride	market for potassium chloride, RER
Calcium chloride dihydrate	market for calcium chloride, RER
Sodium hydroxide	market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state, RER
Potassium hydrogen phosphate	market for potassium carbonate, GLO, market for potassium hydroxide, GLO, and market for phosphoric acid, industrial grade, without water, in 85% solution state, GLO
sodium bromide	market for chemical, organic, GLO
Methanol	market for methanol, RER
Hydrochloric acid	market for hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state, RER
Sodium bicarbonate	market for sodium bicarbonate, RER
Manganese sulfate	market for manganese sulfate, GLO
Magnesium sulfate	market for magnesium sulfate, GLO
Distilled water	market for tap water, Europe without Switzerland
Iron(III) chloride	market for iron(III) chloride, without water, in 40% solution state, GLO

Annex 2: Questionnaires to organizations in ViSS value chain for the So-LCA

Purpose & Confidentiality disclosures

This questionnaire is intended to gather the required information to perform the Social Organizational Life Cycle Assessment entitled in the ViSS project under the Task 6.4.

The data you provide through this questionnaire will only be used for the ViSS project purposes, under no circumstances will be passed on to third parties. This data will be managed by José Benedicto Royuela & the staff of SENIOR EUROPA S.L. (with commercial brand Kveloce). You can exercise your rights of access, modification or deletion of data by sending an email to jbenedicto@kveloce.com

Please include your name and surname: _____

Position in the organization: _____

General company information³⁹ Please complete the following gaps with the organization information:

Last accounting year	
Total company workforce in the last accounting year	
Nº of injuries in the last accounting year	
Total number of hours worked by employees in the last accounting year	

Human Resources Department

I2-W2 Indicate the living wage in euros per month (i.e., the monthly wage needed to cover the necessary living costs of an individual or family, for example the minimum living income) of the region/nation

I2-W3 Indicate the minimum wage (i.e., the lowest gross wage a full-time worker can be remunerated in a specific country, defined by national law and legally binding) in the region in euros

I2-W4 Please indicate in euros the organisation average wage in nominal terms, per month in the last accounting year

I3-W5 Please indicate the number of full-time permanent staff in the organisation in the last accounting year

I4-W6 Please indicate the total number of women working in the workforce of the organisation in the last accounting year

³⁹ Please keep in mind when completing the questionnaire that all the information is referred to the last accounting year

I5-W8 Include the number of injured persons (work-related incident) in the last accounting year in your company

I5-W9 Does your company comply with the safety measures obligations required according to your applicable law?

Elija un elemento.

I6-W10.1 Has your organisation been sanctioned in the last accounting year for non-compliance with current legislation or labour regulations?

Elija un elemento.

I6-W10.2 If yes, how many? Please indicate the number of sanctions in the last accounting year:

I7-W11.1.1 Does your organisation has collective bargaining agreements signed at the moment?

Elija un elemento.

I.7-W11.1.2 If yes, are the collective bargaining agreement and meeting minutes available for workers (i.e., copies of collective bargaining negotiations and agreements are kept on file)?

Elija un elemento.

I7-W11.2.1 Are there labour organizations(trade union delegates) in the company?

Elija un elemento.

I7-W11.2.2 If yes, is their presence adequately supported? (i.e., availability of facilities to union, posting of union notices, time to exercise the representation functions on paid work hours)

Elija un elemento.

I7-W11.3 Are the employee/union representatives invited to contribute to planning of large changes in the company (such as launching a new department for example), which affect the working conditions?

Elija un elemento.

I7-W11.4 Do workers have access to a neutral, binding, and independent dispute resolution procedure?

Elija un elemento.

I1-W1 How many persons work, or provide services in your company under the menace of any penalty and from which the said person has not offered himself or herself voluntarily? Please indicate the number:

I8-W12. Indicate the number of sexual harassment incidents reported within the organization in the last accounting year

I3-LC3 Please complete the following gap with the required information

Number of immigrants in the _____
organization workforce in the
last accounting year

I7-LC10 Please indicate the total number of locally hired workers in the last accounting year (the local labour market has the characteristic of containing within its borders most of the residence-labour flows of its population.):

Finance and Administration Department

I1-VC1.1 Has your institution been sanctioned for unfair competition (anti-competitive behaviour)?

Elija un elemento.

I1-VC1.2 If yes, please indicate the number of sanctions in the last accounting year:

I2-VC3 Please indicate the following

{VC3.1} Number of hired _____
suppliers **audited** with regard
to social responsibility in the
last year accounting year

{VC3.2} Number of hired _____
suppliers in the last
accounting year

I3-VC4 Please, indicate how would you rate the relationship with the organization suppliers:

1	Coercive communication	2	3	4	5	6	Very fluent communication

I4-VC5 Please indicate the number of conflicts that arose due to the use of local intellectual property:

I2-S2 Indicate in euros the total amount of taxes (all the paid taxes including VAT, social security contributions, Tax on Economic Activities, Corporate income tax, IRPF) paid in the last accounting year

I3-S4 Please complete the following gaps with the required information:

{ I3-S4.1} Last accounting year _____
investment in euros in
technology development
and/or transfer

{ I3-S4.2} Last accounting year _____
total organisation investment
in euros

I5-LC6 Has your organization dedicated financial resources (in €) to strengthen community health (i.e., through shared community access to organization health resources)?

NO

I6-LC7 How diverse are the stakeholder engaged with the organization?

1	Not very diverse	2	3	4	5	6	Very diverse

I6-LC8 How many meetings have been done in the last accounting year with community stakeholders?

I6-LC9.1 How many volunteer-hours of organizational support have been provided for community initiatives?

I6-LC9.2 How many financial resources (in €) have been provided for community initiatives?

I7-LC11 Please complete the following gap with the required information:

{I7-LC11.1} Spendings _____
without taxes of the last
accounting year in euros on
locally based suppliers

{I7-LC11.2} Total amount of _____
spending without taxes on
suppliers (in euros)

AGREEMENTS & SPECIFIC PROGRAMMS

I2-VC2 Does your intuition has a Corporate Social Responsibility agreement?

Elija un elemento.

I4-W7 Do formal policies on equal opportunities exist in the organisation, such as Gender Equality Plan?

Elija un elemento.

I5-VC6 Does the organisation have a specific policy for deciding a fair price (i.e., a price that covers all the production costs and returns an acceptable profit margin)?

Elija un elemento.

I1-S1 DoNOes the organization has any public available document as promises or agreements on sustainability issues?

Elija un elemento.

I3-S3 Does you organisation has a technology transfer program, or any project related with results transfer?

Elija un elemento.

I1-LC1 Does your organization have a certified environmental management system?

Elija un elemento.

I3-LC4 Does the organization has any internal procedures to integrate migrant workers into the community?

Elija un elemento.

I1-C3 Does your organization have a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System such as ISO 9001:2015, British Retail Consortium (BRC), Halal, International Food Standard (IFS), ISO 10377:2013, etc.?

Elija un elemento.

I5-C7 Do you have internal management systems to ensure that clear information is provided to consumers on end-of life options (if applicable)?

Elija un elemento.

CONSUMERS

I8-LC12 Please indicate the number of legal complaints by the local community in the last accounting year received with regard to security concerns

I1-C1 Does your products have informative labels?

Elija un elemento.

I1-C2 How many consumer complaints have your organization received in the last accounting year referring to the quality of the commercialised products/services of the organization?

I3-C5 Please indicate the number of consumer complaints related to breach of privacy or loss of data within the last accounting year

I4-C6 Rate the effort of the organization on communicating all issues regarding its products and social responsibility in a transparent way towards consumers

1 Not very transparent communication	2	3	4	5	6 Very transparent communication

Annex 3: ViSS aspects used in Social Dimension assessment

In **green** preferred options (in **bold green** letters those that have had a score higher than 4,5 in WP6 GA workshop in 2024), in **red** less valued options and indicators that are not covered by the project manager questionnaire.

CATEGORY	ASPECT	INDICATOR	VISS 2024 GA workshop score	Included in survey to organizations	Used in assessment
Workers	Forced labour	Employment terms	3.32	No	No
		Forced Labour		No	No
	Fair salary	Living wage per month	4.23	Yes	No
		Minimum wage, per month		Yes	No
		Organisation average wage, per month		Yes	Yes
	Working hours	Flexibility	3.73	No	No
		Full-time staff		Yes	Yes
	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Gender equality	4.12	Yes	Yes
		Equal opportunities policies		No	No
	Health and safety	Occupational safety measures	4.62	Yes	Yes
		Lost time injury frequency rate		Yes	Yes
	Social benefits, legal issues, social security	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	3.77	Yes	Yes
	Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Trade unions density	4.23	No	No
Collective Bargaining Agreement		Yes		Yes	
Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported	3.56	Yes	Yes	
Value chain actors	Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	3.82	Yes	Yes
	Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	3.91	Yes	Yes
		Suppliers audit		Yes	Yes
	Supplier relationships	Suppliers' communication relationship	3.68	Yes	Yes
	Wealth distribution	Fair price definition	4.05	Yes	Yes
	Respect intellectual property rights	Number of property rights infringements	-	Yes	No

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Society	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	4.22	Yes	Yes
	Contributions to economic development	Total taxation per capita	4.04	Yes	Yes
	Technology development	Technology transfer	4.48	Yes	Yes
		Investments in technology development/ transfer		Yes	Yes
	Corruption (value chain actors)	Corruption	3.39	No	No
Poverty alleviation	Poverty alleviation programme	3.48	No	No	
Local community	Access to material resources	Environmental management system	3.70	Yes	Yes
	Access to immaterial resources	Community education initiatives	3.22	No	No
	Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate	3.61	Yes	Yes
		Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community		Yes	Yes
	Cultural heritage	Funding dedicated to support and promote cultural heritage	3.13	No	No
	Safe and healthy living conditions	Promotion of community health	4.74	Yes	Yes
	Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation	3.68	Yes	Yes
		Number of meetings with community stakeholders		Yes	Yes
Local employment	Workforce hired locally	4.39	Yes	Yes	
	Spending on locally based suppliers		Yes	Yes	
Secure living conditions	Security complaints by the community	3.96	Yes	Yes	
Consumers	Health and safety	Labelling	4.68	Yes	Yes
		Consumer complaints		Yes	Yes
		Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System		Yes	Yes
	Feedback mechanism	Presence of consumers feedback mechanism	3.27	Yes	No
	Transparency	Organisation communication transparency	3.73	Yes	Yes
	End-of-life responsibility	Internal management systems	4.50	Yes	Yes
	Affordability	Potential price in comparison to market equivalent	4.24	No	No

Annex 4: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment

Value chain: food packaging industry (mesh bags, trays and bags and envelops)

WORKERS:

Fair salary

- Organisation average wage

Definition	Organisation average wage provides information about the mean monthly salaries to assess if the salary is enough to afford a decent standard of living. The indicator is given as the mean of monthly earnings of all employees in the organisation in nominal terms.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	€
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	PSILCA V3 <i>Modified (A2C D.7.5)</i>

Working hours

- Flexibility

Definition	Employee's self-perceived quantification of the extent to which the company provides adequate flexibility for work-life balance, rest and overtime. The indicator provides a synthetic, albeit mainly subjective, measure of different dimensions involved in work-life balance
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	Likert scale (1 to 6)
Data source	Questionnaire
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5

- Full-time staff

Definition	Indicator to see the ratio of full-time permanent staff
Calculation formula	Full-time permanent staff / total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method

Equal opportunities/Discrimination

- Gender equality

Definition	This indicator is intended to measure the percentage of women in the total workforce
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Calculation formula	Nº of women / total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method
- Equal opportunities policies	
Definition	This indicator is intended to note the presence of policies aimed at promoting equal opportunities between men and women, such as for example a Gender Equality Plan
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP
Health and safety	
- Occupational safety measures	
Definition	Indicator to assess whether the worker perceives occupational health measures as adequate.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1,2}
Data source	Questionnaire
Level	Organisation - worker
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP
- Lost time injury frequency rate	
Definition	Lost time injury frequency rate, the number of lost time injuries occurring in a workplace per 1 million hours worked.
Calculation formula	Nº of injuries x10 ⁶ / hours worked
Unit	[0, +∞]
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method
Social benefits, legal issues, social security	
- Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	
Definition	Number of sanctions imposed for non-compliance with current regulations
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1} {0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation

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Source PSILCA V3 *Modified*

Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining

- Collective Bargaining Agreement

Definition All workers and employers have the right to establish and to join organisations of their choice, without prior authorization, to promote and defend their respective interests, and to negotiate collectively with other parties. They should be able to do this freely, without interference by other parties or the state, and should not be discriminated against because of union membership.

Calculation formula NA

Unit {0,1}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method Methodological Sheets 2021 (UNEP)

Sexual harassment

- Sexual harassment incidents reported

Definition This indicator verifies whether the company register the number of sexual harassments incidents.

Calculation formula NA

Unit {1,2}
{0, +∞}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source Methodological Sheets 2021 (UNEP)

VALUE CHAIN ACTORS:

Fair competition

- Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour

Definition Presence of documented statement or procedures to prevent engaging in or being complicit in anti-competitive behaviour à not applicable à number of sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour

Calculation formula NA

Unit {0,1}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source A2C D.7.5 *modified*

Promoting social responsibility

- Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility

Definition Accreditation of Corporate social responsibility compliance

Calculation formula NA

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Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organization
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>
- Suppliers audit	
Definition	Percentage of suppliers the enterprise has audited with regard to social responsibility in the last year
Calculation formula	Number of hired suppliers audited/ number of suppliers hired
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Supplier relationships

- Suppliers' communication relationship

Definition	Existence of direct and satisfying relationship with suppliers.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	Likert 0-5
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organization
Source	A2C

Wealth distribution

- Fair price definition

Definition	Indicator to assess whether the price has been defined fairly: Definition of a fair price, i.e., a price that covers all the production costs and returns an acceptable profit margin; this indicator can be either qualitative and quantitative, the latter calculated through a detailed cost assessment
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, 1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Respect intellectual property rights

- Number of property rights infringements

Definition	This indicator is aimed to know if the company have had any type of conflict related with the use of intellectual property at local level
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organization
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

SOCIETY:**Public commitment to sustainability issues**

- **Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues**

Definition Indicator to assess if the company has a public document as promise or agreement on sustainability issues. This information might be complemented with an interview

Calculation formula NA

Unit {0, 1}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Contributions to economic development

- **Total taxation per capita**

Definition Total taxes paid in the last year, by all typologies, per capita (organisation). Taxes paid represent a proxy for the social contribution of each company

Calculation formula Taxation per capita= total taxes paid / total workforce

Unit €

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organization

Source A2C D.7.5 *modified*

Technology development

- **Technology transfer**

Definition Involvement in technology transfer program or projects. The indicator verifies whether the company is actively involved in technology transfer programs or projects

Calculation formula NA

Unit {0,1}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source A2C D.7.5 *modified*

- **Investments in technology development/ transfer**

Definition Share of investment in technology development and/or transfer over total investment. This indicator is a proxy for the effort made by the organisation in development and/or technology transfer, as well as the degree of technological innovation that a product incorporates

Calculation formula $pi=ni/Ni$

pi : proportion of investment in technology development and/or transfer over total investment items

ni : represents the investment in technology development and/or transfer (in euros) of the company

Ni : represents the total investment, all items (in euros)

Unit {0,1}

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Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

LOCAL COMMUNITY:

Access to material resources

- Environmental management system

Definition Presence of a certified environmental management system. The indicator verifies whether the company has a certified environmental management system.

Calculation formula NA

Unit {0,1}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source A2C D.7.5 *modified*

Delocalization and migration

- Immigrant workforce rate

Definition The immigration rate indicates social risks linked with a migrant inflow. The more migrants are in a certain region the more they influence the job market. Therefore, this indicator is intended to calculate the percentage of immigrants in the organisation workflow to be compared at regional level.

Calculation formula Number of immigrants in the workforce/ total workforce

Unit %

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source PSILCA V3 Modified

- Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community

Definition Indicator to assess if the company has any internal procedure for integrating migrant workers into the community

Calculation formula NA

Unit {0,1}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Safe and healthy living conditions

- Promotion of community health

Definition Indicator to assess if the company has dedicated resources to promoting community health

Calculation formula NA

Unit {0,1}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

D6.10 Interim sustainable by design assessment. v1.0

Source Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Community engagement

- Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation

Definition To which extent the organisation has a diverse stakeholder's community

Calculation formula NA

Unit Likert scale 1-6

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source Methodological sheets UNEP

- Number of meetings with community stakeholders

Definition This indicator is intended to know whether the relationship of the organisation with its community stakeholders is recurrent

Calculation formula NA

Unit {0, +∞}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source Methodological sheets UNEP (*modified*)

Local employment

- Workforce hired locally

Definition Proportion of locally hired workers over total new hires. The indicator is a proxy of the organisations' involvement with the local workforce

Calculation formula $pi=ni/Ni$
 pi : proportion of locally hired workers
 ni : number of locally hired workers
 Ni : total workforce

Unit {0,1}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source A2C D.7.5 *modified*

- Spending on locally based suppliers

Definition Proportion of spending on locally based suppliers over total expenditure on materials, equipment and services. The indicator is a proxy for the organisation's involvement with the local supply of goods & services, as well as for the weight of local suppliers in the manufacture of a product

Calculation formula $pi=ni/Ni$
 pi : proportion of spending on locally-based suppliers of the company
 ni : spending on locally-based suppliers (in euros) of the company
 Ni : total amount of spending on suppliers (in euros) of the company

Unit {0,1}

Data source Consultation with industrial partners

Level Organisation

Source A2C D.7.5 *modified*

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Secure living conditions

- Security complaints by the community

Definition	Number of legal complaints against the organisation with regard to security concerns by the local community
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,+∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

CONSUMERS:

Health and safety

- Labelling

Definition	Information available regarding features. The existence of labels in the product about its characteristics provides useful information to the consumer
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

- Consumer complaints

Definition	Number of consumer complaints in the last accounting year referring to the quality of the commercialised products/services of the organisation
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

- Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System

Definition	Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System such as ISO 9001:2015, British Retail Consortium (BRC), Halal, International Food Standard (IFS), ISO 10377:2013, etc.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

Transparency

- Organisation communication transparency

Definition	Organisation effort on communication all issues regarding its products and social responsibility in a transparent way
Calculation formula	NA

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Unit	Likert scale 0-6
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

End-of-life responsibility

- Internal management systems

Definition	This indicator is intended to know if the company has internal management systems that ensure that clear information is provided to consumers on end-of-life options for products. <i>In a product life cycle, end-of-life refers to product disposal, reuse, or recycling. In an environmental context, this concept is commonly referred to as extended producer responsibility. Product disposal can lead to significant environmental and social concerns.</i>
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1,2}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

Affordability

- Potential price in comparison to market equivalent

Definition	Price proposed comparable to conventional products in the market.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organization
Source	

Annex 5: S-LCA indicators: technical sheets

Workers

W1: Legal Compliance & Fundamental Rights

Indicator ID	W1
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Fundamental rights
Indicator Name	Legal Compliance & Fundamental Rights - Minimum Threshold
Observational Unit	PHBV operations (within organization)
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Serious violations in the last 3 years. Type: Two-level threshold gate (GATE 1: Absolute prohibitions, GATE 2: Serious violations)</p> <p>Function: Minimum acceptability verification for Workers category. Acts as mandatory precondition that must be satisfied before quality assessment (W2-W6) proceeds.</p> <p>Two-tiered verification of legal compliance across PHBV value chain through public enforcement records:</p> <p>GATE 1: ABSOLUTE PROHIBITIONS (Mandatory stop) Scope:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Child labor (workers <16 years) • Forced labor / Modern slavery • Human trafficking for labor • H&S violations causing death or permanent disability <p>Threshold: ANY verified instance = GATE 1 FAIL Action: IMMEDIATE assessment halt, supplier change REQUIRED, NO remediation option Prevalence: <0.1% in Spanish/EU context</p> <p>GATE 2: SERIOUS VIOLATIONS (Conditional stop/remediation) Scope:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic wage fraud (<70% SMI, >20% workforce affected OR 2+ years pattern) • Extreme working hours (>60h/week for >20% workforce, systematic) • Severe discrimination (>30% pay gap with harassment sanctions, systematic) • Social security fraud (>20% workers undeclared OR >6 months non-payment) <p>Threshold: SYSTEMATIC pattern (>20% affected OR 2+ years OR court "systematic")</p>

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	<p>Action: Conditional assessment, detailed remediation plan 6-12 months required Prevalence: 5-10% in Spanish context</p> <p>NOT GATE-WORTHY (handled by W2-W6 quality scoring):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payment delays <30 days, overtime issues (isolated) • Working hours 45-52h/week (not extreme) • Pay gaps 10-25%, minor H&S violations • Administrative compliance issues
Unit	Three-state outcome {GATE 1 FAIL, GATE 2 FAIL, PASS}
Reference Scale	No score
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	N/A
Weighting Basis	N/A
Threshold Gate	W1 IS the threshold gate (evaluated FIRST before W2-W6)

W2: Full-time staff percentage

Indicator ID	W2
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Working hours
Indicator Name	Full-time staff percentage
Observational Unit	PHBV operations
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Percentage of workforce in PHBV-specific activities with full-time permanent employment contracts. Includes: All workers with ≥ 35 hours/week and indefinite duration contracts.</p> <p>Excludes: Temporary, seasonal, and part-time workers; general corporate staff not attributable to PHBV.</p>
Unit	%
Reference Scale	<p>0: <40%</p> <p>1: 40-59%</p> <p>2: 60-74%</p> <p>3: 75-90%</p> <p>4: >90% (Spain: 88%)</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	GRADIENT: Weighted avg by worker-hours. IF any phase <40%: Flag + require justification in report

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Weighting Basis	$W2_product = \Sigma(W2_org \times Hours_org) / \Sigma(Hours_org)$
Threshold Gate	N/A
Threshold Gate	NO formal threshold. Flag if <40% (high precariousness). Document if <60% (below recommended)

W3: Equal Opportunities & Non-Discrimination (COMPOSITE)

Indicator ID	W3
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Equal opportunities/Discrimination
Indicator Name	Equal Opportunities & Non-Discrimination (COMPOSITE)
Observational Unit	Organisation
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Composite indicator (0-4 scale) assessing equality policies and practices through four weighted sub-indicators organized in two components:</p> <p>(1) Policy Component (50% weight): Formal non-discrimination framework including policy existence (W3.1: 20% weight) and systematic gender pay gap monitoring with corrective actions (W3.2: 30% weight).</p> <p>(2) Representation Component (50% weight): Gender representation outcomes including absolute percentage of women in decision-making roles (W3.3: 20% weight) and contextualized workforce gender composition versus sector baseline to identify systematic exclusion (W3.4: 30% weight).</p> <p>The weighting structure prioritizes outcome-oriented indicators (W3.2, W3.4) over process-only indicators (W3.1, W3.3), with W3.4 receiving highest weight as it provides the most robust evidence of organizational discrimination by controlling for sectoral pipeline constraints.</p>
Unit	Composite score (dimensionless)
Reference Scale	<p>0: Fail - Severe deficiencies across policy and representation</p> <p>1-1.9: Poor - Major gaps in either policy framework or representation outcomes</p> <p>2-2.9: Acceptable - Basic compliance but significant improvement needed</p> <p>3-3.9: Good - Strong performance with minor gaps</p> <p>4: Excellent - Comprehensive equality framework with demonstrated outcomes</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	STEP 1 - Calculate composite score per organization:

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	<p> $W3_org = (W3.1 \times 0.20) + (W3.2 \times 0.30) + (W3.3 \times 0.20) + (W3.4 \times 0.30)$ Where each sub-indicator W3.1-W3.4 is normalized to 0-4 scale before weighting. STEP 2 - Aggregate across lifecycle phases: $W3_product = \Sigma(W3_org \times Worker\text{-}hours_org) / \Sigma(Worker\text{-}hours_org)$ Where Worker-hours_org = total worker-hours in PHBV operations for that organization/phase per ton of PHBV produced. This ensures labor-intensive phases with poor equality performance are not masked by smaller, better-performing operations. </p>
Weighting Basis	<p> Policy Component (50% total): - W3.1 (Non-discrimination policy): 20% - W3.2 (Gender pay gap monitoring + actions): 30% </p> <p> Representation Component (50% total): - W3.3 (Women in decision-making): 20% - W3.4 (Gender representation vs pipeline): 30% </p> <p> Composite formula: $W3 = (W3.1 \times 0.20) + (W3.2 \times 0.30) + (W3.3 \times 0.20) + (W3.4 \times 0.30)$ </p> <p> JUSTIFICATION: The 50/50 balance between Policy and Representation reflects outcome-over-process principle while recognizing policy provides necessary structure. Within each component, higher weight assigned to outcome-oriented indicators: W3.2 includes corrective actions (not just monitoring), and W3.4 contextualizes representation against sector baseline (cleaner attribution of organizational practices). W3.4 receives highest individual weight (30%) as it provides most robust evidence of discrimination by controlling for sectoral pipeline constraints. </p>
Threshold Gate	<p> SOFT THRESHOLD: Flag if $W3_org < 1.5$ (failing basic equality measures - fewer than 2 of 4 elements adequately addressed). Require written explanation and improvement plan, not automatic disqualification. Flag if W3.4 gap > -25pp (severe segregation - workforce gender composition dramatically worse than sector baseline). Require detailed explanation of legitimate constraints (if any) or remediation timeline. </p>

W3.1: Non-discrimination policy

Indicator ID	W3.1
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Equal opportunities/Discrimination
Indicator Name	Non-discrimination policy
Observational Unit	Organisation
Is Sub-Indicator	Yes

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Measurement Detail	<p>Existence and quality of formal written non-discrimination policy covering gender, race, religion, disability, age, and other protected characteristics. Policy must be documented, communicated to workforce, and include enforcement mechanisms.</p> <p>Evaluation criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation: Policy must be formally documented (written policy, employee handbook section, or publicly available commitment document), not merely informal verbal commitments. • Coverage scope: Policy must explicitly address multiple protected characteristics: Minimum (for score >0): Gender + at least 2 other characteristics Comprehensive (for maximum score): Gender, race/ethnicity, religion, disability (physical and mental), age, sexual orientation, gender identity, and any additional characteristics protected under national law (e.g., political opinion, family status, genetic information) • Communication: Policy must be communicated to workforce through one or more channels: Employee handbook (physical or digital) Onboarding/induction training Posted in workplace (physical or intranet) Regular reminders/training sessions • Enforcement mechanisms: Policy must specify implementation procedures: How discrimination complaints are reported (channels, confidentiality) Investigation process (who conducts, timeline) Consequences/sanctions for violations Protection against retaliation for complainants <p>Attribution to PHBV: Organizational-level policy applies to all operations (not PHBV-specific). For multi-product organizations, assumes corporate HR policies apply uniformly across product lines. Policy existence attributed to PHBV proportionally to organization's engagement with PHBV production.</p> <p>Excludes: Generic "diversity and inclusion" statements without specific protected characteristics, aspirational commitments without enforcement mechanisms, policies that exist only on paper without any communication to workforce.</p>
Unit	{0, 0.5, 1.0}
Reference Scale	0: No formal non-discrimination policy 0.5: Basic written policy exists 1.0: Comprehensive policy with implementation evidence
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	<p>Rationale for worker-hour weighting: Ensures that labor-intensive phases with absent or weak non-discrimination policies are not masked by smaller operations with strong policies. A product's social performance should reflect the policy environment experienced by the majority of workers in its value chain.</p>

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	$W3.1_product = \frac{\Sigma(W3.1_org \times Worker\text{-}hours_org)}{\Sigma(Worker\text{-}hours_org)}$ <p>Where Worker-hours_org = total worker-hours contributed by organization to produce 1 ton of PHBV.</p>
Weighting Basis	N/A
Threshold Gate	No strict minimum (but absence = 0 points)

W3.2: Gender pay gap monitoring

Indicator ID	W3.2
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Equal opportunities/Discrimination
Indicator Name	Gender pay gap monitoring
Observational Unit	Organisation
Is Sub-Indicator	Yes
Measurement Detail	Frequency and quality of organizational gender pay gap analysis, and evidence of corrective actions when gaps are identified. Evaluates: Regular monitoring (annual minimum), transparent methodology, and documented corrective measures when gaps identified.
Unit	{0, 0.5, 1.0}
Reference Scale	0: No monitoring 0.5: Gap monitored regularly 1.0: Gap monitored + corrective actions documented if gap >5%.
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	<p>Rationale for worker-hour weighting: Pay equity monitoring affects all workers in organization. Labor-intensive phases without monitoring have greater social footprint (more workers without pay equity oversight). Weighting ensures product assessment reflects pay equity governance experienced by majority of value chain workers.</p> $W3.2_product = \frac{\Sigma(W3.2_org \times Worker\text{-}hours_org)}{\Sigma(Worker\text{-}hours_org)}$ <p>Where Worker-hours_org = total worker-hours contributed by organization to produce 1 ton of PHBV.</p>
Weighting Basis	N/A (component of composite)
Threshold Gate	No mandatory minimum, but regulatory note: LEGAL CONTEXT FLAG: If organization subject to mandatory pay gap reporting requirements (EU >100 employees, Spain >50 employees) AND scores W3.2 = 0, flag as potential legal non-compliance. EU Pay

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	Transparency Directive (https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/970/oj/eng)
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W3.3: Women in decision-making roles

Indicator ID	W3.3
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Equal opportunities/Discrimination
Indicator Name	Women in decision-making roles
Observational Unit	Organisation
Is Sub-Indicator	Yes
Measurement Detail	<p>Percentage of women in management, supervisory, or decision-making positions within the organisation.</p> <p>Includes: All positions with authority over budget allocation, personnel decisions (hiring, firing, promotions), or strategic/operational decisions. Encompasses all management levels: senior management (C-suite, directors), middle management (department heads, managers), and supervisory roles (team leaders, shift supervisors with personnel authority).</p> <p>Attribution to PHBV: When organizations produce multiple products, management practices are assumed to apply uniformly across all operations. The indicator is attributed to PHBV proportionally to the organization's engagement with PHBV production.</p> <p>Calculation: $(\text{Number of women in management positions} / \text{Total number of management positions}) \times 100$</p> <p>Excludes: Administrative support roles without decision-making authority, technical specialists without management responsibility, board members external to operations.</p> <p>Small organizations (<20 employees): Use "participation in strategic decision-making" instead of formal management titles, as small firms may lack hierarchical structure. Document decision-making participants (e.g., production planning meetings, investment decisions).</p>
Unit	Percentage (%), reported on 0-1 scale for aggregation: {0, 0.33, 0.66, 1.0}
Reference Scale	<p>0: <25% or >75% of women</p> <p>0.33: [25-35%) or (65-75%) of women</p> <p>0.67: [35-40%) or (60-65%) of women</p> <p>1: [40-60%) of women</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	<p>STEP 1 - Calculate percentage per organization:</p> $W3.3_org = (\text{Women in management} / \text{Total management}) \times 100$

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Weighting Basis	<p>STEP 2 - Apply scoring scale: Convert percentage to 0-1 score using reference scale thresholds</p> <p>STEP 3 - Aggregate across lifecycle phases to product level: $W3.3_{product} = \frac{\sum(W3.3_{org} \times Worker\text{-}hours_{org})}{\sum(Worker\text{-}hours_{org})}$ Where Worker-hours_{org} = total worker-hours in PHBV operations for that organization/phase per functional unit (ton of PHBV)</p> <p>STEP 4 - Normalize for W3 composite: $W3.3 \text{ normalized contribution} = W3.3_{product} \times 4 \times 0.20 = W3.3_{product} \times 0.80$</p>
Threshold Gate	<p>SOFT FLAG: If W3.3 = 0 (<15% women), flag as "potential severe glass ceiling" and require narrative explanation in assessment report. Not a hard stop, but triggers additional scrutiny.</p> <p>CONTEXT CHECK: Compare W3.3 result with W3.4 result. If W3.3 is low BUT W3.4 shows organization matches sector pipeline, this indicates sector-wide issue rather than organizational discrimination. Document this distinction clearly.</p>

W3.4: Gender representation vs pipeline

Indicator ID	W3.4
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Equal opportunities/Discrimination
Indicator Name	Gender representation vs pipeline
Observational Unit	Organisation
Is Sub-Indicator	Yes
Measurement Detail	Gap between actual gender representation in workforce and expected baseline from sector graduate pool or sector average. Calculation: Absolute difference between observed % female workers and sector benchmark. Evaluates whether gender imbalance reflects sector constraints or organizational practices.
Unit	Percentage points (pp) gap, reported on 0-1 scale for aggregation: {0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0}
Reference Scale	0: Gap >25pp below baseline (severe underrepresentation) 0.25: Gap 15-25pp below baseline (major underrepresentation) 0.5: Gap 5-15pp below baseline (moderate underrepresentation) 0.75: Gap ±5pp of baseline (matches sector availability) 1.0: Gap >5pp above baseline (exceeds sector availability)
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	Calculate gap per phase: (Actual % women - Expected baseline %). Expected baseline = % women graduates in relevant field OR sector

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	average. Score by gap size. Aggregate phases by worker-hours weighting
Weighting Basis	NA
Threshold Gate	Flag if gap >-25pp below baseline. Require explanation of legitimate reasons (new company, highly specialized role, geographic constraints)

W4: Occupational H&S Management System (COMPOSITE)

Indicator ID	W4
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	Occupational H&S Management System (COMPOSITE)
Observational Unit	Composite (see sub-indicators for details)
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Composite indicator (0-4 scale) assessing comprehensiveness and effectiveness of occupational H&S management across PHBV lifecycle.</p> <p>Composed of 3 sub-indicators (equal weight 33.3% each):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • W4.1: H&S management system presence • W4.2: Process-specific PHBV risk assessments • W4.3: H&S audit & continuous improvement cycle <p>Each sub-indicator scored {0, 0.5, 1.0}, then scaled $\times 1.333$ to reach max 1.33 per sub. Composite calculated at BOTH organization and product levels (mathematically equivalent approaches).</p>
Unit	Composite score (dimensionless)
Reference Scale	<p>Composite from 3 equally-weighted sub-indicators (33.3% each).</p> <p>SCALING FORMULA: $\text{Scaled_score} = \text{Raw_score} \times (4/3) = \text{Raw_score} \times 1.333$</p> <p>Final score = W4.1_scaled + W4.2_scaled + W4.3_scaled</p> <p>Total range: 0.0 (no H&S management) to 4.0 (excellent comprehensive system)</p> <p>Rating scale:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3.5-4.0: Excellent comprehensive system • 2.5-3.4: Good system with minor gaps • 1.5-2.4: Basic functional system • 0.5-1.4: Significant gaps • 0.0-0.4: Inadequate or absent

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Lifecycle Phase Applicability	See individual sub-indicator fiches for specific scoring
	All phases
Aggregation Method	<p>WORKER-HOURS WEIGHTED AGGREGATION (3 sub-indicators):</p> <p>Two mathematically equivalent approaches can be used:</p> <p>APPROACH A: Aggregate sub-indicators, then compose (recommended for dimensional analysis) STEP 1: Aggregate each sub-indicator to product level (worker-hours weighted) $W4.1_product = \Sigma(W4.1_org \times Hours_org) / \Sigma(Hours_org)$ $W4.2_product = \Sigma(W4.2_org \times Hours_org) / \Sigma(Hours_org)$ $W4.3_product = \Sigma(W4.3_org \times Hours_org) / \Sigma(Hours_org)$</p> <p>STEP 2: Scale each aggregated sub-indicator $W4.1_scaled = W4.1_product \times 1.333$ $W4.2_scaled = W4.2_product \times 1.333$ $W4.3_scaled = W4.3_product \times 1.333$</p> <p>STEP 3: Calculate product composite $W4_product = W4.1_scaled + W4.2_scaled + W4.3_scaled$</p> <p>APPROACH B: Compose at organization level, then aggregate (recommended for organization comparison) STEP 1: Calculate composite for each organization $W4_org = (W4.1_org \times 1.333) + (W4.2_org \times 1.333) + (W4.3_org \times 1.333)$</p> <p>STEP 2: Aggregate organization composites (worker-hours weighted) $W4_product = \Sigma(W4_org \times Hours_org) / \Sigma(Hours_org)$</p> <p>BOTH APPROACHES YIELD IDENTICAL PRODUCT-LEVEL SCORE due to linearity of operations.</p> <p>RECOMMENDATION: Calculate and report BOTH levels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization level: W4.1, W4.2, W4.3, and W4 composite per organization • Product level: W4.1, W4.2, W4.3 aggregated, and W4 composite for product <p>This dual reporting enables:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Quick organization comparison (W4 composite per org) 2. Detailed dimensional diagnosis (subs per org) 3. Product-level dimensional analysis (subs aggregated) 4. Overall product assessment (W4 composite product) <p>Rationale for worker-hours weighting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality metrics admit degrees (0.5 = functional minimum acceptable) • Labor-intensive phases have proportionally greater social impact • Weights by where workers actually exposed to H&S conditions
	Weighting Basis

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Threshold Gate	SOFT threshold: 80% lifecycle coverage, W4 ≥2.0 recommended. NO hard gate at W4 level (violations in W1).
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W4.1: Formal H&S system presence

Indicator ID	W4.1
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	Formal H&S system presence
Observational Unit	Organisation
Is Sub-Indicator	Yes
Measurement Detail	Presence of certified occupational health and safety management system (ISO 45001, OHSAS 18001) or equivalent documented system with defined procedures, responsibilities, and audit mechanisms.
Unit	{0, 0.5, 1.0}
Reference Scale	<p>0: No documented system OR missing ANY critical element 0.5: Has all 3 critical elements. Functional minimum system. 1.0: Complete system (7/7 elements See Methodological notes) OR ISO 45001 certified. Best practice system.</p> <p>CRITICAL ELEMENTS (mandatory for score >0): - #2: Risk assessment procedures - #3: Legal compliance register - #5: Emergency response plan</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	<p>Worker-hours weighting $\text{Product Score W4.1} = \frac{\sum(\text{Score}_{\text{org}} \times \text{Worker-hours}_{\text{org}})}{\sum(\text{Worker-hours}_{\text{org}})}$</p> <p>RATIONALE: Social impacts are proportional to where workers are employed. A phase with 100 workers has greater social impact than a phase with 10 workers, even if production volume is similar. Worker-hour weighting ensures labor-intensive phases are appropriately weighted versus capital-intensive automated phases.</p>
Weighting Basis	N/A (component of composite)
Threshold Gate	<p>YES: All 3 critical elements (Risk assessment, Legal register, Emergency plan) MUST be present. Missing any critical element → maximum score = 0. Organization cannot score >0 without these fundamental components.</p> <p>If any organization scores 0 à FLAG</p>

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W4.2: Process-specific risk assessments

Indicator ID	W4.2
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	Process-specific risk assessments
Observational Unit	PHBV operations
Is Sub-Indicator	Yes
Measurement Detail	Documented risk assessments specific to PHBV processes: feedstock handling (sugar waste, poultry residues), fermentation operations, solvent extraction (ethyl acetate), and polymer transformation. Must identify hazards, assess risks, and define control measures.
Unit	{0, 0.5, 1.0}
Reference Scale	0: Not documented OR generic only (no PHBV-specific content) 0.5: Process-specific risk assessments documented for SOME key PHBV operations At least 1 key process documented, but incomplete coverage 1.0: Process-specific risk assessments documented for ALL key PHBV operations relevant to this organization
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	Worker-hours weighting $\text{Product Score W4.2} = \frac{\sum(\text{Score}_{\text{org}} \times \text{Worker-hours}_{\text{org}})}{\sum(\text{Worker-hours}_{\text{org}})}$
Weighting Basis	N/A (component of composite)
Threshold Gate	YES: Risk assessments MUST be documented. Generic insufficient.

W4.3: H&S audit frequency & corrective actions

Indicator ID	W4.3
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	H&S management system audit & continuous improvement
Observational Unit	Organisation
Is Sub-Indicator	Yes
Measurement Detail	Frequency of systematic H&S management system audits (internal or external) and evidence of corrective actions implemented from audit findings.

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Unit	Audits verify that H&S procedures are implemented effectively, identify gaps in the system, and drive continuous improvement through corrective and preventive actions.
	{0, 0.5, 1.0}
Reference Scale	0: No systematic audits OR last audit >2 years ago No evidence of management system verification 0.5: Audits conducted but INCOMPLETE implementation: - Adequate frequency (annual/biennial) BUT no documented corrective actions OR - Corrective actions documented BUT audit frequency inadequate 1.0: Regular systematic audits (annual for high-risk operations; biennial for low-risk) WITH documented corrective actions implemented AND closure verified Complete audit-action-verification cycle
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	Worker-hours weighting Product Score W4.1 = $\frac{\sum(\text{Score}_{org} \times \text{Worker-hours}_{org})}{\sum(\text{Worker-hours}_{org})}$
Weighting Basis	N/A (component of composite)
Threshold Gate	RECOMMENDED: Annual audits for high-risk PHBV operations (solvent extraction, fermentation). Biennial acceptable for lower-risk operations (feedstock storage, packaging). Score 0 if >2 years without audit.

W5: Collective Bargaining Coverage

Indicator ID	W5
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Workers rights
Indicator Name	Collective Bargaining Coverage
Observational Unit	Organisation (but focused on PHBV operations)
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	Percentage of workers directly engaged in PHBV operations (production, processing, handling, quality control, storage) covered by collective bargaining agreements (company-level or sectoral). Collective bargaining coverage indicates workers have access to collective negotiation mechanisms for wages, working conditions, benefits, and dispute resolution beyond legal minimums. Coverage measured as proportion of PHBV workforce with CBA protection.
Unit	Percentage (%), reported on 0-4 scale
Reference Scale	0 points: 0% coverage 1 point: 1-25% coverage - Minimal coverage

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Lifecycle Phase Applicability	2 points: 26-50% coverage - Partial coverage 3 points: 51-75% coverage - Majority coverage 4 points: 76-100% coverage Near-complete to complete coverage
	All phases
	$W5_product = \frac{\sum(W5_org \times Worker\text{-}hours_org)}{\sum(Worker\text{-}hours_org)}$
	N/A
Threshold Gate	<p>SOFT THRESHOLD: If $W5_product < 2.0$ (less than half maximum, indicating <50% average coverage across value chain), flag as "limited collective bargaining protection in PHBV value chain - recommend supplier engagement on freedom of association and worker rights." Rationale: $W5 < 2.0$ indicates either:</p> <p>Complete absence of CBA at major lifecycle phases ($W5 = 0$), OR Partial coverage (<50% workers) at dominant phases</p>

W6: Organisation average wage

Indicator ID	W6
Stakeholder Category	Workers
Social Aspect	Fair salary
Indicator Name	Average Wage for product operations
Observational Unit	PHBV operations
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	Monthly average gross salary of all workers directly engaged in PHBV production, processing, and distribution activities. Includes: Base salary, regular bonuses, and fixed allowances. Excludes: Overtime pay, irregular bonuses, and workers in general corporate functions not attributable to PHBV.
Unit	€/month
Reference Scale	<p>0: <SMI (€1.323) 1: SMI - 1,2*SMI (€1.323 - €1.588) - Below Spanish legal minimum wage: Indicates labour law violation or informal employment 2: 1,2*SMI – 1,7*SMI (€1.588 - €2.249) - Legal minimum to modest premium: Covers basic subsistence but limited purchasing power 3: 1,7*SMI – 2,5*SMI (€2.249 – €3.308) - Good wage exceeding living wage: Provides comfortable living standard and economic security 4: >2,5*SMI (>€3.308) (Spain avg: €2,128/month) - Excellent wage significantly above living wage: High economic security with substantial discretionary income</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases

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Aggregation Method	$W6_product = \Sigma(W6_org \times Worker_hours_org) / \Sigma(Worker_hours_org)$
Weighting Basis	Worker-hours per ton PHBV: Weight=(Workers×Hours/ton)/Total_worker-hours. CRITICAL for fair assessment
Threshold Gate	<p>SOFT FLAGS for wage adequacy violations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FLAG 1 - CRITICAL: Below legal minimum (W6_phase < SMI, score 0) Trigger: Any lifecycle phase with average wage < €1,323/month Interpretation: Labor law violation. Immediate intervention required regardless of phase labor intensity. - FLAG 2 - HIGH CONCERN: Below living wage threshold (W6_phase < 1.7×SMI, score < 2) Trigger: Any lifecycle phase with average wage < €2,249/month Interpretation: Workers cannot meet basic needs adequately. Priority for improvement, especially if labor-intensive phase. <p>FLAGS DO NOT MODIFY W6_PRODUCT SCORE. Score calculated via worker-hour weighted average. Flags serve as diagnostic tool identifying specific phases requiring intervention independent of their contribution to overall score.</p> <p>Rationale: Small phases (e.g., 2% labor) below legal minimum still represent exploitation of workers in that phase. Flags ensure no violations are hidden by aggregation weighting.</p>

Value Chain Actors

VC1: Fair payment terms to suppliers

Indicator ID	VC1
Stakeholder Category	Value Chain Actors
Social Aspect	Supplier relationships
Indicator Name	Fair payment terms to suppliers
Observational Unit	Organisation (PHBV-scoped)
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Average payment term to suppliers, in days, self-reported by each organisation for goods and services directly attributable to product operations, as collected through the assessment survey (Q7.1.1).</p> <p>For this assessment: All PHBV-specific procurement (feedstocks, processing materials, chemicals, equipment, services) across the product lifecycle.</p> <p>Includes: All suppliers of raw materials and inputs for product operations as reported by the surveyed organisation.</p>

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Unit	Excludes: General corporate overhead not attributable to the product line; intra-group transactions between entities of the same corporate group.
	days
Reference Scale	<p>0: >90 days or systematic rejection</p> <p>1: 61-90 days</p> <p>2: 31-60 days (industry standard)</p> <p>3: 15-30 days</p> <p>4: <15 days or advance payment</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	<p>STEP 1 — Convert to reference scale: Convert each organisation's reported payment days (Q7.1.1) to a 0-4 score using the Reference Scale above: $\text{Score}_i = f(\text{payment_days}_i)$</p> <p>STEP 2 — Within-phase aggregation (if multiple organisations per phase): Calculate the worker-hour-weighted average score across all organisations within the phase: $\text{VC1_phase} = \frac{\sum (\text{Score}_i \times \text{worker_hours}_i)}{\sum \text{worker_hours}_i}$ Where i = each organisation evaluated within that phase.</p> <p>Note: Procurement-spend weighting would be preferable conceptually for this indicator, as organisations with higher procurement volumes have greater impact on supplier cash flows. However, spend-per-organisation data is not collected in the ViSS survey instrument. Worker-hour weighting is applied as the methodologically consistent and feasible alternative. Document this limitation in reporting.</p>
	<p>STEP 3 — Across-phase aggregation: Calculate the worker-hour-weighted average score across all lifecycle phases: $\text{VC1_product} = \frac{\sum (\text{VC1_phase}_j \times \text{worker_hours}_j)}{\sum \text{worker_hours}_j}$ Where j = each lifecycle phase with available data.</p>
Weighting Basis	N/A
Threshold Gate	No minimum threshold. Payment terms are a regulated commercial practice, not a fundamental right whose violation would invalidate the assessment. However, scores of 0 (>90 days systematic delay) should be flagged narratively as potentially unlawful practice under Ley 15/2010 and EU Directive 2011/7/EU.

VC2: Regional supplier spending

Indicator ID	VC2
Stakeholder Category	Value Chain Actors
Social Aspect	Supply chain localization

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Indicator Name	Regional supplier spending
Observational Unit	PHBV operations
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	Percentage of total procurement spend allocated to regional suppliers for PHBV production. Regional defined as: Suppliers located within 300km of production facility OR within Region of Murcia. Calculation: (Regional supplier spend for PHBV / Total PHBV procurement spend) × 100. Excludes: General corporate purchases not attributable to PHBV.
Unit	%
Reference Scale	0: <20% regional spend 1: ≥20 - <40% regional spend 2: ≥40 - <60% regional spend 3: ≥60 - <80% regional spend 4: ≥80% regional spend
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	If multiple companies in phase: weighted average by their total procurement value for PHBV operations. Calculate % regional spend for each organization, then aggregate
Weighting Basis	Procurement value per organization (within phase) Worker-hours per ton PHBV (across lifecycle phases)
Threshold Gate	No minimum threshold (regional sourcing encouraged but not mandatory)

Society

S1: Public sustainability documents

Indicator ID	S1
Stakeholder Category	Society
Social Aspect	Public commitment to sustainability
Indicator Name	Public sustainability reporting
Observational Unit	Organisation
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	Presence and quality of publicly available sustainability reporting following recognized standards (GRI, EMAS, CDP, ISO 26000). Evaluates: Publication existence, standard compliance, scope comprehensiveness, and update frequency for organizations across PHBV lifecycle phases.

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Unit	Score on 0-4 scale (dimensionless)
Reference Scale	<p>0: No public sustainability documentation</p> <p>1: Minimal sustainability info (website only, scattered)</p> <p>2: Structured sustainability report — no recognised standard</p> <p>3: Report following recognized standard (GRI Core, EMAS, CDP)</p> <p>4: Comprehensive report (GRI Comprehensive) AND/OR externally verified</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	<p>Calculate the worker-hour-weighted average score across all lifecycle phases:</p> $S1_{product} = \frac{\sum (S1_{org_j} \times worker_hours_j)}{\sum worker_hours_j}$ <p>Where j = each org/phase with available data.</p>
Weighting Basis	N/A
Threshold Gate	<p>No hard threshold. However, a soft flag applies:</p> <p>FLAG — CRITICAL OPACITY: Triggered when any lifecycle phase scores 0.</p> <p>Interpretation: An organisation with complete absence of public sustainability reporting in a phase that represents significant labour intensity signals a transparency gap that cannot be masked by good performance elsewhere. Flag does not modify product score but must be reported narratively.</p> <p>Priority: Scales with worker-hour weight of the flagged phase (HIGH if phase >50% of total worker-hours; MEDIUM if 25-50%; LOW if <25%).</p> <p>SME consideration: no reporting obligation</p>

S2: End-of-Life Pathway Design

Indicator ID	S2
Stakeholder Category	Society
Social Aspect	End-of-Life social impact
Indicator Name	End-of-Life Pathway Design
Observational Unit	Product
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>The highest-accessibility end-of-life pathway for which the product is certified or technically documented as compatible. Assessed based on the minimum level of infrastructure required to correctly manage the product at end of life — from specialised industrial infrastructure at one extreme to no infrastructure at the other.</p> <p>The score reflects the most accessible certified pathway available for the product. If multiple pathways are certified, the one requiring the least infrastructure determines the score.</p> <p>Includes: Any pathway for which the product holds a recognised certification or has documented technical compatibility — industrial</p>

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	<p>composting (EN 13432), home composting (ISO 17088 / EN 17033), anaerobic digestion, mechanical recycling, chemical recycling, reuse systems.</p> <p>Excludes: Incineration with energy recovery and landfill — these are residual options available for virtually all materials and do not represent a social benefit of product design.</p>
Unit	Score on 0-4 scale (dimensionless)
Reference Scale	<p>0 points: No certified or documented end-of-life pathway beyond incineration or landfill</p> <p>1 point: Compatible with at least one pathway requiring specialised industrial infrastructure</p> <p>2 points: Compatible with at least two pathways, at least one requiring only standard industrial infrastructure</p> <p>3 points: Compatible with existing standard municipal collection streams without dedicated infrastructure</p> <p>4 points: Compatible with domestic management — no infrastructure of any kind required</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	End-of-life phase (primary)
Aggregation Method	No aggregation required. Indicator evaluated directly at product level based on technical product characteristics and market infrastructure data. Score is assigned once per assessment period.
Weighting Basis	N/A
Threshold Gate	No hard threshold. Score 0 should be noted as a product design limitation.

Local Community

LC1: Environmental management system for community impact mitigation

Indicator ID	LC1
Stakeholder Category	Local Community
Social Aspect	Safe and healthy living conditions
Indicator Name	Environmental management system for community impact mitigation
Observational Unit	Product operations
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Assessment of the quality and comprehensiveness of an Environmental Management System (EMS) for managing operational impacts affecting the local community from product operations. Evaluates whether the organisation holds ISO 14001 or EMAS certification, or operates an equivalent documented system covering the nine essential elements listed in the survey instrument. For this assessment: all lifecycle phases producing potential community-affecting impacts — including air emissions/odours, noise, traffic, and waste — are in scope. Phases with</p>

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	negligible community impact potential (e.g., purely administrative operations, geographically dispersed end-of-life) may be assigned N/A with documented justification. Does not assess technical environmental performance (quantities of emissions, noise levels in dB): that is within the scope of Environmental LCA. This indicator measures the social dimension — whether adequate management systems exist to identify, communicate about, and respond to community-affecting impacts.
Unit	Score on 0–4 scale (dimensionless)
Reference Scale	<p>0 points: No environmental management system, OR unresolved serious community health or environmental complaints, OR documented regulatory violations affecting the local community in the past 12 months.</p> <p>1 point: Basic informal procedures addressing some environmental aspects; no systematic approach, no community engagement, minimal or no documentation.</p> <p>2 points: Documented procedures covering 3–5 of the 9 essential EMS elements; addresses at least one community-affecting aspect (air emissions, OR noise, OR traffic); limited community communication; some complaints management.</p> <p>3 points: ISO 14001 or EMAS certified EMS, OR comprehensive documented equivalent covering 6–8 essential elements; includes a formal community complaint system with response procedures; regular communication with the local community about operations and environmental performance; addresses the main community-affecting aspects relevant to the phase (emissions/odours, noise, traffic as applicable).</p> <p>4 points: ISO 14001 or EMAS certified EMS, OR fully documented equivalent covering all 9 essential elements; proactive community engagement (regular public reporting of environmental performance, open communication channels); zero unresolved complaints</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases with community impact potential
Aggregation Method	<p>Weighted aggregation by worker-hours: $LC1_product = \frac{\sum(\text{Score_phase} \times \text{Worker-hours_phase})}{\sum(\text{Worker-hours_phase})}$</p> <p>Where: Score_phase = score 0–4 assigned to each lifecycle phase Worker-hours_phase = total worker-hours per tonne of PHBV produced for that phase</p> <p>Rationale: Worker-hours is applied as the aggregation driver consistently across all stakeholder categories in this assessment for D6.10. Phases with greater labour intensity contribute proportionally more to the product score. This is a provisional proxy</p>
Weighting Basis	N/A
Threshold Gate	<p>SOFT FLAGS identify community impact management failures requiring intervention:</p> <p>🚩 FLAG 1 — CRITICAL: Inadequate management of high community-impact phase</p>

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<p>Trigger: Any phase with Score ≤ 1 that involves high-intensity VOC emissions, industrial-scale fermentation odours, continuous noise near residential areas, or solvent extraction/recovery processes.</p> <p>Interpretation: A phase with high potential to affect community health and quality of life operates without adequate environmental management. Worker-hours weighting alone may not prevent this from being partially attenuated in the aggregate if the phase is labour-light — hence the cap.</p> <p>Action: Product score capped at maximum 2,0 until all flagged phases achieve Score ≥ 2. Immediate intervention required.</p> <p>⚠ FLAG 2 — HIGH CONCERN: Unresolved complaints or regulatory violations</p> <p>Trigger: Any phase with documented unresolved serious community health or environmental complaints, OR regulatory violations affecting the local community in the past 12 months.</p> <p>Interpretation: The EMS has failed in its primary purpose — actual harm or unresolved conflict with the community is present regardless of system documentation quality.</p> <p>Priority scales with worker-hours intensity of the affected phase:</p> <p>HIGH: Phase represents > 50% of total product worker-hours MEDIUM: Phase represents 25–50% of total product worker-hours LOW: Phase represents < 25% of total product worker-hours</p> <p>Action: Assign Score = 0 to affected phase. Require documented corrective action plan with timeline. Score remains 0 until complaints are formally resolved or violations remediated.</p> <p>FLAGS DO NOT MODIFY THE PRODUCT SCORE independently of the aggregation formula, except for the Flag 1 cap (maximum 2,0) and the Flag 2 phase score override (Score = 0). Flags serve as a diagnostic tool surfacing phase-specific failures that aggregation might otherwise attenuate.</p>	
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LC2: Integration support for migrant workers in PHBV operations

Indicator ID	LC2
Stakeholder Category	Local Community
Social Aspect	Delocalization and migration
Indicator Name	Integration support for workers with linguistic barriers in product operations
Observational Unit	Product operations
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	Assessment of the quality and comprehensiveness of integration support programmes offered by organisations to workers whose primary working language differs from the local language of operations in product-related phases.

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	<p>The trigger for this indicator is the presence of workers with a primary working language different from the local language of operations (question 9.2.3), not migrant status per se. This reflects that the social impact measured — difficulties integrating into the local community and workplace — is driven primarily by linguistic barriers rather than by nationality or legal migration status. Question 9.2.1 collects migrant worker data under the ILO definition for contextual reporting purposes only.</p> <p>For this assessment: phases with no workers meeting the linguistic barrier criterion are assigned N/A and excluded from aggregation. The indicator evaluates six possible support elements: local language training, housing support, cultural orientation, legal/administrative assistance, cultural mediation, and family integration programmes.</p> <p>Does not assess employment outcomes for workers with linguistic barriers (wage gaps, promotion access, rights violations) — those are covered in Workers category indicators W1 (Legal Compliance & Fundamental Rights), W3 (Equal Opportunities & Non-Discrimination), and W6 (Average Wage for Product Operations).</p>
Unit	Score on 0–4 scale (dimensionless)
Reference Scale	<p>0 points: No integration support declared. Represents complete absence of organisational response to the integration needs of workers with linguistic barriers.</p> <p>1 point: Informal/ad-hoc support only, no formal documentation. Represents minimal good will without systematic commitment. Workers with linguistic barriers are largely left to manage integration independently.</p> <p>2 points: 1–2 support elements declared and formally documented. Represents a basic structured response. The organisation has acknowledged the need and formalised at least one element, but coverage remains limited.</p> <p>3 points: 3–4 support elements declared and formally documented. Represents good practice — a genuine programme addressing the main integration needs of workers with linguistic barriers.</p> <p>4 points: 5–6 support elements declared and formally documented. Represents excellent practice — comprehensive, formalised support covering virtually all identified integration dimensions.</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases where workers with a primary working language different from the local language of operations are present. Phases with no such workers are assigned N/A and excluded from aggregation.
Aggregation Method	<p>STEP1: Calculate migrant worker-hours per phase:</p> $WH_{\text{linguistic_phase}} = WH_{\text{total_phase}} \times (N_{\text{linguistic_phase}} / N_{\text{total_phase}})$ <p>Where:</p> <p>WH_total_phase = total worker-hours per tonne of product for that phase</p> <p>N_linguistic_phase = number of workers with primary working language different from local language (from question 9.2.2)</p> <p>N_total_phase = total number of workers in PHBV operations for that phase</p>

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Weighting Basis	<p>This assumes workers with linguistic barriers have the same average working hours as other workers in the same phase — a reasonable approximation for D6.10 given available data.</p> <p>STEP 2: Weighted aggregation</p> $LC2_product = \frac{\sum(\text{Score_phase} \times \text{WH_linguistic_phase})}{\sum(\text{WH_linguistic_phase})}$ <p>Where the sum runs only over phases with WH_linguistic_phase > 0.</p>
	<p>N/A — LC2 is not a composite indicator; it has no sub-indicators with differential weights.</p>
Threshold Gate	<p>SOFT FLAGS identify integration failures requiring intervention:</p> <p> FLAG 2 — HIGH CONCERN: Significant linguistic barrier workforce with no structured support Trigger: Any phase where workers with linguistic barriers represent > 15% of the phase workforce AND Score ≤ 1. Interpretation: A significant proportion of the workforce faces integration challenges without any structured organisational support, creating risk of social exclusion, workplace miscommunication, and community integration difficulties. Priority scales with WH_linguistic_phase intensity: HIGH: Phase represents > 50% of total LC2 product worker-hours MEDIUM: Phase represents 25–50% of total LC2 product worker-hours LOW: Phase represents < 25% of total LC2 product worker-hours Action: Recommend structured integration programme development. Priority proportional to share of workers affected.</p> <p>FLAGS DO NOT MODIFY THE PRODUCT SCORE independently of the aggregation formula, except for the Flag 1 phase score override (Score = 0). Flags serve as a diagnostic tool identifying phases requiring targeted intervention.</p>

LC3: Community grievance mechanism for PHBV operations

Indicator ID	LC3
Stakeholder Category	Local Community
Social Aspect	Community engagement
Indicator Name	Community grievance mechanism for product operations

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Observational Unit	Organisation
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Assessment of the accessibility and effectiveness of the grievance mechanism available to the local community for raising concerns about product operations. Evaluates five dimensions derived from the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (Principles 29–31): (1) accessibility — multiple channels, community awareness; (2) procedural clarity — documented process, complaint tracking; (3) responsiveness — timely acknowledgment, investigation, corrective actions; (4) transparency to complainants — process communication, outcome notification; (5) non-retaliation protection — explicit commitment protecting complainants.</p> <p>For this assessment: all lifecycle phases where operations may generate community-affecting impacts are in scope. Phases with no community interface (e.g., purely administrative operations) may be assigned N/A with documented justification.</p> <p>Does not assess the technical magnitude of environmental impacts — that is within the scope of Environmental LCA and LC1. This indicator measures whether the community has a functional, accessible channel to raise concerns and receive a response.</p>
Unit	Score on 0–4 scale (dimensionless)
Reference Scale	<p>0 points: No grievance mechanism exists for the community to report concerns about operations, OR mechanism exists but there is documented evidence of retaliation or intimidation against users, OR systematic ignoring of serious complaints (≥ 3 serious complaints over ≥ 6 months with no investigation, acknowledgment, or response)</p> <p>1 point: Informal ad-hoc complaint handling only; single channel (typically a manager's phone number); no documented procedure or systematic tracking; community has limited or no awareness of how to complain; inconsistent or very slow responses (> 90 days); no evidence of corrective actions taken.</p> <p>2 points: Basic grievance mechanism established with defined primary channel(s) (phone and/or email); some community awareness exists; complaints acknowledged and recorded; investigation occurs but responses often slow (60–90 days) or incomplete; some documentation maintained but not systematic; limited evidence of corrective actions.</p> <p>3 points: Good grievance mechanism with multiple accessible channels (phone, email, in-person, with anonymous option available); clear procedure documented and communicated to community through multiple means; consistent acknowledgment within defined timeframe (≤ 7 days); investigation and response typically within 30–60 days; documented records systematically maintained; clear evidence of corrective actions taken when complaints warranted; complainants informed of outcomes.</p> <p>4 points: Excellent grievance mechanism fully meeting UN Guiding Principles effectiveness criteria: highly accessible with multiple channels including anonymous option and proactive outreach to community about mechanism availability; transparent documented process with clear timeframes consistently met; highly responsive with thorough investigations and prompt corrective actions; complainants systematically</p>

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	informed throughout process and of final outcomes with explanations; regular review and continuous improvement documented; zero tolerance for retaliation with explicit policy; may include independent third-party escalation option for unresolved disputes; annual reporting to community on complaints received and actions taken.
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases with community interface. Phases with no credible community-affecting impacts may be assigned N/A
Aggregation Method	Weighted aggregation by worker-hours: $LC3_product = \frac{\sum(\text{Score_phase} \times \text{Worker-hours_phase})}{\sum(\text{Worker-hours_phase})}$
Weighting Basis	N/A
Threshold Gate	<p>FLAG 1 — CRITICAL: No grievance mechanism Trigger: Any phase with Score = 0 (no mechanism exists). Interpretation: The complete absence of a grievance channel means the local community has no formal way to raise concerns about operations affecting their health, safety, or quality of life. Action: Establish at minimum a basic accessible channel (email or phone) with documented procedure.</p>

LC4: Local employment in PHBV operations

Indicator ID	LC4
Stakeholder Category	Local Community
Social Aspect	Local employment
Indicator Name	Local employment in product operations
Observational Unit	Product operations
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Percentage of workers directly engaged in product operations who currently reside in the same primary administrative division (province or equivalent) as the facility where they work.</p> <p>For this assessment: "local" is defined as current residence in the same province or equivalent primary administrative division as the workplace, regardless of the worker's origin prior to employment. This reflects that the primary mechanism of local economic impact is wage expenditure in the local economy and integration into the regional labour market — both of which apply to any worker currently residing in the province, irrespective of whether they were living there before being hired.</p> <p>Includes: workers directly engaged in production, processing, quality control, maintenance, and logistics attributable to product operations.</p>

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Unit	Excludes: general corporate staff (CEO, CFO, HR for entire company) not attributable to product operations; workers in other product lines at multi-product facilities. %
Reference Scale	0 points: < 20% local workforce in product operations 1 point: 20–40% local workforce 2 points: 41–60% local workforce. 3 points: 61–80% local workforce. 4 points: > 80% local workforce.
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	All phases
Aggregation Method	Weighted aggregation by worker-hours: $LC4_product = \frac{\sum(\text{Score_phase} \times \text{Worker-hours_phase})}{\sum(\text{Worker-hours_phase})}$ Where: Worker-hours_phase = total worker-hours per tonne of product for that phase
Weighting Basis	N/A
Threshold Gate	N/A

Consumers

CO1: Consumer product information quality (COMPOSITE)

Indicator ID	CO1
Stakeholder Category	Consumers
Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	Consumer product information quality (COMPOSITE)
Observational Unit	Organisation (B2C only)
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Composite indicator (0–4 scale) assessing the quality and completeness of voluntary consumer-facing product information across three weighted dimensions: (1) End-of-life information (CO1.2, 50%), (2) Consumer communication channel accessibility (CO1.4, 30%), (3) Voluntary sustainability information quality (CO1.3, 20%).</p> <p>Applicable only to B2C phases with consumer-facing packaging. B2B phases (fermentation, compounding, upstream processing) = N/A.</p> <p>Additionally, CO1.1 operates as a mandatory regulatory compliance check independent of the composite score. CO1.1 non-compliance triggers Flag 1 (INFORMATIVE or CRITICAL) reported alongside the composite score. Critical non-compliance caps the composite score at maximum 1,0.</p>

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Unit	Composite score 0–4 (dimensionless)
Reference Scale	<p>0,0 — no EoL guidance, no sustainability claims, no accessible contact channels.</p> <p>1,0: Minimal voluntary information across all dimensions. Also the maximum achievable score when Flag 1 CRITICAL is active (critical regulatory non-compliance).</p> <p>2,0: Basic voluntary information across dimensions.</p> <p>3,0: Strong EoL guidance, substantiated sustainability claims, accessible communication channels.</p> <p>4,0: comprehensive certified EoL guidance, multiple verified sustainability claims with independent verification, comprehensive accessible contact channels including non-digital options.</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	Use phase; End-of-life. B2C organisations with consumer-facing packaging only.
Aggregation Method	<p>STEP 1 - Calculate composite score per organization: $CO1_org = (CO1.2 \times 0.50) + (CO1.3 \times 0.20) + (CO1.4 \times 0.30)$ Where each sub-indicator CO1.2-CO1.4 is normalized to 0-4 scale before weighting.</p> <p>STEP 2 - Aggregate across lifecycle phases: $CO1_product = \Sigma(CO1_org \times Worker\text{-}hours_org) / \Sigma(Worker\text{-}hours_org)$ Where Worker-hours_org = total worker-hours per tonne of PHBV attributed to B2C packaging operations for that organisation (provisional D6.10 driver; target driver D6.13: consumer units sold).</p>
Weighting Basis	<p>CO1.2: 50%; CO1.4: 30%; CO1.3: 20%</p> <p>Composite formula: $CO1 = (CO1.2 \times 0.50) + (CO1.3 \times 0.20) + (CO1.4 \times 0.30)$</p>
Threshold Gate	<p>FLAG 1 INFORMATIVE — Minor regulatory non-compliance (CO1.1 check): One or more minor mandatory elements absent in any B2C organisation (lot/batch traceability code, declaration of conformity not referenced on pack, instructions for safe use absent where self-evident, compostability certification indication absent per Art. 13.5 RD 1055/2022). Effect: reported explicitly alongside CO1 composite score with documentation of absent element(s). No cap applied to composite score.</p> <p>FLAG 1 CRITICAL — Critical regulatory non-compliance (CO1.1 check): One or more critical mandatory elements absent or prohibited claims present in any B2C organisation: responsible party identification absent, 'for food contact' indication absent where not self-evident, or prohibited environmental claims present per Art. 13.3 RD 1055/2022. Effect: CO1 composite score for that organisation capped at maximum 1,0. If calculated score already below 1,0, lower value retained. Nature of critical non-compliance documented explicitly in assessment reporting. Flag 1 CRITICAL takes precedence over Flag 1 INFORMATIVE if both present simultaneously.</p>

CO1.1: Mandatory regulatory information

Indicator ID	CO1.1
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Stakeholder Category	Consumers
Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	Mandatory regulatory information on packaging
Observational Unit	Organisation (B2C only)
Is Sub-Indicator	No — prerequisite compliance check. Feeds Flag 1 of CO1 composite. Not included in CO1 composite score calculation.
Measurement Detail	<p>Presence of mandatory regulatory information on consumer-facing packaging of the PHBV-containing product. This is a compliance check, not a performance indicator — it establishes whether the minimum legal baseline is met before assessing voluntary consumer information performance (CO1.2–CO1.4).</p> <p>Mandatory elements are classified as critical or minor based on their direct impact on the consumer's ability to protect their interests and make informed decisions. Critical elements trigger Flag 1 CRITICAL with cap effect on CO1 composite score; minor elements trigger Flag 1 INFORMATIVE without cap effect.</p> <p>Primary regulatory reference: Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 (Art. 15 — labelling obligations; Art. 16 — declaration of conformity; Art. 17 — traceability). For plastic food contact materials, declaration of conformity additionally required under Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 (Art. 15). For compostable plastic packaging: Art. 13.5 RD 1055/2022 requires indication of compostability certification (UNE EN 13432:2001) and 'do not litter' instruction.</p> <p>Mandatory elements assessed: (1) 'for food contact' indication or fork-and-glass symbol, unless self-evident by characteristics; (2) name and address of responsible party established in the EU; (3) lot/batch traceability identification; (4) instructions for safe and adequate use where necessary; (5) declaration of conformity available for plastic FCM; (6) for compostable plastics: compostability certification indication per Art. 13.5 RD 1055/2022; (7) absence of prohibited environmental claims — terms such as "biodegradable", "eco-friendly", "respectful with the environment" or any equivalent likely to induce littering or mislead consumers about end-of-life behaviour, without specified conditions or certification, are explicitly prohibited per Art. 13.3 RD 1055/2022.</p>
Unit	Compliant / Minor non-compliant / Critical non-compliant
Reference Scale	<p>COMPLIANT: All mandatory elements present. No flag triggered. CO1 composite score calculated normally.</p> <p>MINOR NON-COMPLIANT: One or more minor elements absent. Triggers Flag 1 INFORMATIVE. CO1 composite score calculated normally without cap. Mandatory documentation of absent element(s) in assessment reporting.</p> <p>Minor elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lot/batch traceability code absent • Declaration of conformity not referenced on pack (available on request but not linked) • Instructions for safe use absent where use is self-evident • Compostability certification indication absent (Art. 13.5 RD 1055/2022)

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	<p>CRITICAL NON-COMPLIANT: One or more critical elements absent or prohibited claims present. Triggers Flag 1 CRITICAL + cap of CO1 composite score to maximum 1,0. Mandatory documentation of absent/violated element(s) in assessment reporting.</p> <p>Critical elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of responsible party absent (name and EU address) — consumer cannot claim or contact • 'For food contact' indication or fork-and-glass symbol absent where not self-evident by characteristics — consumer cannot identify food contact suitability • Prohibited environmental claims present (Art. 13.3 RD 1055/2022) — actively misleading consumer on end-of-life behaviour
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	Use phase
Aggregation Method	<p>If multiple B2C organisations assessed: report compliance status individually per organisation. Critical non-compliance in any single organisation triggers Flag 1 CRITICAL for the product-level CO1 assessment regardless of other organisations' compliance status. Minor non-compliance in any single organisation triggers Flag 1 INFORMATIVE unless a Critical non-compliance is already present, in which case Flag 1 CRITICAL takes precedence.</p>
Weighting Basis	N/A
Threshold Gate	<p>FLAG 1 INFORMATIVE — Minor non-compliance: One or more minor mandatory elements absent in any B2C organisation assessed. Effect: reported explicitly alongside CO1 composite score with documentation of absent element(s). No cap applied to CO1 composite score.</p> <p>FLAG 2 CRITICAL — Critical non-compliance: One or more critical mandatory elements absent, or prohibited environmental claims present (Art. 13.3 RD 1055/2022), in any B2C organisation assessed. Effect: CO1 composite score capped at maximum 1,0. If calculated composite score is already below 1,0, the lower value is retained. Nature of critical non-compliance documented explicitly in assessment reporting.</p>

CO1.2: End-of-life information

Indicator ID	CO1.2
Stakeholder Category	Consumers
Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	End-of-life information
Observational Unit	Organisation (B2C only)

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Is Sub-Indicator	Yes
Measurement Detail	<p>Quality and completeness of voluntary end-of-life disposal information provided to consumers on packaging, beyond mandatory certification requirements (those are assessed under CO1.1). Evaluates whether the information is actionable — i.e. whether a consumer reading the packaging can make a correct and informed disposal decision without additional research.</p> <p>For PHBV specifically, correct end-of-life management is functionally critical: incorrect disposal (e.g. placing industrial-compostable packaging in home composting or conventional recycling) negates the environmental benefits of the material. The social value of this information is therefore directly tied to its actionability, not merely its presence.</p> <p>Excludes: compostability certification indication (assessed under CO1.1 as mandatory per Art. 13.5 RD 1055/2022); prohibited environmental claims (assessed under CO1.1 per Art. 13.3 RD 1055/2022).</p>
Unit	{0.0, 0.5, 1.0}
Reference Scale	<p>0,0: No voluntary end-of-life information provided beyond mandatory certification indication. Consumer has no guidance on how or where to dispose of the packaging correctly.</p> <p>0,5: Basic actionable information — disposal pathway clearly stated and accurate (e.g. "industrial composting only — do not place in home compost or recycling bin"). Consumer can make a correct disposal decision. May lack detail on conditions or infrastructure guidance, but information present is accurate and unambiguous.</p> <p>1,0: Comprehensive actionable information — all of the following present: (a) disposal pathway clearly stated; (b) specific conditions where relevant (timeframe, temperature, facility type); (c) guidance on where to dispose (QR to facility locator, reference to municipal collection service, or equivalent). Consumer can not only make the correct disposal decision but can also act on it without additional research.</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	Use phase - B2C consumer-facing packaging only.
Aggregation Method	<p>Weighted aggregation by worker-hours:</p> $CO1_product = \frac{\sum(\text{Score_CO1_org} \times \text{Worker-hours_org})}{\sum(\text{Worker-hours_org})}$ <p>Where Worker-hours_org = total worker-hours per tonne of PHBV attributed to B2C packaging operations for that organisation (provisional D6.10 driver; target driver D6.13: consumer units sold).</p>
Weighting Basis	50% of parent composite
Threshold Gate	N/A

CO1.3: Sustainability information

Indicator ID	CO1.3
Stakeholder Category	Consumers

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Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	Voluntary sustainability information quality
Observational Unit	Organisation (B2C only)
Is Sub-Indicator	Yes
Measurement Detail	<p>Presence and quality of voluntary sustainability information on consumer-facing packaging beyond mandatory regulatory requirements, enabling consumers to make informed purchasing decisions based on verified sustainability attributes of the product.</p> <p>Evaluates whether sustainability claims are specific, verifiable and substantiated — not merely present. Focuses on bio-based origin, content certification, and quantified environmental performance data with independent verification.</p> <p>Excludes: compostability certifications (OK Compost, TÜV Austria, Seedling) — mandatory indication assessed under CO1.1 (Art. 13.5 RD 1055/2022). Excludes voluntary end-of-life disposal information (instructions, conditions, infrastructure guidance) — assessed under CO1.2. Excludes prohibited vague claims ("eco-friendly", "biodegradable" without conditions) — assessed under CO1.1 Flag 1 per Art. 13.3 RD 1055/2022.</p>
Unit	{0.0, 0.5, 1.0}
Reference Scale	<p>0,0: No voluntary sustainability information present beyond mandatory requirements. Or: sustainability claims present but not specific or not verifiable (e.g. "made from natural materials" without quantification or certification) — note these do not reach the threshold of Art. 13.3 RD 1055/2022 prohibition but provide no meaningful information to the consumer.</p> <p>0,5: At least one specific and verifiable sustainability claim present: verified bio-based content certification with certificate number visible or accessible, OR specific bio-based percentage stated with identified source, OR one quantified environmental performance data point with identified methodology. Consumer has substantiated information on at least one sustainability attribute enabling a more informed purchasing decision.</p> <p>1,0: Multiple complementary verified sustainability claims present: bio-based certification AND quantified environmental performance data (carbon footprint, LCA summary) with independent verification AND access to full documentation (QR or weblink to sustainability report or EPD). Consumer has a comprehensive and verifiable picture of the product's sustainability profile.</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	Use phase - B2C consumer-facing packaging only.
Aggregation Method	<p>Weighted aggregation by worker-hours:</p> $CO1_product = \frac{\sum(Score_CO1_org \times Worker_hours_org)}{\sum(Worker_hours_org)}$ <p>Where Worker-hours_org = total worker-hours per tonne of PHBV attributed to B2C packaging operations for that organisation (provisional D6.10 driver; target driver D6.13: consumer units sold).</p>

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Weighting Basis	20% of parent composite - lowest weight among 3 subs (useful voluntary info but not critical for product function)
Threshold Gate	N/A

CO1.4: Consumer communication channels

Indicator ID	CO1.4
Stakeholder Category	Consumers
Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	Consumer communication channel accessibility
Observational Unit	Organisation (B2C only)
Is Sub-Indicator	Yes
Measurement Detail	<p>Accessibility of voluntary communication channels provided to consumers for product information requests, usage questions, and general enquiries, beyond the mandatory responsible party identification required under Reg. (EC) 1935/2004 Art. 15.1.</p> <p>Evaluates whether a consumer encountering the product can actively reach the organisation through accessible, functional channels — not merely identify who is responsible. The distinction from CO1.1 is explicit: CO1.1 assesses presence of mandatory identification; CO1.4 assesses voluntary provision of active communication infrastructure.</p> <p>Scoring based on number and accessibility of voluntary channels provided, with recognition that QR codes effectively compensate for physical space constraints on secondary packaging.</p> <p>Excludes: mandatory responsible party name and address (assessed under CO1.1). Excludes complaint handling effectiveness — assessed under CO2.</p>
Unit	{0.0, 0.5, 1.0}
Reference Scale	<p>0,0: No voluntary communication channels provided beyond mandatory responsible party identification. Consumer can identify who is responsible but has no accessible means to actively contact the organisation.</p> <p>0,5: At least one voluntary active channel clearly visible on packaging or accessible via QR: email address OR phone number OR website URL with identifiable contact section. Consumer can reach the organisation through at least one channel with reasonable effort.</p> <p>1,0: Multiple complementary voluntary channels provided and accessible: at least two of the following clearly present — phone, email, website contact section, QR to product information page with contact options. Channels are functional and verified (QR destination active, URL accessible). Accessible to consumers with different preferences and digital literacy levels — at least one non-digital channel present alongside any digital options.</p>
Lifecycle Phase Applicability	Use phase — B2C consumer-facing packaging only.

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Aggregation Method	<p>Weighted aggregation by worker-hours: $CO1_product = \frac{\sum(\text{Score_CO1_org} \times \text{Worker-hours_org})}{\sum(\text{Worker-hours_org})}$ </p> <p>Where Worker-hours_org = total worker-hours per tonne of PHBV attributed to B2C packaging operations for that organisation (provisional D6.10 driver; target driver D6.13: consumer units sold).</p>
Weighting Basis	30% of parent composite
Threshold Gate	N/A

CO2: Consumer complaints mechanism

Indicator ID	CO2
Stakeholder Category	Consumers
Social Aspect	Health and safety
Indicator Name	Consumer complaints mechanism effectiveness
Observational Unit	Organisation (B2C only)
Is Sub-Indicator	No
Measurement Detail	<p>Assessment of the effectiveness of the consumer complaint and query handling mechanism for the PHBV-containing product, based on ISO 10002:2018 principles. Evaluates whether consumers have a genuine, accessible, and responsive means of raising concerns about the product — covering accessibility of the mechanism, clarity of procedure, responsiveness, and evidence of continuous improvement.</p> <p>Distinct from CO1.4 (which measures whether communication channels exist and are visible on packaging) — CO2 measures what happens when a consumer uses those channels to submit a complaint or query: whether the process is effective, responsive, and trustworthy.</p>
Unit	Score on 0–4 scale (dimensionless)
Reference Scale	<p>0: No mechanism exists — consumers have no accessible means to submit complaints or queries about the product. Or: mechanism exists nominally but systematically fails to respond to or acknowledge complaints (performative mechanism with no actual function). Or: evidence of retaliation or intimidation against consumers for complaining.</p> <p>1: Informal ad-hoc mechanism only — consumers can reach the organisation through a single channel (phone or email) but there is no documented procedure, no consistent tracking, handling is case-by-case with inconsistent response times, and consumers are not systematically informed of outcomes.</p> <p>2: Basic formal mechanism — at least one defined channel communicated to consumers, complaints are acknowledged and recorded with reference numbers, investigations occur but response times are slow or inconsistent (typically >30 days), some corrective actions taken but not systematically documented, limited communication to complainants about resolution.</p>

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<p>Lifecycle Phase Applicability</p>	<p>3: Good mechanism — multiple accessible channels clearly communicated to consumers (on packaging, website, or point of sale), documented procedure with defined steps and timeframes, consistent acknowledgement and investigation, resolution typically within 30 days, complainants informed of outcome with explanation, some evidence of systematic learning from complaints (pattern identification, corrective actions).</p> <p>4: Excellent mechanism — all Score 3 elements present plus: proactive monitoring of consumer feedback beyond reactive complaints (post-purchase surveys, review platform monitoring), highly responsive with thorough investigations and prompt corrective actions, complainants systematically informed throughout the process with detailed explanations, strong continuous improvement culture with documented root cause analysis and preventive actions, regular management reporting on complaint trends, may include independent third-party escalation pathway.</p> <p>Use phase — B2C organisations with direct consumer market presence only. B2B phases = N/A.</p>
<p>Aggregation Method</p>	<p>Weighted aggregation by worker-hours: $CO2_{product} = \frac{\sum(Score_{org} \times Worker\text{-}hours_{org})}{\sum(Worker\text{-}hours_{org})}$ Where: Worker-hours_{org} = total worker-hours per tonne of PHBV attributed to B2C packaging operations for that organisation (provisional D6.10 driver; target driver D6.13: consumer units sold).</p>
<p>Weighting Basis</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Threshold Gate</p>	<p>N/A</p>